

Novafert

Deliverable 3.3 – Lessons learnt from the Specific Action Plans

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<i>Version:</i>	<i>Final Version</i>
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<i>Date:</i>	<i>02-09-2024</i>
<i>Dissemination level:</i>	<i>Public (PU)</i>
<i>Grant Agreement N°:</i>	<i>101060835</i>
<i>Starting Date:</i>	<i>01-09-2022</i>
<i>Duration:</i>	<i>36 months</i>
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Executive Summary

The objective of this document is to present the Regional Specific Action Plans developed for each of the seven regions participating in the NOVAFERT project.

Each Regional Specific Action Plan (RSAP) consists of a set of area-specific actions that aim to overcome the barriers and foster the use of alternative fertilisers in agriculture in each target region. These RSAPs provide the main issues identified from NOVAFERT regional analyses, as well as details on the ways in which lessons learnt from the cooperation within NOVAFERT consortium, the outcomes of the Regional Working Groups' work and the conclusions of the participatory workshops can be explored and horizontally applied towards the general goal of successfully improve the use of alternative fertilisers in the target regions.

The RSAPs are structured according to the priority areas set out in the General Action Plan (GAP) (Deliverable 3.2). This GAP, structured in 3 different levels, has as general objective or goal (first level) the demonstration of the technical, economic, and environmental feasibility and safe use of a wide portfolio of alternative fertilising products containing recovered nutrients from different waste streams. The specific objectives are identified as priority areas (second level) and are set out to guide the target regions into the successful creation of the RSAPs, which will be composed of practical steps for implementation (third level), concrete activities to be executed at short, medium and long term.

Figure 1. Levels for the development of a Regional Specific Action Plan

The RSAPs have been developed thanks to the outputs of several previous and ongoing tasks; on the one hand, those related to the specific needs of each target region, like *task 3.1*

on SWOT and PEST analyses uptake of alternative fertilising products and task 3.2 on development of a general strategy (Action Plan) to overcome the barriers and, on the other hand, those related to the identification, mobilisation and integration of relevant regional stakeholders from each of the relevant sectors according to the concerned waste streams, such as task 5.1 on stakeholder engagement and consultation, task 5.2 on cross-network collaboration – establishment of Regional Working Groups (RWGs) and task 5.3 on participatory workshops. A stakeholder analysis was the preliminary step where the most relevant stakeholders of each region were gathered. Then, using the feedback of the RWGs, a critical issue analysis (SWOT and PEST analyses) was delivered for each region to identify the key gaps and issues that should be the focus of the activities to be developed in the RSAPs, developed in the framework of the GAP and with the support of relevant stakeholders attending the participatory workshops. The mentioned proposed activities of the RSAPs are the ones reported in the present deliverable.

As mentioned in previous deliverables, the activities performed are framed in two dimensions: on the one hand, the target region, and on the other hand, the waste streams targeted for each region from which nutrients to further develop alternative fertilisers will be extracted. The 7 project regions are listed in alphabetical order, and their associated waste streams following a colour code:

- Belgium – Flanders. Targeted secondary raw material: **Animal manure** and **digestate**. Regional leader: UGent.
- Croatia – Continental Croatia. Targeted secondary raw material: **Bio-waste**, **animal manure** and **digestate**. Regional leader: IPS.
- Finland – South-West Finland. Targeted secondary raw material: **Bio-waste**, **digestate** and **animal manure**. Regional leader: LUKE.
- Ireland – Wicklow / Carlow / Wexford. Targeted secondary raw material: **Bio-waste** and **biological by-products**. Regional leader: TEAGASC.
- Poland – South-East Poland. Targeted secondary raw material: **Sewage sludge**, **animal manure** and **digestate**. Regional leader: MEERI.
- Spain – Andalusia. Targeted secondary raw material: **Wastewater** and **sewage sludge**. Regional leader: BIOAZUL.
- Spain – Catalonia. Targeted secondary raw material: **Animal manure**. Regional leader: UVIC.

Figure 2. NOVAFERT regions and their associated waste streams

The present deliverable has been structured in five sections to facilitate its lecture: introduction, overall methodology, RSAPs executive summaries, RSAPs as such and general conclusions.

The executive summaries (section 3) include a short overview of the regional characterisation done for Deliverable 3.1 to focus the reader on the region under discussion and the waste stream(s) tackled, as well as a “main findings” section summarising the RSAPs outputs using the table format, to make it clearer and more visual. This allows the reader getting an overall impression of the RSAPs and can be separated as a stand-alone document.

The RSAPs as such (section 4) include extended information on the actions proposed, as well as a description of the concrete methodology followed by each regional cluster to gather all needed information (being the participatory workshops of WP5 a key tool in most cases).

The Regional Specific Action Plans (RSAPs) created by the NOVAFERT project represent a considerable effort to adapt the marketing and uptake of alternative fertilisers across seven European regions. Each region's action plan is systematically prepared to meet its own socioeconomic, environmental, and regulatory landscapes, reflecting the complexity and variability of challenges faced in the transition towards sustainable agricultural practices. The NOVAFERT initiative shows a localised approach to global environmental concerns, notably in terms of reducing dependency on synthetic fertilisers and promoting a circular economy.

Cross-Regional Insights and Impact

Across all seven regions, common themes emerge, including the need for stronger regulatory frameworks, increased public awareness, and the development of financial incentives to support the adoption of alternative fertilisers. The RSAPs collectively advocate for a shift in agricultural practices that not only meets local needs but also aligns with broader EU

sustainability goals. By focusing on region-specific actions, the NOVAFERT project ensures that the transition towards sustainable fertilisation practices is both practical and effective, addressing the distinct challenges faced by each region.

In conclusion, the RSAPs provide a clear roadmap for each region to follow, ensuring that the lessons learned from the NOVAFERT project can be applied in a way that maximises local benefits while contributing to the global challenge of sustainable agriculture. These plans are dynamic and will continue to evolve as the regions implement the proposed actions, monitor their progress, and adapt to new developments and challenges in the agricultural sector.

1. Introduction

One of the main objectives of NOVAFERT project is the development of a portfolio of support policies and legislative instruments suitable for local deployment in the EC regions through 7 specific action plans and 4 policy briefs. The objective is indeed the main outcome of WP3, namely “Supporting policy formulation to overcome existing barriers and implementation at local and EU level”, and will be achieved through the successful implementation of five tasks, one of which is the focus of this deliverable:

- Task 3.3: Development of 7 region specific Action Plans for fast uptake of alternative fertilising products (October 2023 – August 2024).

The main aim of this task is to develop strategies and recommendations to pave the way for a more extensive use of alternative fertilisers. For practical implementation, due to regional differences, the General Action Plan (GAP, task 3.2) needs to be adapted to the 7 target regions into Regional Specific Action Plans (RSAPs). The RSAP is a document providing details and guidelines on how the lessons learnt from the cooperation among the NOVAFERT project consortium may be exploited, specified, and applied in different geographical clusters to improve the use of alternative fertilisers in the targeted European regions.

The RSAPs include key aspects and guidelines that meet the specific needs of targeted regions while focusing on a description of actions outlined in the GAP, and it is oriented to specific measures adapted to each regional context. Hence, they establish measures (i.e., specific actions) needed to address each of the strategic issues set in the GAP. These RSAPs include actions where the consortium members worked with local actors in their regions to build the strategies following a participatory approach which can move forward alternative fertilisers uptake agenda, showing the opportunities in each target region and defining specific measures to take advantage of those opportunities.

As a result, NOVAFERT has developed RSAPs on the seven target European regions to enhance alternative fertilisers use at regional and even national levels. The necessity of strategic planning at regional level with the development of RSAPs during the project has engaged stakeholders in a multi-level approach to raise awareness on the benefits of the alternative fertilisers use and to plan in advance their promotion in each regional cluster.

2. Overall methodology

2.1. The Action Plan

An Action Plan is a document providing details on how the lessons learnt from the cooperation among the project consortium will be exploited in order to enhance the use of alternative fertilising products containing recovered nutrients from 6 different waste streams in 7 different EU regions. It specifies the nature of the actions to be implemented, their timeframe, the players involved, the costs (if any) and potential funding sources (if any). In other words, it is a structured set of objectives, results, actions and activities outlining the pathway to reach one or more goals.

The action plan may include the following information:

1. General information: partners involved, countries/regions involved.
2. Action plan context: who/what does the action plan aim to impact, name of instruments to be addressed.
3. Details of the actions envisaged: background (description of the lessons learnt from the project that constitute the basis for the development of the Action Plan), actions (list and description of the actions to be implemented), players involved in each action, timeframe of each action, costs of each action, funding sources.

2.2. Regional Specific Action Plan Framework within NOVAFERT

The RSAPs have been produced in the 7 target EU regions of the NOVAFERT project, being focused on their assigned waste stream(s) (6 different ones in total). Regions are listed in alphabetical order:

- Belgium – Flanders. Targeted secondary raw material: **Animal manure** and **digestate**. Regional leader: UGent.
- Croatia – Continental Croatia. Targeted secondary raw material: **Bio-waste**, **animal manure** and **digestate**. Regional leader: IPS.
- Finland – South-West Finland. Targeted secondary raw material: **Bio-waste**, **digestate** and **animal manure**. Regional leader: LUKE.
- Ireland – Wicklow / Carlow / Wexford. Targeted secondary raw material: **Bio-waste** and **biological by-products**. Regional leader: TEAGASC.
- Poland – South-East Poland. Targeted secondary raw material: **Sewage sludge**, **animal manure** and **digestate**. Regional leader: MEERI.
- Spain – Andalusia. Targeted secondary raw material: **Wastewater** and **sewage sludge**. Regional leader: BIOAZUL.
- Spain – Catalonia. Targeted secondary raw material: **Animal manure**. Regional leader: UVIC.

Figure 3. NOVAFERT regions and their associated waste streams

Each of the local partners that are responsible for elaborating the RSAP has undertaken a series of activities in close collaboration with their corresponding Regional Work Group (RWG). All RWGs have been established in the framework of task 5.2, "Cross-network collaboration – Establishment of Regional Working Groups". A series of open participatory workshops have been organised in most regions to get the needed information. At these workshops, a series of intensive discussions were conducted being focused on each region critical issues linked with to the use of alternative fertilisers. All arguments claimed by the key player participants were documented to build up the present RSAPs. However, workshops have not been the only tools used by the partners to get this info. Smaller meetings, individual discussions, etc. have been also held to understand what is needed in each of the concerned regions.

According to the previous tasks, there are several topics that can be considered as transversal, even when dealing with different waste streams in different regions. Some of these common concerns are:

- **Regulatory framework**, that has appeared independently from the region and the waste stream analysed. However, sometimes has been considered as a negative aspect (restrictive character of some current laws) and, others, as positive (upcoming policies, existing recommendations, political willingness, etc.).
- **Social perception**, which traditionally has not been as good as desired due to the lack of information for consumers and lack of information and/or training of farmers, but at the same time is improving thanks to the increasing environmental awareness of the general public and the increasing demand for ecological products.

- **Financial coverage**, as investment (e.g., new installations) and/or maintenance costs (e.g., energy consumption) still create some reluctance, but at the same time the lack of critical raw materials makes indispensable looking for alternatives, and at the same time paves the way for a met market for secondary raw materials.
- **Quality of the final products**, as the efficiency of alternative fertilisers needs to be improved, as well as other technical aspects like the storing options, what entails a further need of research and development.

These issues (among others) have been commonly raised by the consortium members and are chained to each regional cluster as basic issues for the development of the Regional Specific Action Plans.

2.3. Formulation of the NOVAFERT Regional Specific Action Plans

To best serve the purpose of the RSAPs, focusing and covering all critical aspects, the strategic planning has been divided into three different levels:

Figure 4. Levels for the development of a Regional Specific Action Plan

First level

General objective. Demonstrate the technical, economic, and environmental feasibility and safe use of a wide portfolio of alternative fertilising products containing recovered nutrients from different waste streams.

Second level

Priority areas. These are the main areas/fields of the implementation strategy to achieve the general objective (first level). The priority areas selected are:

1. Legal Framework.
2. Political willingness.
3. Research and technological development.
4. New business models.
5. Financial incentives.
6. Self-sufficiency.
7. Public acceptance.
8. Environmental protection.

Third level

In the last step (primary focus of Deliverable 3.3) every region defines the tasks or actions required to achieve every result. This is the most empirical and simpler level, and has to contemplate every action needed to reach a result.

The RSAPs have taken the GAP (Deliverable 3.2) as the common strategy and have established measures (i.e., actions) needed to address each of the strategic issues set in the GAP.

In order to formulate the desired actions, some guiding questions have been provided to the partners for each priority area, so they could use them to conduct the discussions with the key players in their regions.

Priority area 1: Legal framework.

- How can we combat non-compatibility of certification schemes across the EU?
- What are the challenging / complex national regulations and policies, lack of knowledge and uncertainty on the registration, certification and labelling regulatory framework?

- What kind of regulatory framework needs to be put in place to ensure the safe use of alternative fertilisers?

Priority area 2: Political willingness.

- How can we increase the willingness of the local and regional governments to look for solutions to substitute synthetic fertilisers?
- How can we promote/encourage farmer to use certain alternative fertilisers (e.g. subsidies, knowledge transfer, capacity building etc...)?
- How is your local administration promoting circular economy practices via agricultural practices?

Priority area 3: Research and technological development.

- What are the key regional research opportunities in this area (improving processing methods, increase nutritional content and availability, formulating new products, including digital tools etc...)?
- What is needed for technological development to successfully implement innovative solutions in this area? Is there sufficient space for innovation in this field to thrive?
- What local support is in place for research and development of alternative fertilisers? How can this be further encouraged?

Priority area 4: New business models.

- How can the circular economy model help contribute to the transformation of waste materials into valuable sources of nutrients?
- How can we help to encourage the creation of green jobs in this area? What new employment opportunities are available?
- How can the startup sector get more involved and what opportunities may there be in for social entrepreneurs? Which startups are already active in the area?
- How relevant are alternative fertilisers for the organic farming sector? What synergies could be further developed?

Priority area 5: Financial incentives.

- What kind of financial support mechanisms need to be put in place to allow for the implementation of installations?
- What support mechanisms are already in place locally and are these well promoted? If not, what needs to happen to improve this situation?
- Are there financing models available elsewhere that could be adopted locally?

Priority area 6: Self-sufficiency.

- Facing mineral fertilisers scarcity, how could alternative fertilisers serve or have the potential to replace / substitute them and for example reduce dependency on imports?

Priority area 7: Public acceptance.

- What is the public perception/understanding of alternative fertilisers?
- How can this perception/understanding be shifted towards even greater understanding that this is an opportunity to reduce our carbon footprint and work towards ecological solutions?

Priority area 8: Environmental protection.

- In your region what environmental benefits can be associated with the use and promotion of alternative fertilisers?
- How can we encourage the narrative of climate change mitigation and increase of soil resilience against extreme weather events?

3. Regional Specific Action Plans Executive Summaries

3.1. Belgium – Flanders

3.1.1. Regional characterisation

Socio-economic characterisation of the region. Flanders is the Dutch-speaking region of northern Belgium, mostly flat with a small stretch of coastline on the North Sea. Despite accounting for just 45% of Belgium's land, it has the largest population, with 6,653,062 (or 57%) of the country's 11,431,406 residents, with Antwerp being the most populous province. Flanders accounts for 45% of the country's landmass, covering 13,522 km². Dutch is the primary language spoken in the area; however, most residents are also fluent in English and French.

Flanders is divided into two geographical regions: the northwestern coastal Yser basin plain, consisting mainly of sand dunes and clayey alluvial soils in the polders, and the central plain, that begins with similar soils along the lowermost Scheldt basin, a smooth, slowly rising fertile area irrigated by many waterways with an average height of about five meters above sea level. The region has wide valleys of its rivers upstream and sandy soils at around thirty meters in the Campine region to the east. Near its southern borders, close to Wallonia, there is significantly harsher ground, richer in calcium, with low hills reaching up to 150 m and small valleys, and marl caves may be found in the Meuse basin on the eastern border with the Netherlands.

The industries with the most economic growth include transportation and communications, health and social services, business services, and equipment manufacturing. The Flemish economy is heavily export-oriented. Flanders' exports account for 82.0% of Belgium's total export volume (2021). Flemish exports experienced robust growth in 2021 following a decrease in 2020 due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The region's most successful export products include chemicals and pharmaceuticals, transportation equipment and components, machinery and

equipment, mineral products, and plastics. Pig farming is the most significant economic activity in Flanders' agricultural and horticultural sectors.

Agriculture. Flanders's agriculture mainly produces vegetables forage plants and cereals (Eurostat, 2019). The agricultural areas are most prevalent in the north, where there are formerly seabeds that have fertile soils. Agriculture benefits from the mild as well. Sugar beets, grains, and potatoes are the most significant crops.

In addition to agriculture, meat and dairy products are key commodities as well. Pig alone contributes to a fourth of agricultural export value. Flanders has the most pig farms, whereas Wallonia has the largest grain output.

Fertilising products sector in relation to the waste streams studied in the region: animal manure and digestate. The nitrogen (N) ranges for cattle, pigs, and poultry are comparable. The distribution varies by province (NUTS-2). Cattle and pig nitrogen output are higher in the west, in accordance with larger animal production. In 2021 around 4,250,857 tonnes of animal manure were treated in Flanders. This tonnage equates to 39.8 million kg of nitrogen extracted from cattle manure. In 2020, 4,632,182 tonnes (or 43,474,955 kg N) were processed. Flanders now operates 142 manure processing units. Regarding nitrogen processing, pig and poultry manure accounted for 88.9% of total manure processing, with 17.1 million kg N (43.0%) and 18.3 million kg N (45.9%), respectively. In terms of quantity, 2,812,050 tonnes of pig manure (66.2%) and 602 041 tonnes of poultry dung (14.2%) were treated.

Regulatory and institutional framework. In Flanders, manure use and management are strictly regulated by the manure decree and the manure action plans. All farmers with a production of at least 300 kg P₂O₅ have to submit a manure declaration. The whole Flanders region is designated as a nitrate vulnerable zone, which means that the maximum application standard for manure is 170 kg N per ha, in line with the Nitrate Directive. The Nitrates Directive implementation via the Flemish Manure decree since 1991 is rated as having a neutral effect.

Digestate products resulting from co-fermented animal manure with plant-based input streams are considered as 'animal manure' and are therefore limited in Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZ) to 170 kg N/ha/y.

3.1.2. Main findings

The waste streams **animal manure** and **digestate** have been considered as secondary raw materials' sources for producing alternative fertilisers in Flanders region, Belgium. The main actions outlined per each priority area are summarised in the following table.

Table 1. Main actions outlined in the RSAP of Flanders, Belgium

What will we do?	How will we do it	When is it being proposed?	Who will be responsible?	Status (Completed / In Process / Awaiting)	Possible Funding Sources
<p>Priority area 1: Legal Framework</p>					
Incentive policy.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Interdisciplinary collaboration. 2. Removing legal barriers. 3. Lead by example. 4. Research into related legislation. 5. Consultation with the Flemish entities. 	Long term vision (by 2050).	Nutricycle Vlaanderen, VLM, VMM, OVAM, L&V, Dept. Environment, EWI, VLAIO, Boerenbond, ABS, FEVIA, VCM, Aquafin.	<i>In Process</i>	Regular operation of organisations.
Communication: translate national and international policy developments and research into the Flemish context and disseminate nutrient-related information.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nutricycle Vlaanderen Flemish consultation platform website, as well as social media, newsletters, trade press articles. 2. Nutricycle Vlaanderen Flemish consultation platform brochures. 	4-monthly newsletter. 3 brochures per working year. 1 policy brief per year.	Nutricycle Vlaanderen, WG chairmen Nutricycle Flanders, Ghent University, Inagro, ILVO, Impact vzw, Agrolink, Vlaco, Biogas-E.	<i>In Process</i>	Regular operation of organisations.
<p>Priority area 2: Political Willingness</p>					
Establish a Multi-Stakeholder Task Force.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify and invite key stakeholders. 2. Schedule regular meetings to discuss goals, challenges, and strategies. 3. Assign roles and responsibilities for advocacy and outreach efforts. 	Already established, and further communications are ongoing.	Nutricycle Vlaanderen.	<i>In Process</i>	EU Projects.

Priority area 3: Research and technical development

<p>Flanders as a European knowledge region in the field of nutrient cycling and recovery.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Digital, regularly updated inventory of research on Nutricycle Flanders website. 2. Support of the broader RE-SOURCE.BIO and Biorefine Cluster Europe network. 3. Connecting knowledge centres to further strengthen inter-university cooperation, including targeted workshops and webinars. 4. Analogous scientific cooperation framework in the field of R&D on the Nexus Nutrients-Water-Energy. 5. ManuREsource biannual conference organisation. 6. European Sustainable Nutrient Initiative annual event organisation in Brussels. 7. Translation of international research into the Flemish language and context by Nutricycle Flanders. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Joint PhD, until 2029. 2. Scientific cooperation framework, ongoing efforts. 3. ManuREsource, annually. 4. ESNI conference, annually. 	<p>Ghent University, INAGRO, University of Antwerp, KU Leuven, VCM, Vlaco.</p>	<p><i>In Process</i></p>	<p>Project financing; Flemish government; institutional resources institutions involved, Nutricycle Flanders.</p>
<p>Systemic scenario analysis for more sustainable nitrogen, phosphorus and protein flows in the food chain.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inventory of N and P flows in Flanders and identification of the junctions. 2. Development and application of a powerful and user-friendly model to map shifts in nutrient and protein flows in Flanders. 3. Recording and calculating indicators that estimate nutrient efficiency and circularity. 	<p>2023-2026.</p>	<p>Ghent University and UA Antwerp.</p>	<p><i>In Process</i></p>	<p>Department of the Environment, UA, Ghent University.</p>
<p>Foster Public-Private Partnerships.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify potential private sector partners such as fertiliser companies and agritech startups. 2. Facilitate collaboration between public institutions and private companies. 	<p>Ongoing, with initial partnerships established in the</p>	<p>Ghent University.</p>	<p><i>In Process</i></p>	<p>EC, Interreg, Vaio, etc.</p>

	3. Promote joint ventures and funding opportunities for R&D in biobased fertilisers.	frame of multiple EU projects.			
<p>Priority area 4: New business models</p>					
Counter function for first-line advice.	1. Providing a counter function (digital & contact person) that gives a complete picture of nutrient recovery in Flanders and works as a contact point for first-line advice.	2023-2026.	Nutricycle Vlaanderen.	<i>In Process</i>	Regular operation of Nutricycle Flanders (including via the Flemish Government Subsidy).
Drawing up a Green Deal for the implementation of the Action Plan.	1. Catalysis and monitoring of the Green Deal by Nutricycle Flanders.	2023-2026.	Nutricycle Vlaanderen.	<i>Awaiting</i>	N/A.
<p>Priority area 5: Financial incentives</p>					
Provision of economic incentives to farmers that use alternative fertilisers by public administration	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Awareness campaigns development to promote alternative fertilisers, contributing to the EU strategy "Farm to Fork". 2. Creation of a set of national, regional, and/or local taxes bonification / exemptions. 3. Development of preferential financing options for alternative fertiliser infrastructure. 	1-2 years.	Nutricycle Vlaanderen.	<i>In Process</i>	Flemish government.

Priority area 6: Self sufficiency					
Optimised manure management: by closing cycles at company level, such as pocket fermentation or farm composting.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monitoring nutrient management, including methane emissions from installed pocket digesters 2. Optimisation of nutrient use. 3. Experiences, networking, demo sessions, workshops further spread farm composting within the sector. 4. Support of local partnerships (legal framework, advice, analyses). 	Ongoing effort.	Inagro, ILVO, Biogas-E, UGent, VCM, KU Leuven, Bioelectric, PCS, PSKW, Vlaco, PCA, VCM, UGent, UE, Paardenpunt Vlaanderen.	<i>In Process</i>	Regular operation of the organisations involved, OG, Vlaio LA, Vlaanderen Circulair, Interreg.
<p>Priority area 7: Public acceptance</p>					
Stakeholder interaction through organisation's own workshops and support organisation of other actors to shape the transition from nutrient removal to nutrient recovery.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establishment of working groups. 2. Organisation of workshops in the context of NOVAFERT and other EU projects. 3. Working groups meetings. 4. Organisation of 2 thematic workshops per year. 	Working groups already established in 2023. Organisation of 2 thematic workshops per year.	Nutricycle Vlaanderen, Watercircle.be), VCM, Flanders' FOOD, sustainable Sales and Land use.	<i>In Process</i>	EU projects.
Providing information to farmers about RENURE products and new organo-mineral fertilisers, growth substrates and soil improvers that (under the new EU regulations) can replace products from primary raw materials in Flanders.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nutricycle Flanders will work on a series of target group-oriented documents. 2. Workshops / webinars and demonstration moments for farmers in the field will also be organised. 	Already implemented as part of the NutriCycle project, to be expanded in the framework of continuing projects over the next three years.	Nutricycle Vlaanderen, UGent, VCM, VLACO, Biogas-E, Boerenbond, ABS, ILVO, B3W, Inagro.	<i>In Process</i>	Project operations.

 Priority area 8: Environmental protection					
Substantiating and supporting precision agriculture to achieve optimal coordination and allocation of raw materials based on local crop and soil needs.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Setting up a centre for precision fertilisation in Flanders. 2. Developing technology for variable fertilisation with various types of fertilisers. 3. Specific soil management. 	Ongoing effort.	Ghent University and KUL.	<i>In Process</i>	EU projects.
Scientific research into agronomic and environmental performance of bio-based mineral nitrogen fertilisers (N) with specific attention to field validation.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monitoring nitrogen losses. 2. Monitoring the quality (variation in composition, stability) of the bio-based mineral N fertilisers. 3. Building up practical experience in real conditions (fertilisation regimes and methods, storage and transport). 	Some of the analyses have already been done, but it will be ongoing effort within the framework of programs.	Ghent University.	<i>In Process</i>	Project operations.

3.2. Croatia – Continental Croatia

3.2.1. Regional characterisation

Socio-economic characterisation of the region. Continental Croatia refers to the inland region of Croatia, located away from the country's coastline along the Adriatic Sea. It is characterised by diverse landscapes, rich cultural heritage, and historical significance. In 2021 the population of Croatia was estimated to be around 3.8 million people.

Continental Croatia is situated in the central and north-eastern parts of the country. It is primarily a lowland area, with rolling hills, fertile plains, and numerous rivers. The main soil types in Continental Croatia are Chernozem, Luvisols, Cambisols and Gleysols. Chernozem is found in the agricultural areas of Continental Croatia, especially in Slavonia and Baranja. Luvisols are prevalent in many parts of Continental Croatia. Gleysols can be found in low-lying areas and floodplains in Continental Croatia.

Continental Croatia contributes significantly to the country's economy by employing a significant portion of the region's workforce. The year 2021 was marked by the recovery of the Croatian economy and the growth of employment after the global crisis in 2020 caused by the coronavirus pandemic. In 2021, the agricultural sector achieved a production value of 20.7 billion HRK. Compared to 2020, the production value of the agricultural sector increased by 2.4 billion HRK, or 13.3%.

Agriculture. Agriculture has traditionally been an important economic activity in the region, particularly in rural areas. According to the data from the Croatian Paying Agency for Agriculture, Fisheries and Rural Development (PAAFRD) in 2021, there were 170,436 farmers registered, with the majority being family farms, representing 82.9 % of the total number of farmers. The highest number of farmers is in the Zagreb County (14,291), 8.4 % of the total number of farmers in Croatia. Croatia is self-sufficient in cereal production, and in 2020, self-sufficiency in cereal production reached 174.2 %. Croatia is also self-sufficient in oilseed production, with a self-sufficiency rate of 287.2 % in 2020. Croatia is a significant producer of soybeans within the European Union.

Fertilising products sector in relation to the waste streams studied in the region: animal manure, digestate and bio-waste. With regards to the fertilisers, Croatian fertiliser production is predicted to drop by 2 % per year, on average, from 2021 to 2026. In 2021, it was recorded at 247,820 metric tons, putting Croatia at 15th place in the world rankings. Croatia's fertiliser exports are forecasted to decrease by 2.7 % annually, from 130,020 metric tons in 2021. Croatia's fertiliser imports are estimated to rise by an average of 2.5 % per year, from 42,940 metric tons in 2021. Since 2007, fertiliser demand in Croatia has decreased by 4.7 %.

According to the reported data, in 2021, a total of 1,101,925 tonnes of biodegradable municipal waste were produced, which is an increase of 3.9 % compared to 2020 when the quantity of generated biodegradable municipal waste amounted to 1,058,703 tonnes. The largest quantities of generated biodegradable municipal waste are recorded in the city of Zagreb.

Regulatory and institutional framework. According to Regulation (EU) 2019/1009, digestate can no longer be treated as organic fertiliser and soil improver, meaning it is no longer considered a fertilising product. According to the Regulation, the only place for digestate is to be used as a component in the preparation and production of specific fertilising products or as a component for creating organic soil improvers. The biggest obstacle to the use of digestate as an organic fertiliser or soil improver in Croatian legislation (Regulation on by-products and disposal of waste status) comes from meeting the legal requirements.

Regarding the animal manure, in one calendar year, the agricultural holding can fertilise agricultural areas with manure up to the limit value of nitrogen application of 170 kg/ha of N. Manure is applied in such a way as to reduce nitrogen losses to the minimum possible extent.

The management of bio-waste in Continental Croatia is governed by waste management regulations and guidelines. In the Waste Management Plan for the period from 2017 to 2022, the Republic of Croatia prescribed the dynamics of separate collection of municipal bio-waste on an annual level, according to which by 2022, 40% of the produced amount of bio-waste from municipal waste must be separately collected at the national level.

3.2.2. Main findings

The waste streams **animal manure**, **digestate** and **bio-waste** have been considered as secondary raw materials' sources for producing alternative fertilisers in Continental Croatia. The main actions outlined per each priority area are summarised in the following table.

Table 2. Main actions outlined in the RSAP of Continental Croatia

What will we do?	How will we do it	When is it being proposed?	Who will be responsible?	Status (Completed / In Process / Awaiting)	Possible Funding Sources
 Priority area 1: Legal Framework					
Work with local agricultural associations and policymakers to advocate for regulatory adjustments that facilitate the adoption of alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establish Collaborative Partnerships, engaging key stakeholders and creating working groups. 2. Research, collecting data and highlighting successful case studies. 3. Implementation, launching awareness campaigns and monitoring progress. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. From 01/05/2023. 2. From 01/01/2025. 6-9 months to conduct comprehensive research and compile findings. 3. From 01/02/2025. 9-12 months to launch campaigns and establish ongoing 	Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Farmers, agricultural associations, policymakers, environmental NGOs. 2. Agricultural researchers, universities, policy analysts, farmers. 3. Local media and farmers. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In Process 2. Awaiting 3. Awaiting 	NOVAFERT.

		monitoring mechanisms.			
Transfer of knowledge about good regulatory frameworks in other EU countries.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify best practices in EU countries with successful regulatory frameworks for alternative fertilisers. 2. Attend knowledge exchange programs where policymakers, regulatory authorities, and stakeholders from different EU countries share their experiences on regulatory frameworks. 3. Information-sharing platform to facilitate continuous exchange of regulatory knowledge and best practices. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. From 01/02/2025. 3-6 months to conduct research and compile detailed documentation. 2. From 01/11/2024. 6-9 months to attend and actively engage in various knowledge exchange events. 3. From 01/02/2023. 	<p>Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Agricultural researchers, policy makers, government officials, and EU regulatory bodies. 2. Policy makers, regulatory authorities, agricultural associations, EU representatives. 3. Agricultural researchers, EU regulatory bodies, farmers. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Awaiting</i> 2. <i>Awaiting</i> 3. <i>In Process</i> 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. NOVAFERT. 2. NOVAFERT. 3. NOVAFERT, internally.
<p>Priority area 2: Political Willingness</p>					
Foster partnerships between governments, private sector, and NGOs to promote the use of alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify and engage stakeholders with interest in sustainable agriculture and alternative fertilisers. 2. Establish cross-sector working groups, and combine resources to promote alternative fertilisers. 3. Conduct public awareness campaigns, advocate for supportive policies, and monitor and report progress. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. From 01/05/2023. 2. From 01/03/2025. 4-6 months to establish working groups and begin collaborative efforts. 3. From 01/11/2024. 6-12 months to plan and execute campaigns, with ongoing monitoring and reporting. 	<p>Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Government officials, private sector representatives, NGO leaders, agricultural experts. 2. Members from government agencies, private companies, and NGOs. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>In Process</i> 2. <i>Awaiting</i> 3. <i>Awaiting</i> 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. NOVAFERT. 2. NOVAFERT. 3. NOVAFERT, internally.

			3. Marketing team, agricultural associations, policy makers, farmers.		
Create a knowledge exchange campaign to learn from countries that have successfully implemented alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify and Partner: Research successful countries, establish partnerships, and formalise agreements for knowledge exchange. 2. Arrange study tours, workshops, seminars, and virtual knowledge-sharing activities. 3. Evaluate outcomes and disseminate knowledge to local stakeholders. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. From 01/02/2025. 3-6 months to identify successful countries, establish partnerships, and formalise agreements. 2. From 01/03/2025. 6-9 months to plan and execute study tours, workshops, and virtual sessions. 3. From 01/04/2025. 3-6 months for evaluation and dissemination of knowledge, with ongoing updates as necessary. 	<p>Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Agricultural researchers, international experts, government agencies, NGOs. 2. Policy makers, agricultural extension officers, farmers, international experts. 3. Agricultural researchers, policymakers, farmers. 	<i>Awaiting</i>	NOVAFERT.
<p>Priority area 3: Research and technical development</p>					
Raise awareness.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Create informative content (brochures, infographics, videos, and articles that showcase recent research findings, innovations, and the scientific benefits of alternative fertilisers). 2. Simplify technical information (translate complex R&D data into easy-to-understand language, making it accessible 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. From 01/07/2024. 2. From 01/01/2023. 3. From 01/05/2023. 	<p>Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Agricultural researchers, marketing team, graphic designers, content creators. 	<i>In Process</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. NOVAFERT. 2. NOVAFERT. 3. NOVAFERT, internally.

	<p>to farmers, agricultural stakeholders, and the general public).</p> <p>3. Highlight successful case studies that demonstrate the positive impact of alternative fertilisers on crop yields, soil health, and environmental sustainability.</p>		<p>2. Agricultural experts, communication specialists.</p> <p>3. Agricultural researchers, farmers who have implemented alternative fertilisers.</p>		
<p>Find examples of studies showing differences between traditional fertilisers and alternative options.</p>	<p>1. Compile summaries of the most relevant studies, highlighting key findings and differences in performance, environmental impact, and cost-effectiveness.</p> <p>2. Engage in discussions to gain insights and access to studies.</p> <p>3. Synthesise the gathered information into a comprehensive overview that highlights key differences and benefits of alternative fertilisers compared to traditional ones.</p>	<p>1. From 01/02/2025. 3-4 months to gather and summarise relevant studies.</p> <p>2. From 01/11/2024. Ongoing, with key engagements planned over a period of 6-12 months.</p> <p>3. From 01/01/2025. 2-3 months to synthesise data and produce the final comprehensive overview.</p>	<p>Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting.</p> <p>1. Agricultural researchers, academic institutions, policy analysts.</p> <p>2. Agricultural researchers, industry experts, academic institutions, conference organisers.</p> <p>3. Agricultural researchers, communication specialists.</p>	<i>Awaiting</i>	NOVAFERT.
<p>Priority area 4: New business models</p>					
<p>Conduct comprehensive market research to understand the current fertilising product landscape, identify potential competitors, and</p>	<p>1. Access market databases and online resources to gather existing data on market size, growth rates, and trends.</p> <p>2. Design and distribute surveys to farmers, agricultural suppliers, and distributors to gather firsthand information on fertiliser</p>	<p>1. From 01/03/2024.</p> <p>2. From 01/01/2024.</p> <p>3. From 01/03/2024.</p>	<p>Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting.</p> <p>1. Market researchers, data analysts, agricultural economists.</p> <p>2. Survey designers, farmers.</p>	<i>In Process</i>	NOVAFERT.

gauge market demand in Croatia	usage, preferences, and purchasing behaviour. 3. Compile a list of major fertiliser suppliers and manufacturers operating in Croatia, including both local and international companies.		3. Market analysts, business researchers.		
Develop and implement awareness campaigns to educate farmers and agricultural businesses about the benefits of alternative fertilising products.	1. Develop brochures, fact sheets, infographics, and videos explaining how alternative fertilisers work, their benefits, and how to use them. 2. Collect and present case studies and testimonials from farmers who have successfully used alternative fertilisers. 3. Use social media platforms to share educational content, success stories, and interactive posts to engage with the farming community.	1. From 01/05/2024. 2. From 01/02/2025. 3-4 months to collect, document, and present case studies and testimonials. 3. From 01/11/2022.	Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting. 1. Agricultural experts, graphic designers, content creators, marketing teams. 2. Communication specialists, successful farmers. 3. Social media managers, content creators, community engagement specialists.	1. <i>In Process</i> 2. <i>Awaiting</i> 3. <i>In Process</i>	1. NOVAFERT. 2. NOVAFERT. 3. NOVAFERT, internally.
 Priority area 5: Financial incentives					
Explore opportunities for financial assistance from EU agricultural funds or other international organisations focused on sustainable agriculture.	1. Participate in informational sessions, workshops, and webinars organised by funding bodies. 2. Establish and maintain relationships with key contacts. 3. Publicise the successful acquisition of funding and the progress of the funded projects to build credibility and attract future funding opportunities.	1. From 01/05/2024. 2. From 01/05/2024. 3. From 01/01/2023.	Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting. 1. Agricultural experts, representatives from funding bodies. 2. Agricultural experts, funding body representatives.	<i>In Process</i>	1. NOVAFERT. 2. NOVAFERT, internally. 3. NOVAFERT.

			3. Communication specialists, marketing team.		
 Priority area 6: Self sufficiency					
Promote the use of alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop brochures, videos, and infographics that explain the benefits of alternative fertilisers for self-sufficiency, including improved soil health, reduced dependency on imports, and cost savings. 2. Ensure all educational materials are available in the local language(s) to maximise accessibility and understanding. 3. Use social media platforms to share success stories, educational content, and interactive posts about alternative fertilisers and self-sufficiency. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. From 01/07/2023. 2. From 01/07/2023. 3. From 01/11/2022. 	Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Agricultural experts, content creators, marketing team, local agricultural associations. 2. Content creators, local agricultural associations, communication specialists. 3. Social media creators, content creators, agricultural experts, community engagement specialists. 	<i>In Process</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. NOVAFERT. 2. NOVAFERT, internally. 3. NOVAFERT, internally.
 Priority area 7: Public acceptance					
Public awareness campaigns.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organise field days where farmers and the public can visit demonstration sites, observe the results, and interact with experts. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. From 01/11/2024. 3-4 months to plan and execute, with events scheduled regularly throughout the year. 	Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Agricultural experts, local farmers, community organisers. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Awaiting</i> 2. <i>Awaiting</i> 3. <i>In Process</i> 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. NOVAFERT. 2. NOVAFERT. 3. NOVAFERT, internally.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Conduct workshops and training sessions for farmers to educate them on the proper use, benefits, and potential challenges of alternative fertilisers. 3. Launch targeted social media campaigns to engage with younger farmers and the broader community. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. From 01/10/2024. 2-3 months for initial planning and organisation, followed by ongoing sessions throughout the year. 3. From 01/05/2023. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Agricultural trainers, extension officers, local agricultural associations, farmers. 3. Content creators, farmers. 		
<p>Priority area 8: Environmental protection</p>					
Raise public awareness.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use platforms (Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube) to share educational content, success stories, calls to action. 2. Ensure the content is relevant to local environmental challenges and available in the local language. 3. Share success stories, impact reports, and case studies with the community and stakeholders to highlight progress and encourage continued involvement. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. From 01/10/2022. 2. From 01/10/2022. 3. From 01/01/2023. 2-3 months to gather and compile stories and reports, followed by regular updates and sharing. 	<p>Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Content creators, agricultural experts, community engagement specialists. 2. Local environmental experts, agricultural experts, content creators. 3. Agricultural experts, farmers, communication specialists. 	<i>In Process</i>	NOVAFERT, internally.

3.3. Finland – South-West Finland

3.3.1. Regional characterisation

Socio-economic characterisation of the region. Finland lies between latitudes 60°N and 70°N, and is the sixth largest country in Europe, occupies an area of 338,312 km². Finland is bordered on the east and southeast by the Russian Federation, on the west by Sweden and the Gulf of Bothnia, on the north by Norway and on the south by the Gulf of Finland. Most of the country is low but not necessarily flat. Soil is very thin. Mainly moraine deposits from ice age glaciers, finer mineral soils, and organic soil types are common in Finland. One third of the fields contain clay soil types. The clay soils concentrate in Southwest Finland. The share of peatland in the arable land areas of Lapland, Northern Ostrobothnia and Kainuu is 20–40%. A quarter of arable land in Ostrobothnia and Southern Ostrobothnia consists of organic soil types.

Population of Finland is 5.56 million (2022). The gross domestic product (GDP) of Finland was 269 billion euros in 2022, an increase of around 18 billion euros compared with the previous year. GDP per capita amounted to 48 345 euros in 2022, which was the ninth highest in Europe. In 2022, GDP share of agriculture in Finland was 2.38%. The largest sector of the Finnish economy is services at 65 percent, followed by manufacturing and refining at 31 percent. Finland's main industrial products are paper and board, electronics and metal products. Engineering and high technology industries are the leading branches of manufacturing.

Agriculture. Finland is considered the most northerly agricultural country in the world. Finland's agriculture relies heavily on grassland and cereal varieties suited to the northern climate. The total area used for agriculture in Finland comes to about 2.3 million hectares. In recent years, cereal crops have accounted for just over 1 million hectares and grassland for some 0.7 million hectares. In 2021, approximately 14% of arable land area was used for organic production.

In 2022, there were 44,000 farms in Finland, and nearly all of them were family run (Official Statistics of Finland, 2021). Farmers and their family members perform 80% of all agricultural work in Finland. Agriculture employs 76 000 people. Crop production was the main production activity on 70% of farms and livestock production on 21% of farms. The remainder are mixed farms with no clear main production direction.

Fertilising products sector in relation to the waste streams studied in the region: animal manure, digestate and bio-waste. With regards to the fertilising products, a recent report on the need and potential for phosphorus recycling in Finland estimated the phosphorus demand for crop production on the country's 2.3 million hectares of arable land at just over 10 kg/ha (Lemola et al., 2023). Divided evenly according to need, the amount of manure phosphorus would cover 6,7 kg/ha, i.e., 65 % of the need. The need for phosphorus replenishment would be less than 4 kg/ha in the case of even distribution, but the volume of mineral fertiliser phosphorus sold in the last two decades has been around 5 kg/ha. When

considering other recyclable biomasses in addition to manure, 90% of the needed phosphorus fertilisation could be covered by nutrient recycling.

In Finland, 13 million tonnes of manure are produced from livestock production. Livestock and fur animals generate over 73 million kg of nitrogen and 15 million kg of phosphorus yearly. There are large regional differences in manure production due to the high concentration of livestock production in western and southwestern Finland.

Biowaste from municipalities yields 484 000 tonnes per year containing 3 000 tonnes of nitrogen and 550 tonnes of phosphorus. Regional differences in population are reflected in the quantity of municipal biowaste.

Digestates are currently produced in around 130 biogas plants, including urban and industrial wastewater treatment plants, co-processing plants of various sizes and farm-scale biogas plants. The biogas production was 1 TWh in 2021.

Regulatory and institutional framework. Fertiliser use of manure and organic fertiliser products is governed via national legislation enacting the EU Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC) and the EU Fertilising Product Regulation (EU 2019/1009). The Government Decree on Limiting Certain Emissions from Agriculture (1250/2014), known as 'Nitrates Decree', aims to reduce nitrogen emissions caused by the storage and use of manure and other organic fertiliser products and the use of inorganic fertiliser products. In the Decree, the whole of Finland is defined as a nitrate vulnerable zone and thus it controls nitrogen fertilisation in all farms across the country.

Digested biowaste and sewage sludge are also largely used as soil improvers and fertilisers in agriculture, but there are some legal restrictions. Digested sewage sludge can be used on fields where crops such as cereals, sugar beet, oilseeds or other crops are grown that are not eaten fresh, as a subsoil crop or as animal feed. Slurry can be applied to grassland by establishing the grassland with cover crops.

3.3.2. Main findings

The waste streams **animal manure**, **digestate** and **bio-waste** have been considered as secondary raw materials' sources for producing alternative fertilisers in South-West Finland. The main actions outlined per each priority area are summarised in the following table.

Table 3. Main actions outlined in the RSAP of South-West Finland

What will we do?	How will we do it	When is it being proposed?	Who will be responsible?	Status (Completed / In Process / Awaiting)	Possible Funding Sources
<p>Priority area 1: Legal Framework</p>					
Uptake of nutrient recycling subsidy for enhancing the use of manure-based nutrients.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mapping of nutrient sources in the region for producing the alternative fertilisers. 2. Producing tailor made alternative fertilisers according to regional crop requirement. 3. Demonstrating the use of alternative fertilisers and showcasing their efficiency for the whole value chain. 	From 2025.	Policy makers, farmers union and farmers.	<i>In Process</i>	H2020 and HORIZON EU projects.
<p>Priority area 2: Political Willingness</p>					
Demonstrating environmental benefits when substituting mineral fertilisers with alternative ones.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collaboration with policy makers to provide information about soil P status in agricultural fields and consequence for P losses. 2. Demonstrate agronomic efficiency of alternative fertilisers. 3. Disseminate results of alternative fertilisers for different stakeholders. 	2024-2025.	Researchers (mainly LUKE).	<i>In Process</i>	National funding schemes, H2020 and HORIZON EU projects.
<p>Priority area 3: Research and technical development</p>					

Supplementing alternative fertilisers with additional nutrients to improve nutrient ratios.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Evaluating the right NP-ratio for fields with varying P status. 2. Improving N/P ratio with fertiliser companies to meet crop demand and minimise nutrient losses. 3. Demonstrate efficiency of new tailor-made fertilisers for farmers and policy makers. 	2025-2028.	Fertiliser companies, policy makers, researchers.	<i>Awaiting</i>	National funding schemes and HORIZON EU projects.
<p>Priority area 4: New business models</p>					
Turning nutrient-rich side-streams into a valuable alternative fertiliser.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increasing awareness of alternative fertilisers and their potential in replacing mineral fertilisers. 2. Creating a system for supporting production of alternative fertilisers. 3. Increased production capacity will secure availability of alternative fertilisers. 	2025-2030.	Fertiliser companies, policy makers, researchers.	<i>In Process</i>	National funding schemes and HORIZON EU projects.
<p>Priority area 5: Financial incentives</p>					
Economic incentives for reducing logistics of using alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Evaluating the barriers related to logistics for using alternative fertilisers. 2. Workshops among farmers, fertiliser producer and policy makers about actions needed to reduce logistics cost. 3. Roadmap developed for the increased uptake of alternative fertilisers. 	Starting in 2025.	Fertiliser producers, farmers, researchers, policy makers.	<i>Awaiting</i>	National funding schemes.
<p>Priority area 6: Self sufficiency</p>					

Enhanced replacement of mineral fertilisers with alternative ones.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collecting farmer's opinion about alternative fertilisers. 2. Providing up-to-date information about potential of alternative fertilisers in workshops arranged for farmers. 3. Reducing restrictions for using alternative fertilisers originating from manure. 4. 	2025-2028.	Fertiliser producers, farmers, researchers, policy makers.	<i>Awaiting</i>	National funding schemes and HORIZON EU projects.
<p>Priority area 7: Public acceptance</p>					
Increase awareness about the food safety when using alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Evaluate potential risks related to the use of alternative fertilisers. 2. Collect information about the safety of alternative fertilisers when it comes to food safety and human health. 3. Disseminate results to the public. 	2025 onwards.	Researchers (mainly LUKE).	<i>In Process</i>	National funding schemes and HORIZON EU projects.
<p>Priority area 8: Environmental protection</p>					
Alternative fertilisers have a potential to reduce the use of mineral fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Current nutrient (N and P) losses and required reduction to reach good ecological status of the surface waters. 2. Determining the reduction limit for N and P losses to meet the requirements. 3. Demonstrating potential N and P losses after using alternative fertilisers versus mineral ones. 	2025 onwards.	Researchers (mainly LUKE).	<i>In Process</i>	HORIZON EU projects.

3.4. Ireland – East Ireland

3.4.1. Regional characterisation

Socio-economic characterisation of the region. Ireland is an island situated in North-western Europe. It is surrounded by the Atlantic Ocean, with the Celtic Sea to the South, the St. George's Channel to the Southeast, and the Irish Sea to the East. Ireland has a diverse landscape that includes low-lying coastal plains, mountains, and lakes. Ireland has a temperate maritime climate, characterised by mild winters and cool summers.

The current population of Ireland is 5,097,599. Ireland has a developed and modern economy, which has undergone significant growth in recent decades. The country has a strong focus on industries such as pharmaceuticals, technology, financial services, and tourism. The agri-food sector is a hugely valuable part of the economy, and is a key contributor to economic growth. Agriculture in Ireland is responsible for 7.1% of the total workforce on the island. Ireland exports the majority of production to 180 countries around the world.

Agriculture. Irish agriculture is dominated by family-owned farms. There are 140,000 farms, with an average land holding of 32.5 hectares. The Irish climate is capable of growing grass for 9 to 10 months of the year. As a result, the dominant enterprise in Ireland is dairy and beef accounting for two-thirds of gross agricultural output. Ireland is currently one of the fastest-growing dairy producers and exporters in the world. In 2022, there was 1.7 million tonnes of dairy product shipped to 130 markets worldwide. Other than grass, crops such as wheat, barley and oats are also grown in Ireland.

Fertilising products sector in relation to the waste streams studied in the region: bio-waste and biological by-products. Ireland is heavily dependent on importing inorganic fertiliser for food production importing over 1.8 million tonnes of fertiliser annually. Ireland imports chemical fertiliser primarily from Russia, United Kingdom, Germany, Spain and Morocco. Ireland is making efforts to reduce reliance on chemical fertilisers and explore alternative nutrient sources in agriculture. Irish stakeholders are promoting alternative farming practices which prioritises the use of biological alternative fertilisers such as compost, animal manure, crop residues, food waste, incorporating legume crops such as clover and beans to fix nitrogen. Nutrient management planning is also a key tool being used in Irish agriculture which helps optimise the use of nutrient sources and limit the loss of nutrients to the environment, which involves analysing soil nutrient levels, crop nutrient requirements and using precision application techniques such as low emission slurry spreading.

Bio-waste and agricultural by products have potential in Ireland to supply nutrients for crop production which will reduce dependence on chemical fertiliser. Therefore, feedstock availability for the use as alternative fertilisers is essential. Approximately 132 million tonnes of agricultural slurries, wastewaters, effluent, and sludge are generated in Ireland on an annual basis. There are approximately 140,686 tonnes of bio-waste processed in the republic of Ireland and 280,496 tonnes processed in Northern Ireland on annual basis. The number of licensed plants controlling bio-waste in Ireland is 8 and 5 in Northern Ireland. The total quantity of waste accepted for treatment at composting and anaerobic digestion plants in Ireland in 2020 was 601,482 tonnes and 733,881 tonnes in Northern Ireland.

Regulatory and institutional framework. Current Irish national fertiliser regulations for biological by products and bio-waste are covered under the fertilisers, feeding stuffs and mineral mixtures act 1955 and the SI No 248 of 1978 (non-EEC fertilisers) which covers mineral fertilisers, organic fertilisers, low nutrient fertilisers and ground limestone. In Ireland, there are currently no national end-of-waste criteria defined for compost and digestate derived from bio-waste and biological by product materials. There are varying quality standards being used by composting and anaerobic digestion plants.

3.4.2. Main findings

The waste streams **bio-waste** and **biological by-products** have been considered as secondary raw materials' sources for producing alternative fertilisers in East Ireland. The main actions outlined per each priority area are summarised in the following table.

Table 4. Main actions outlined in the RSAP of East Ireland

What will we do?	How will we do it	When is it being proposed?	Who will be responsible?	Status (Completed / In Process / Awaiting)	Possible Funding Sources
 Priority area 1: Legal Framework					
National legislation complies with the	1. Mapping of key national and European legislation.	2024.	TBC.	<i>In Process</i>	Link in with existing work

European legislation on the use of alternative fertilisers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Legal harmonisation of the national and regional framework. 3. Coordination within national and regional administrations. 				being carried out within the area.
Introduce carbon credit incentives for farmers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide scientific evidence for the benefits of using fertiliser with greater % carbon. 2. Coordination with national and regional administrations. 	2024.	TEAGASC.	<i>In Process</i>	Link in with existing work being carried out within the area.
Encourage livestock/tillage relationship/partnership for the exchange of nutrients between farms.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Encourage stockless farms to take excess nutrients from livestock farms. 2. Need to encourage correct nutrient management planning in advance of growing seasons to be able account for the use of organic manures without breaching the organic N limit. 3. Connection of intensive livestock farmers with stockless farmers using advisory services/ discussion groups, etc. 	2024.	TEAGASC, farmers, researchers and advisory services.	<i>In Process</i>	Link in with existing work being carried out within the area.
<p>Priority area 2: Political Willingness</p>					
Public awareness and education campaigns.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Educate farmers and the public about the environmental and economic benefits of bio-based fertilisers. 2. Use demonstration farms, workshops, seminars and media campaigns to educate consumers and farmers through networks on the EU funded projects NOVAFERT, Nutriknow and Bbionets. 3. Seek Government funding to provide training and technical assistance to farmers to help educate them on the topic. 	2024.	TEAGASC, researchers, advisors, consumers and farmers.	<i>In Process</i>	Existing funding through EU funded bioeconomy projects.

<p>Priority area 3: Research and technical development</p>					
Provide scientific research for displacing chemical fertilisers with alternative fertilisers for crop production.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Continue to seek funding to run field experiments testing different types of alternative fertilisers. 2. TEAGASC will continue to run field experiments testing different types of alternative fertilisers. 3. Provide relevant information for advisors and teachers to educate young farmers in agricultural college. 	2024.	TEAGASC, researchers, advisors, teachers, students and farmers.	<i>In Process</i>	Horizon EU funded projects and national funding.
Support mechanisms to encourage local production of alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Harmonisation of local and national grant aid to support technological development for refining nutrients. 	2024.	TBC.	<i>Awaiting</i>	Horizon EU funded projects and national funding.
Provide more information for advisory and extension services that farmers avail of regarding to the bioeconomy.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide relevant information for advisors and teachers to include within their education programmes. 	2024.	TEAGASC.	<i>In Process</i>	Horizon EU funded projects and national funding.
<p>Priority area 4: New business models</p>					
Collaboration between research and companies.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Build relationships. 2. Create collaborative agreements. 3. Secure funding through project funding, government agencies, industry sponsors, etc.. 	2024.	TEAGASC, ENVA, researchers, company owners.	<i>In Process</i>	Project funding, government, private companies.
<p>Priority area 5: Financial incentives</p>					

Government provides economic incentives to farmers that use alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Developing awareness campaigns to promote alternative fertilisers, contributing to the EU strategy "Farm to Fork" at the local and regional levels. 2. Creating a set of national, regional, and/or local taxes bonification / exemptions. 3. Developing preferential financing options for alternative fertiliser infrastructure. 	From 2024.	Government representatives, citizens, researchers, farmers and private companies.	<i>In Process</i>	N/A.
 Priority area 6: Self sufficiency					
Provide new research, support and innovative tools that farmers can adapt on farm to make best use of nutrients already available to them on farm.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide scientific and technical information to advisors and farmers regarding to the benefits of adapting tools such as crop rotation, cover cropping, crop residue management, green manure, composting, animal integration and soil testing. 2. Providing up to date technical advice on the best use and management of animal manures from storage to application methods is a key focus within TEAGASC nutrient efficiency research. 3. Continuously researching and updating farmers on the nutrient availability of different bio-based products. 	2024.	TEAGASC, research, education, advisory service, farmers.	<i>In Process</i>	Existing resources available through a range of funded projects.
 Priority area 7: Public acceptance					
Raise awareness of the benefits of using alternative fertiliser to the public through the use of	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. b) Establish lighthouse demonstration farms that are using alternative fertilisers to a high standard through the work of the NOVAFERT project. 	2024.	TEAGASC, researchers, advisors, farmers, citizens and private industry.	<i>In Process</i>	EU funding through the NOVAFERT project.

demonstration farms and videos / success stories.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Organise frequent stakeholder group visits to the lighthouse demonstration farms including open invitation to the public. Provide relevant information regarding the benefits of the system in an agricultural context and receive feedback and questions from other farmers, consumers, general public, etc. 				
Public awareness campaign.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Launch educational campaigns to raise awareness about the benefits of alternative fertilisers (social media channels, workshops, community events). 	2024.	TEAGASC and other interested state and private bodies TBC.	<i>In Process</i>	Resources that are already available.
Case studies/success stories.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Share success stories or case studies of farmers reducing their reliance on chemical fertilisers and replacing them with alternative sources of fertiliser to the public. 	2024.	TEAGASC.	<i>In Process</i>	EU funding through the NOVAFERT project.
<p>Priority area 8: Environmental protection</p>					
Promote the benefits that alternative fertilisers have on soil health.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Continue to carry out field measurements regarding the impact alternative fertilisers have on soil health. Groups visiting the Irish lighthouse demo. 	2024.	TEAGASC.	<i>In Process</i>	EU funding through the NOVAFERT project
Use fertiliser at the right time, rate and place.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Provide scientific research to advisors, lecturers etc. regarding to best practices for applying nutrients to land to minimise chance of nutrient loss to the environment. 	2024.	TEAGASC.	<i>In Process</i>	Internal funding through a range of funded projects.
Enhanced soil health.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Provide up to date scientific research to all relevant stakeholders regarding the positive benefit that bio-based fertilisers have in relation to soil health. 	2024.	TEAGASC.	<i>In Process</i>	Internal funding through a range of funded projects.

3.5. Poland – South-East Poland

3.5.1. Regional characterisation

Socio-economic characterisation of the region. Poland, officially known as the Republic of Poland, is a democratic country in Central Europe with a land area of 312 696 km², Poland is the ninth-largest country in Europe. The population of Poland is 37 654 247 inhabitants, making it the sixth most populous country in Europe. South-east Poland is situated in the eastern part of the country, bordering Ukraine to the east, Slovakia to the south and the Czech Republic to the southwest. It covers a significant portion of the Carpathian Mountains and includes fertile lowlands and river valleys.

In the south-eastern Poland, there are 3 voivodeships - Podkarpackie, Małopolskie and Śląskie. The south-eastern part of Poland, due to its location, is more prone to temperature extremes compared to western and northern parts of the country. Additionally, the presence of the Carpathian Mountains can lead to variations in climate across different elevations. This region experiences distinct seasons with noticeable temperature variations throughout the year.

The economy of south-east Poland is diverse, with a mix of industries including agriculture, manufacturing, services, and tourism. The region has been experiencing economic growth in recent years, with investments in infrastructure and the development of special economic zones. Key sectors include food processing, automotive, machinery, and IT

Agriculture. Agriculture plays a significant role in Poland's economy. The fertile soils and favourable climatic conditions support a variety of agricultural activities. Moreover, Poland is one of the main agricultural producers in the EU: it belongs to the three largest producers of basic cereals and root crops and is also the largest supplier of apples and poultry meat. Major agricultural products include cereals (such as wheat, barley and rye), potatoes, sugar beets and vegetables. Livestock farming, including cattle, pigs, and poultry, is also an important part of the agricultural sector.

Fertilising products sector in relation to the waste streams studied in the region: sewage sludge, animal manure and digestate. The agriculture sector employs a considerable portion of the regional workforce, using both conventional and natural fertilisers. The use of fertilisers derived from sewage sludge, animal manure, and digestate can have both positive and negative environmental aspects.

Regulatory and institutional framework. In Poland, there are legal regulations concerning the use of sewage sludge that govern the management of this material. The most important regulations are presented by Waste Act, Regulation of the Minister of Environment on the conditions for Introducing waste to the soil, Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development on natural fertilisers and Administrative decisions issued by relevant administrative authorities, such as environmental agencies.

The use of animal manure as an alternative fertiliser is regulated by several important regulations. The list of regulations consists of Fertilisers and Fertilisation Act, Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development on the conditions for the use of animal manure, Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) and Environmental Protection Act.

In Poland, the use of digestate, which is the residual material left after anaerobic digestion of organic waste, is regulated by several laws and regulations. The main legal framework includes Waste Act, Fertiliser Act, Water Law, Environmental Protection Law.

3.5.2. Main findings

The waste streams **sewage sludge**, **animal manure** and **digestate** have been considered as secondary raw materials' sources for producing alternative fertilisers in South-East Poland. The main actions outlined per each priority area are summarised in the following table. *Table 5. Main actions outlined in the RSAP of South-East Poland*

What will we do?	How will we do it	When is it being proposed?	Who will be responsible?	Status (Completed / In Process / Awaiting)	Possible Funding Sources
 Priority area 1: Legal Framework					
Review and update regulations regarding alternative fertilisers (animal manure, digestate and sewage sludge).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mapping key national and European regulations. 2. Analysing the compliance of current regulations with EU requirements. 3. Collaborating with the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development to implement legal changes. 	Until the end of this project.	Team MEERI PAS, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and local authorities.	<i>In Process</i>	NOVAFERT.

Priority area 2: Political Willingness					
Increase the engagement of local and regional authorities in seeking solutions to replace mineral fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organising meetings with Regional Working Group. 2. Promoting the environmental benefits of using alternative fertilisers. 3. Supporting legislative initiatives at the regional level." 	Until the end of this project.	Team MEERI PAS, all RWG participants.	<i>In Process</i>	NOVAFERT.
 Priority area 3: Research and technical development					
Support research on new technologies for converting waste into fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifying key research opportunities in the region. 2. Increasing funding for research and development of technologies. 3. Organising scientific conferences and workshops. 	Until the end of this project.	Team MEERI PAS, scientific and industrial sectors.	<i>In Process</i>	NOVAFERT.
 Priority area 4: New business models					
Promote the circular economy in the context of converting waste into fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Analyse the potential for transforming waste materials such as sewage sludge, animal manure and digestate into marketable fertilisers. 2. Promote circular economy frameworks that support waste-to-fertiliser processes. 3. Foster collaborations between organic farmers and alternative fertiliser producers. 	Until the end of this project.	Team MEERI PAS.	<i>In Process</i>	NOVAFERT.

<p>Priority area 5: Financial incentives</p>					
Implement economic support systems for farmers using alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Analysing available funding sources and support opportunities. Developing grant and tax relief programs. Promoting available forms of support among farmers. 	Until the end of this project.	Team MEERI PAS, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and local authorities.	<i>In Process</i>	NOVAFERT.
<p>Priority area 6: Self sufficiency</p>					
Reduce dependence on mineral fertiliser imports by using alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Analysing the potential of local raw material sources. Supporting local fertiliser producers. Promoting self-sufficiency among farmers. 	Until the end of this project.	Team MEERI PAS, local producers and farmers.	<i>In Process</i>	NOVAFERT.
<p>Priority area 7: Public acceptance</p>					
Increase public awareness of the benefits of using alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Organising educational campaigns. Collaborating with environmental organisations. Promoting success stories of farmers using alternative fertilisers. 	Until the end of this project.	Team MEERI PAS.	<i>In Process</i>	NOVAFERT.
Inform stakeholders (especially farmers) about alternative fertiliser products made from sewage sludge, animal manure and digestate.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Organise workshops to promote alternative fertilisers. Engage farmers in promotional activities for lighthouse initiatives. 	Until the end of this project.	Team MEERI PAS, lighthouse demo (Rzeszów Municipal Water and Sewerage Company, MPWiK), agricultural extension services (Boguchwała	<i>In Process</i>	NOVAFERT.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Present examples of alternative fertiliser products and their positive environmental impacts to farmers. 4. Utilise various communication channels to disseminate information. 		Agricultural Advisory Centre) and local farming communities.		
<p>Priority area 8: Environmental protection</p>					
Support environmental protection efforts through the use of alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifying environmental benefits. 2. Promoting narratives on mitigating climate change. 3. Collaborating with environmental protection institutions. 	Until the end of this project.	Team MEERI PAS, Rzeszów Municipal Water and Sewerage Company (MPWiK) Boguchwała Podkarpackie Agricultural Advisory Centre (PODR), environmental protection institutions and farmers.	<i>In Process</i>	NOVAFERT.
Promotion of best practices for the sustainable use of alternative fertilisers from animal manure, sewage sludge and digestate.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organising workshops for farmers on sustainable application methods. 2. Collaborating with agricultural advisors to provide on-site support and consultations for farmers. 	Until the end of this project.	Team MEERI PAS, research institutions, agricultural advisors and farmers.	<i>In Process</i>	NOVAFERT.
Publish scientific research on the use of alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify key research areas related to alternative fertilisers, focusing on animal manure, digestate and sewage sludge. 2. Prepare detailed research papers based on the findings and submit them to high-impact scientific journals. 3. Disseminate published research through academic conferences, workshops, and other relevant platforms. 	Until the end of this project.	Team MEERI PAS.	<i>In Process</i>	NOVAFERT.

3.6. Spain – Andalusia

3.6.1. Regional characterisation

Socio-economic characterisation of the region. Andalusia is located in the South of Spain, between the African continent and the rest of Europe, and it is the point where the Mediterranean Sea and the Atlantic Ocean converge. To the north, the Sierra Morena is the natural border that separates it from the rest of Spain. In the west, Andalusia limits with the Guadiana river and Portugal's border. To the south, with the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea. Andalusia is the second biggest region of Spain with an extension of 87,268 km. 50% of the region is mountainous. Andalusia is Spain's most populated region and the second most extensive with 8,484,804 million inhabitants, 87,598 km² and a population density of 96.86 inhabitants/ km². Its surface represents the 17.3% of Spain. Andalusia's GDP is 160,747 million €, constituting the third largest economy in Spain by volume of GDP. As for GDP per capita, which is a good indicator of life quality, in 2021 was 18,906 €, compared to 25,498 € of GDP per capita in Spain. The main sectors are services, followed by agriculture, construction, manufactured industry and logistics and communication.

Agriculture. The agri-food sector is one of the main sources of wealth and employment within the region, that accounts for 10% of the gross domestic value of the region and participating for 40% of the region's total exports. In comparison to the national context, the Andalusian primary sector accounts for about a quarter of Spanish agricultural production and accounts for over 30% of the added value and employment of the national agricultural sector.

Andalusia is the first Autonomous Community in absolute terms of irrigated area with 1,123,547 ha, 28.97% of the total national irrigated area. In relative terms it accounts for 12.83% of its geographical area and 31.84% of its cultivation area. The main risk of water shortage in Andalusia is drought. This is a gradual circumstance characterised by the periodic water shortage, although the tendency shows how drought periods are becoming more common. Mediterranean climate, climatic and altitude differences within the Andalusian region make it a very varied and abundant region in agricultural terms. One of the most common sectors in Andalusia is the Olive tree. Andalusia is the main producer of olives and olive oil in the world and this kind of activity is non-irrigated. However, the biggest non-irrigated sector in Andalusia is the herbaceous one.

Fertilising products sector in relation to the waste streams studied in the region: wastewater and sewage sludge. Currently the main source of macronutrients is represented by fertilisers of mineral origin, highly dependent on natural gas for the extraction and their production. Among the three macronutrients (N-P-K) Nitrogen represents the main supply in terms of amount delivered, during the seasonal fertiliser plan it accounts for 220,000 tons for Urea only, that represents the most widespread inorganic fertiliser. It follows the Phosphorus consume through Diammonium phosphate for the most (86 000 tons), while Potassium is delivered through mainly Potassium chloride formulation accounting in 2020 for 60,000 tons.

In 2016, the number of sewage treatment plants amounted to 695, considering both those built (668) and those under construction. With a total volume of 698.17 Hm³/year treated wastewater produced in Andalusian UWWTP, the region has a strong potential to use reclaimed water in agriculture. According to the most recent data (2020), 5.22 % of the treated wastewater was finally reused as reclaimed water in Andalusia (36,49 Hm³/year)

Regulatory and institutional framework. The Spanish regulations for water reuse were approved in December 2007, as a Royal Decree 1620/2007. The RD 1620/2007 defines the practice of “water reuse”, introducing the term “reclaimed water”, determining the minimum requirements to develop a safe reuse of reclaimed water, setting the protocols to be followed for getting reclaimed water rights, establishing the scope of water reuse practices (with specific prohibition of certain reclaimed water uses) and setting forth the quality requirements associated to each specific water reuse option. The production and supply of reclaimed water for agricultural irrigation requires a permit. Parties concerned must submit an application to the relevant national authority.

Andalusia faces relevant challenges in the wastewater treatment sector and still fails to comply entirely with the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive. Nevertheless, the wastewater treatment has followed a very positive evolution in this region.

Large volumes of digestate are continuously produced during the purification of unconventional water. Over the years and with the introduction of policies aimed at the circular economy, the digestate has been re-evaluated from waste to resource for the interception of useful substances in agriculture such as organic fertilisers.

3.6.2. Main findings

The waste streams **wastewater** and **sewage sludge** have been considered as secondary raw materials' sources for producing alternative fertilisers in Andalusia region, Spain. The main actions outlined per each priority area are summarised in the following table. .

Table 6. Main actions outlined in the RSAP of Andalusia region, Spain

What will we do?	How will we do it	When is it being proposed?	Who will be responsible?	Status (Completed / In Process / Awaiting)	Possible Funding Sources
<p>Priority area 1: Legal Framework</p>					
Regularisation of irrigation communities, encouraging farmers to associate to have a more efficient and controlled water management.	1. Creation of associations and federations of irrigators that contribute to regularising and updating water rights.	To be accomplished by 2030.	Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, farmers, associations, unions.	<i>Awaiting</i>	National and regional funding.
Harmonisation of national and European legislation.	1. Set goals to guarantee EU legislation compliance.	To be accomplished by 2025.	Farmers, associations, unions, industrial sector, research centres.	<i>In Process</i>	EU funded projects.
<p>Priority area 2: Political Willingness</p>					
Increase of specialised staff in public administration.	1. Increasing the budget devoted to hire administrative staff to speed up the processing and evaluation of applications and files. 2. Promote training, as well as the need of a minimum target of specialised workers in the public administration in the framework of the National Hydrological Plan.	To be accomplished by 2030.	Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.	<i>Awaiting</i>	National funds.

	3. Coordination among different public administrations and knowledge exchange.				
Coordination between national and regional administrations.	1. Drive the coordination between national and regional administrations.	To be accomplished by 2030.	Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.	<i>Awaiting</i>	National funds.
Foster a transparency portal.	1. Creation of a transparency portal to provide final consumers with information about the reclamation process, the water quality, and how the regulation is being complied.	To be accomplished by 2030.	Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.	<i>Awaiting</i>	National funds.
<p>Priority area 3: Research and technical development</p>					
Facilitation of data interoperability.	1. Determination and use of common criteria for data operability (“common language”). This includes the development of a data characterisation protocol and or a data interoperability protocol, as well as a data analysis tool.	To be accomplished by 2030.	Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, industrial sector, research centres.	<i>Awaiting</i>	EU, national and regional funding, private funding.
Improvement of the existing infrastructures.	1. Investments to improve secondary and tertiary treatment plants.	To be accomplished by 2034.	Private sector, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.	<i>Awaiting</i>	National funding, private funding.

Accessibility of reclaimed water to irrigable areas.	1. Assuring the connection between water reclamation facilities and irrigable areas.	To be accomplished by 2034.	Private sector, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.	<i>Awaiting</i>	National funding, private funding.
Need of reclaimed water storage infrastructures (irrigation pools).	1. Building reclaimed water storage infrastructures (irrigation pools).	To be accomplished by 2034.	Private sector, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.	<i>Awaiting</i>	National funding, private funding.
<p>Priority area 4: New business models</p>					
Creation of user associations that allow reducing the costs and scaling sensing technology.	1. Use of digital twin technology, which allows recommendations on efficient water use to be extrapolated to farms that do not have sensing technology, making possible reducing costs.	To be accomplished by 2028.	Private sector.	<i>Awaiting</i>	Private funding.
<p>Priority area 5: Financial incentives</p>					
Establishment of incentives for water saving.	1. Establishment of tax deductions for those farmers who, through introducing sensing technology in their farms, demonstrate that they are using water efficiently.	To be accomplished by 2030.	Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.	<i>Awaiting</i>	National funding.

Establishment of a joint venture capital fund – sector fund.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Characterisation of the sector, identifying the most influential producers. 2. Preparation of a model framework as a baseline to start working. 	To be accomplished by 2028.	Private sector.	<i>Awaiting</i>	Private funding.
Public administration provides economic incentives to farmers that use alternative fertilisers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Developing awareness campaigns to promote alternative fertilisers, contributing to the EU strategy “Farm to Fork” at the local and regional levels. 2. Creating a set of National, regional, and/or local taxes bonification/exemptions. 3. Developing preferential financing options for alternative fertiliser infrastructure. 	To be accomplished by 2030.	Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.	<i>Awaiting</i>	EU, national and regional funding, private funding.
<p>Priority area 6: Self sufficiency</p>					
Creation of an open digital platform at EU level to be continuously fed with onsite data.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of public AI models for specific and tailored recommendations for each crop. 2. Development of free mobile applications with public domain application for crop monitoring. 	To be accomplished by 2028.	Private sector, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.	<i>Awaiting</i>	EU, national and regional funding, private funding.
Updating the existing infrastructure.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Study on the existing vs. the needed infrastructures. This includes the study of population growth and associated needs. In addition, data collection will be necessary for an appropriated hydrological planning. 2. Incorporation of renewable energies for production. This includes the evaluation of renewable energies that are adaptable to the environment, as well as the energy needs of the new infrastructures to be developed. 	To be accomplished by 2034.	Private sector, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.	<i>Awaiting</i>	EU, national and regional funding, private funding.

	<p>Moreover, environmental feasibility studies may be needed.</p> <p>3. Establishment / improvement of distribution structures to facilitate the user access to reclaimed water.</p>				
<p>Priority area 7: Public acceptance</p>					
Promoting the citizenship participation.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of an advertising campaign promoting the positive aspects of using reclaimed water, including healthiness and safety of the food produced with this resource. 2. Contacting a personality from the region, close to the general public, who can articulate the correct message on the benefits of using reclaimed water as alternative fertiliser and attract the attention of the audience. 3. Inserting institutional advertising in prime time. 4. Making (general and specialised) information accessible through public websites. 	To be accomplished by 2028.	Private sector, research centres, marketing companies, communication professionals, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge	<i>Awaiting</i>	EU, national and regional funding, private funding.
Creation of communication campaigns for young students.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of communication campaigns at schools, and also via social networks, to engage the citizens since early age. 2. Creating communication materials adapted according to the different age groups, including also targeted influencers or referents. 	To be accomplished by 2026.	Private sector, research centres, marketing companies, communication professionals.	<i>In process</i>	EU, national and regional funding, private funding.
Creation of an official certificate on the products' circularity.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of a commission of experts to design the circularity certificate. 	To be accomplished by 2028.	Private sector, research centres, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the	<i>Awaiting</i>	EU, national and regional funding, private funding.

			Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge		
Training and information for stakeholders involved in the decision-making process.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of a regional training centre (online or presential). 2. Involvement of unions and agricultural associations to support this training and attack the stakeholders, as they are their first reference. 3. Call from the regional government (Junta de Andalucía) for the specialisation in the use of regenerated water, making thus necessary this kind of training. 4. Facilitation of this training by regional research institutions (IFAPA, LA Mayora, etc.), the authorised control bodies (OCAs), etc. 5. Collaboration of qualified farmers willing to share their experience. 6. Organisation of demonstration workshops, open days, etc. 	To be accomplished by 2026.	Private sector, research centres, marketing companies, communication professionals.	<i>In process</i>	EU, national and regional funding, private funding.
<p>Priority area 8: Environmental protection</p>					
Emerging and other pollutants removal from reclaimed water.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Implementing efficient equipment to remove emerging and other pollutants from reclaimed water. 	To be accomplished by 2026.	Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.	<i>Awaiting</i>	EU, national and regional funding, private funding.

3.7. Spain – Catalonia

3.7.1. Regional characterisation

Socio-economic characterisation of the region. Catalonia, located in northeastern Spain, is a region characterised by a diverse and dynamic socio-economic landscape. Catalonia covers an area of approximately 32,000 square kilometres. Most of its territory (except the Val d'Aran) lies northeast of the Iberian Peninsula, south of the Pyrenees Mountain range. Catalonia is administratively divided into four provinces: Barcelona, Girona, Lleida, and Tarragona. The capital and largest city, Barcelona, is the second-most populated municipality in Spain and the fifth-most populous urban area in the European Union.

Catalonia boasts a varied landscape, including fertile plains, rugged mountains, and a Mediterranean coastline, contributing to its agricultural productivity. The region's agriculture is known for its focus on high-quality, locally grown products, strongly emphasising sustainable and organic farming practices. Catalonia is renowned for its vineyards, producing world-class wines and sparkling cava. Additionally, it is a significant producer of fruits, mainly citrus fruits, vegetables, and nuts.

Agriculture. The region's agriculture is known for its focus on high-quality, locally grown products, strongly emphasising sustainable and organic farming practices. Catalonia is renowned for its vineyards, producing world-class wines and sparkling cava. Additionally, it is a significant producer of fruits, mainly citrus fruits, vegetables, and nuts.

So far, manure has been directly applied as organic fertiliser in crop fields to produce different types of fruits and cereals, nuts and vegetables. The potential contamination of soil and water created by animal manure could be mitigated using biobased fertilisers derived from manure. However, this is still limited to a reduced number of available products without a clear overview of the numbers.

Fertilising products sector in relation to the waste streams studied in the region: animal manure. Currently, the primary source of macronutrients is fertilisers of mineral origin, highly dependent on natural gas for extraction and production. Among the three macronutrients (N-P-K), nitrogen represents the main supply regarding the amount delivered. Catalunya required 22.942 T of N, 6.633 T of P₂O₅ and 22.793 T of K₂O in 2022 in form of external mineral fertilisers.

In Catalonia, there are approximately 7.9 million pigs, 637,000 head of cattle, and 44.6 million poultry (DARP, 2020), generating around 9.4 million tons of slurry and 2.8 million tons of manure and hens yearly. The agriculture and livestock sector contributes 12% of the greenhouse gases emitted in Catalonia. Of these emissions, it is estimated that 47% occur while managing livestock manure. The livestock sector is also responsible for the emission of 92% of atmospheric ammonia.

Over the years, excessive application of manure to crops has resulted in the accumulation of phosphorus in the soil and nitrate in the groundwater.

Regulatory and institutional framework. In accordance with the European Directive on nitrates, currently, 33.8% of the total area of Catalonia is declared vulnerable to pollution by nitrates of agricultural origin and affects 422 municipalities, i.e. 45% of all Catalan municipalities (ACA, 2020). Currently, no regulation in Catalonia establishes maximum concentrations of P according to crop and agroclimatic zone, but there are maximum P levels in the soil.

3.7.2. Main findings

The waste streams **animal manure** has been considered as secondary raw materials' sources for producing alternative fertilisers in Catalonia region, Spain. The main actions outlined per each priority area are summarised in the following table.

Table 7. Main actions outlined in the RSAP of Catalonia region, Spain

What will we do?	How will we do it	When is it being proposed?	Who will be responsible?	Status (Completed / In Process / Awaiting)	Possible Funding Sources
 Priority area 1: Legal Framework					
Revision of normative limitations towards promoting the construction of collective by-product valorisation plants in Catalonia.	2. Evaluation and mapping on the manure treatment volume needed to be treated in these exceptional plants. Strategic distribution of plants in the territory. 3. Establishment of some exceptions to be able to reduce the minimum distance between	To be accomplished by 2025.	Departments of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia and of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biogas plant promoters, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres.	<i>Awaiting</i>	Public funding from the Catalanian Government.

	a by-product treatment/valorisation plant and livestock farms due to the real livestock management. Additionally, evaluation on exceptions to accept manure from the same epidemiological unit and of the same owner in an on-farm treatment system will be promoted.				
Proposal to amend the National regulation on wastes (Law 7/2022) to determine an end point in the manufacture of fertilisers currently not included in EU regulation 2019/1009.	1. Amendment request.	To be accomplished by 2030.	General Directorate of Agriculture, Catalonian Waste Agency, Departments of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia and of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biogas plant promoters, composting companies, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres.	<i>Awaiting</i>	No funding needed.
Proposal to amend the National regulation on wastes (Law 7/2022) to facilitate the utilisation of certain organic by-products in alternative fertilisers production and subsequent commercialisation.	1. Assess under which regulations the products resulting from their processing will be marketed. Identification of key materials currently not allowed to reach the end-of waste status enabling their commercialisation. 2. Data gathering on the effects (logistics, market perspective, business models) on the impact of the application of article 28 of the waste law on existing and new installations. 3. Compilation of quality and safety criteria and certificates for	To be accomplished by 2030.	Departments of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia and of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, Catalonian Waste Agency, Catalonian Water Agency, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biogas plant promoters, composting companies, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres.	1. <i>In Process</i> 2. <i>In Process</i> 3. <i>Awaiting</i> 4. <i>In Process</i> 5. <i>In Process</i>	No funding needed.

	<p>materials that cannot reach the end-of waste status, to help give value to these materials that cannot be marketed as a product, also by consumers.</p> <p>4. Distribution and sharing of the data compiled. Discussion with the competent authority of the findings.</p> <p>5. Propose the modification of the Waste Law 7/2022 to establish the end-of-waste status of the materials identified.</p>				
Recognition of RENURE (Recovered Nitrogen from Manures) products.	<p>1. Transfer to the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture the convenience of using RENURE as analogous to mineral fertilisers.</p> <p>2. Develop and follow up of RENURE fertilisers (pilot testing and public funding to related projects).</p> <p>3. Assessing the possibility of including further derivatives of the digestate, in addition to the products accepted to meet the RENURE criteria, within the framework of the RENURE initiative.</p>	To be accomplished by 2030.	Departments of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia and of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.	<p>1. <i>In Process</i></p> <p>2. <i>Awaiting</i></p> <p>3. <i>In Process</i></p>	No funding needed.
Promotion of alternative fertilisers in the sector of organic farming.	<p>1. Unification of criteria for the definition of intensive farming, and assessing the efforts needed towards converting conventional farms in Catalonia into suitable</p>	To be accomplished by 2030.	Departments of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia and of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, policy makers at regional, national and EU level,	<i>In Process</i>	No funding needed.

	<p>rearing systems in organic farming sector.</p> <p>2. Promotion of the representation of the Catalanian region in the technical expert groups advising the decision-making organisms related to the organic farming sector (EGTOP, EU CAP NETWORK, DG AGRI, DG ENV, etc.).</p> <p>3. Compilation of relevant data on quality and safety aspects of alternative fertilisers of the products obtained from the conventional farms and compare the composition of the components from the extensive farms.</p>		<p>particularly the competent authorities in organic farming issues (EGTOP; DG AGRI, DG ENVI), agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.</p>		
<p>Promotion of the establishment of new end-points in the manufacturing chain in the framework of animal by-products regulation (Reg 1009/2009 and Implementing Regulation 142/2011).</p>	<p>1. Creation of a working group with different entities in the sector (private sector, research centres, administration) to promote the incorporation of alternative methods of final points of the manufacturing chain (PCFC).</p> <p>2. Encourage the generation of studies to incorporate new end points of the manufacturing chain (PCFC) through the inclusion in calls for funding for R+D+i projects.</p>	<p>To be accomplished by 2030.</p>	<p>Catalonian Waste Agency, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.</p>	<p><i>Awaiting</i></p>	<p>No funding needed.</p>

Priority area 2: Political Willingness

<p>Improve the characterisation, quantification and optimisation of generation and distribution of organic by-products or biomass (mentioned in EBC2030 and CBP).</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Elaboration of a guide according to the Waste Catalogue of Catalonia, to assist identifying the types of organic wastes and their codification, that could be processed in valorisation plants. 2. Generation of information on the potential wastes that could be managed via certain technological processes (anaerobic digestion, stripping, composting etc.). 	<p>To be accomplished by 2025.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Catalanian Waste Agency, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres. 2. Catalanian Waste Agency, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production 	<p><i>Awaiting</i></p>	<p>Catalonian Government, Waste Agency.</p>
<p>Development of a business network based on the circular bioeconomy throughout the territory, with special attention to the first sector and promotion of industrial symbiosis.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Development of the Catalanian Bioeconomy-Hub. 2. Promotion of the consumption of the bioproducts obtained through adequate communication and marketing strategies, environmental declarations and labelling. 3. Promotion of research, innovation and knowledge transfer related to circular bioeconomy. A program for the capitalisation of results should be foreseen together with advisory services for the whole value chain. 	<p>To be accomplished by 2030.</p>	<p>Public administration, stakeholders from the whole value chain including industry, research and general society.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Completed</i> 2. <i>In Process</i> 3. <i>In Process</i> 	<p>Catalonian Government.</p>

<p>Promotion of the adoption of measures to shortening and simplifying the procedures for the licences for the valorisation plants for by-products.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of a working group of the units involved in environmental, energy and urban processing. 2. Preparation of a specific templates to present by-product valorisation projects, an orientation guide for the processing of projects and technical instruction for the procedures for the manufacture and marketing of alternative fertilisers products. 3. Revision of other legal requirements related to other normative frameworks that could potentially apply and integrate the requirements identified in the same procedure. 4. Detailed description of the administrative procedures for the management and processing of the by-products and alternative fertilising products and coordination of the different Departments and Agencies to unify criteria and have a single solution. 	<p>To be accomplished by 2025.</p>	<p>Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda as main responsible, other several departments in the Catalonian Government like DG Environmental Quality and Climate Change, DG Energy, DG Agriculture and Livestock, DG Services, Water Agency, Waste Agency, DG Spatial Planning, Urbanism and Architecture and the Catalonian Institute of the Energy (ICAEN).</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>In Process</i> 2. <i>In Process</i> 3. <i>Awaiting</i> 4. <i>Awaiting</i> 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Catalonian Government. 2. Catalonian Government, Waste Agency. 3. No funding needed. 4. Catalonian Government, Waste Agency.
<p>Determine the targets to be accomplished and implementation model of recovered fertilisers in Catalonia.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establishing the target of the treatment plants to be built in Catalonia by 2030. 	<p>To be accomplished by 2024.</p>	<p>Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.</p>	<p><i>In Process</i></p>	<p>Catalonian Government.</p>

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Estimation on the economic support for existing and new plants targeted. 3. Establishing the management model for each of the plants foreseen and estimation on the need of infrastructure and its distribution across the region. 4. Establishing quantitative and qualitative objectives for plants and identifying barriers followed by the planification of potential actions to overcome them. 				
Promotion of the creation of the Catalonian Platform of Nutrients	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identification and mapping of the key actors involved in the whole nutrients' value chain. 2. Elaboration of the strategic plan, governance model and viability plan of the Catalonian Nutrient Platform. 3. Legal establishment of the platform. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To be accomplished by 2025. 2. To be accomplished by 2026. 3. To be accomplished by 2026. 	Generators of effluents rich in nutrients, farmers, related industries like suppliers of nutrient valorisation/recovery technologies, fertiliser producers, reference research centres, related associations, public administration.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>In Process</i> 2. <i>Awaiting</i> 3. <i>Awaiting</i> 	Catalonian Government.
Promotion of new accredited Notified Bodies for CMCs 3, 5, 12 and 13 in Catalonia.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Evaluate the conformity evaluation procedure as a bottleneck for the manufacture and marketing of fertiliser products derived from digestate. 2. Development of a work plan with measures to facilitate and streamline the conformity assessment. 	To be accomplished by 2030.	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.	<i>Awaiting</i>	Catalonian Government.

Priority area 3: Research and technical development

<p>Promotion of research projects related to experimentation and demonstration of the benefits of the use of alternative fertilisers in agricultural fields.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Promotion of demonstration projects in the experimental fields that the Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda holds for this kind of demonstration. Promotion of R&D&I projects in collaboration with other research institutions. 	<p>To be accomplished by 2030.</p>	<p>Departments of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia and of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, Waste Agency and Catalanian Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology, agricultural and livestock sector, agricultural, industrial, biogas plant promoters, biofertilisers marketing companies, research centres.</p>	<p><i>In Process</i></p>	<p>Catalonian Government, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production.</p>
<p>Promotion of research projects towards demonstrating the feasibility of alternative processing methods towards the establishment of the end-point in the manufacturing chain of animal by-products (in the framework of Reg 1069/2009 and Implementing Regulation 142/2011).</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Public calls for funding related to this topic. 	<p>To be accomplished by 2030.</p>	<p>Catalonian Waste Agency.</p>	<p><i>Awaiting</i></p>	<p>Catalonian Government, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production.</p>
<p>Promotion of studies assessing the techno-economic feasibility of several organic by-product treatment systems.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Promotion of a specific funding program for the pre-feasibility of organic by-product treatment systems, including the assessment of the most suitable treatment technology(ies) and a 	<p>To be accomplished by 2030.</p>	<p>Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda</p>	<p><i>Awaiting</i></p>	<p>Catalonian Government, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of</p>

	techno-economic feasibility study.				Agricultural Production.
Promotion of research and innovation studies focused on reducing the cost of treatment and valorisation of organic by-products and maximising their potential benefits.	1. Promotion of such studies.	To be accomplished by 2030.	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda	<i>Awaiting</i>	Catalonian Government, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production.
<p>Priority area 4: New business models</p>					
Creation of rules for a Carbon credits market.	1. Other incentives based on the resources prevented.	To be accomplished by 2030.	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.	<i>Awaiting</i>	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.
Inclusion of sustainable nutrient management schemes in a certification system.	1. Inclusion of sustainable nutrient management schemes in a certification system.	To be accomplished by 2030.	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.	<i>Awaiting</i>	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.
Efforts to find synergies between livestock farmers, waste producers and nearby by-product treatment facilities towards developing new business models.	1. Promote conferences and technical meetings that can help create synergies, within the framework of the Bioeconomy Strategy of Catalonia 2030. 2. Creation of a figure within the Administration that facilitates synergies between these sectors.	To be accomplished by 2030.	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.	1. <i>In Process</i> 2. <i>Awaiting</i> 3. <i>Awaiting</i> 4. <i>Awaiting</i>	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Development of a digital platform to put into contact the waste/by-product producers with the manufacturers of fertilising products. Provide a list of companies that provide by-product treatment technologies and manufacturers and marketers of organic fertiliser products, detailing the type of products they market. 				
Promoting the market of the alternative fertilisers obtained from post processing of organic by-products.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting the quality of the alternative fertilisers to facilitate the development of the market for those products. Promoting technology implementation towards obtaining high quality fertilisers with potential to be competitive in the fertilising product market. Application of environmental labels. 	To be accomplished by 2030.	Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia, Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.	<i>In Process</i>	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.
Promotion of intermediate processing units and shared infrastructure schemes for the management, storage and concentration of nutrients in organic by-products.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Assessment of the techno-economic feasibility of the schemes proposed and their governance systems. 	To be accomplished by 2030.	Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia, Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.	<i>Awaiting</i>	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.
 Priority area 5: Financial incentives					

<p>Public administration provides economic incentives to build organic by-product treatment plants and to increase infrastructure for alternative fertiliser manufacturing plants.</p>	<p>1. Developing awareness campaigns to promote alternative fertilisers, contributing to the EU strategy "Farm to Fork" at the local and regional levels.</p>	<p>Accomplished by 2026.</p>	<p>Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia, Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.</p>	<p><i>In Process</i></p>	<p>Catalonian Government already makes available public subsidies in 3 annual calls (budgets: 46M€ for 2024; 25M€ for 2025 and 9M€ for 2026) for new biogas plants (46M€) and digestate post-processing (3M€) in 2024.</p>
<p>Articulation of public subsidies towards co-financing organic by-products treatment plants.</p>	<p>1. Articulation of public subsidies towards co-financing organic by-products treatment plants.</p>	<p>According to the Catalanian Government, a new budget line is foreseen for the same issue for the period between 2027 and 2030.</p>	<p>Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia, Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.</p>	<p><i>In Process</i></p>	<p>Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.</p>
<p>Priority area 6: Self sufficiency</p>					
<p>Enhancement of the production of several bio-products by improving the operation of technological infrastructures.</p>	<p>1. Encourage the techniques and design the most efficient facilities on farms to improve the productivity of bio-products, including alternative fertilisers, and facilitate the transformation of current infrastructure to the ones better suited for circular bioeconomy.</p>	<p>To be accomplished by 2030.</p>	<p>Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia, Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.</p>	<p><i>In Process</i></p>	<p>Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.</p>

Promotion of self-consumption in industry.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Promote the modification of the electricity self-consumption national regulation (Royal Decree 244/2019). In the case of anaerobic digestion plants, promote the use of biogas and biomethane. 	To be accomplished by 2030.	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, Spanish Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.	<i>Awaiting</i>	No funding needed.
Incentives for the dependence reduction from third countries with geopolitical conflicts.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Promotion of RENURE products to reduce the dependency on synthetic mineral fertilisers. Promotion of phosphorus rich products such as struvite or similar to reduce the dependency on synthetic mineral fertilisers. Promotion of carbon-rich products in agriculture to promote soils' health and its microbial activity to optimise the agricultural production limiting the use of nutrients. 	To be accomplished by 2030.	Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia, Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.	<i>In Process</i>	Catalonian Government, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production.
 Priority area 7: Public acceptance					
Promotion of the circular bioeconomy model, including the acceptance of organic by-product transformation technological processes and end products by the	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Pedagogy in society to inform on the benefits of alternative fertiliser production from by-products such as of manure and organic waste. 	To be accomplished by 2030.	Departments of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia and of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, research institutions, manufacturers of alternative fertilisers, farmers, industrial sector, other layers of public administration.	<i>In Process</i>	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

end-users and general society.					
Promotion of workshops related to the alternative fertilisers in the framework of specific conferences and workshops.	1. Promotion of workshops related to the alternative fertilisers (from production step to the utilisation) in the framework of specific conferences and workshops.	These workshops have been promoted for some years. This action should be extended as long as it is required to improve the public acceptance of the alternative fertilisers.	Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, research centres, manufacturers of alternative fertilisers, farmers and public administration	<i>In Process</i>	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.
 Priority area 8: Environmental protection					
Development of rules for eco-labelling.	1. Development of rules for eco-labelling.	To be accomplished by 2030	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.	<i>Awaiting</i>	Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.
Application of environmental sustainability labels (eco-labels).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Preparation of a manual or guide for the estimation of GHG emissions from alternative fertilisers manufacturing activities and the emission reduction achieved with the actions carried out. Estimation of GHG emissions from facilities generating biodegradable organic resources. Establishment of a public certification of the sustainability 	To be accomplished by 2025.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1+2. Catalanian Office for the Climate Change, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production, Waste Agency, Water Agency, Catalanian Institute of the Energy (ICAEN), research institutions. 3+4. Departments of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalanian and of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, SG of Livestock, DG of Agri-Food Companies, Quality, and 	<i>Awaiting</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Catalonian Office for the Climate Change. Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda. Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

	<p>of agricultural holdings and animal husbandries.</p> <p>4. Creation of a Sustainable Agricultural Production (SAP) label that contemplates the production and valorisation of the by-products generated.</p>		<p>Gastronomy, Waste Agency, research institutions.</p>		<p>4. Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.</p>
<p>Promotion of the implementation of Best Available Techniques (BAT) in the whole value chain of nutrients to avoid or minimise ammonia emissions.</p>	<p>1. Financial incentives in this line should be articulated</p>	<p>To be accomplished by 2030.</p>	<p>Catalonian Office for the Climate Change (OCCC) while it involves also other departments (Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production, Waste Agency, Water Agency) and Catalanian Institute of the Energy (ICAEN).</p>	<p><i>Awaiting</i></p>	<p>Catalonian Office for the Climate Change</p>

4. Regional Specific Action Plans

4.1. Belgium – Flanders

4.1.1. Methodology

Most of the information was gathered in the framework of the 1st NOVAFERT participatory workshop organised in Belgium. On April 26th, Nutricycle Vlaanderen, together with NOVAFERT, ReNu2Cycle and Soilutions, invited Flemish farmers, knowledge centres and companies to discuss alternative fertilisers such as frass, struvite and ammonium salts, which can potentially replace traditional artificial fertilisers. In order to tailor circular fertilisers even better to crop needs, combinations of circular fertilisers that can meet nitrogen and/or sulphur needs in a more balanced way were also discussed. Companies putting innovation into practice were among the speakers too. 38 people actively participated.

Key question was: How do you, as a farmer, work with these sustainable forms of fertilisation, making sure to apply the right amount of nitrogen, sulphur or phosphorus, also via the use of mixtures?

Figure 5. Invitation to the 1st NOVAFERT participatory workshop organised in Flanders region, Belgium

Figure 6. 1st NOVAFERT participatory workshop organised in Flanders region, Belgium

4.1.2. Regional Action Plan

The RSAP is structured, as already explained, in the 8 common priority areas identified in the GAP.

Priority area 1: Legal Framework.

- Action 1.1: **Incentive policy.**

The Flemish judgment to promote sustainable development guarantees the continuity of sustainable development policy. The Flemish Strategy for Sustainable Development (VSDO) forms the framework of the Flemish policy for sustainable development.

The current version of the VSDO is included in Vision 2050, the future vision of the Flemish Government. Within the abovementioned.

Long-term Vision 2050, Flemish Policy, through its agencies, aims, among other things, for "Agro-ecological innovation".

- a) Step 1.1.1: interdisciplinary collaboration. A successful transition implies interdisciplinary collaboration between sectors focused on the environment, agriculture, innovation, circular economy.
- b) Step 1.1.2: removing legal barriers. Actors in the field often experience the legal framework as a delaying factor in the implementation of recovery techniques. In the context of the proposed transition, research can be done into creating 'room for experimentation' or 'restricted zones'. For example, space can be provided for the sometimes-difficult starting phase of an innovative project.
- c) Step 1.1.3: lead by example. Proactive policy: To realise the transition in Flanders, there is a need in the coming years, all sectors will work hard on a stimulating and coherent approach.
- d) Step 1.1.4: research into related legislation. This transition is closely related to how (European) legislation continues to evolve.
- e) Step 1.1.5: consultation with the Flemish entities. Consultation with the Flemish entities to coordinate the implementation of the action plan and policy to vote.

Timing: long term vision (by 2050).

Status: in process.

Responsible: Nutricycle Vlaanderen (nutricycle.vlaanderen@ugent.be). Executors involved: VLM, VMM, OVAM, L&V, Dept. Environment, EWI, VLAIO, Boerenbond, ABS, FEVIA, VCM, Aquafin.

Possible funding sources: regular operation of the mentioned organisations.

Expected output:

- Interdisciplinary consultation and action between different sectors.
 - Assessment of legal barriers and consideration of room for experimentation and low-regulation zones.
- Action 1.2: **Communication: translate national and international policy developments and research into the Flemish context and disseminate nutrient-related information.**

In Flanders, there is a pronounced need to translate international developments in the context of project work on nutrient recovery into a local context. [NUTRICYCLE VLAANDEREN](#), a Flemish consultation platform, is committed to translating international developments in the field of nutrient recovery to the Flemish context and the Dutch language during the term, by translating scientific or technical reports into brochures and texts tailored to target groups that can work with them, thus making them accessible for various target groups. Attention will not only be paid to the technical aspect of nutrient recovery, product (composition) and sales markets, but the broader context will also be discussed (environment, safety, financing mechanisms, etc.).

- a) Step 1.2.1: Nutricycle Vlaanderen Flemish consultation platform website. Information and updates, including all developments and initiatives regarding nutrient recovery, event announcements and relevant project calls, are shared via the website. It also contains an overview of all nutrient-related projects, all publications and information about the operation of the platform. Social media presence is expanded for frequent news updates. Collaboration with other organisations enhances information transfer through shared content on social media, newsletters, websites, and trade press articles.
- b) Step 1.2.2: Nutricycle Vlaanderen Flemish consultation platform brochures. Easy-to-read, practice-oriented brochures provide concrete, useful information for specific target groups, translating international research into the Flemish context. These cover all aspects of nutrient recovery to keep various audiences informed about the latest developments.

Timing: 4-monthly newsletter, 3 brochures per working year, 1 policy brief per year.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Nutricycle Vlaanderen (nutricycle.vlaanderen@ugent.be). Executors involved: VLM, VMM, OVAM, L&V, Dept. Environment, EWI, VLAIO, Boerenbond, ABS, FEVIA, VCM, Aquafin.

Possible funding sources: regular operation of the mentioned organisations.

Priority area 2: Political willingness.

- Action 2.1: **Establish a Multi-Stakeholder Task Force.**

Create a coalition comprising government officials, agricultural experts, industry leaders, farmers, environmental organisations, and researchers to collectively advocate for biobased fertilisers.

- a) Step 2.1.1: identify and invite key stakeholders.
- b) Step 2.1.2: schedule regular meetings to discuss goals, challenges, and strategies.
- c) Step 2.1.3: assign roles and responsibilities for advocacy and outreach efforts.

Timing: already established, and further communications are ongoing.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Nutricycle Vlaanderen (nutricycle.vlaanderen@ugent.be).

Possible funding sources: EU projects.

Priority area 3: Research and technical development.

- Action 3.1: **Flanders as a European knowledge region in the field of nutrient cycling and recovery.**

Over the past 20 years, Flanders has emerged as a region within Europe with pronounced expertise in the field of mitigation of nutrient problems, and also as a forerunner in nutrient recovery technology. Research at knowledge centres, practice centres, but also the business community have led the region to become a recognised authority. Flanders must also consolidate its pioneering role in the effective transition to implementation of this

knowledge with scientific research into agronomic and environmental performance of bio-based mineral nitrogen fertilisers (N) with specific attention to field validation. [Nutricycle Flanders](#), a dynamic Flemish network of experts supported by the broader RE-SOURCE.BIO and Biorefine Cluster Europe network, builds bridges across university associations and institutes.

- a) Step 3.1.1: digital, regularly updated inventory of research on Nutricycle Flanders website.
- b) Step 3.1.2: support of the broader RE-SOURCE.BIO and Biorefine Cluster Europe network.
- c) Step 3.1.3: connecting knowledge centres to further strengthen inter-university cooperation, including targeted workshops and webinars with the institutions involved.
- d) Step 3.1.4: analogous scientific cooperation framework between KULeuven and Ghent University, with a vision of expansion to other Flemish institutes, in the field of R&D on the Nexus Nutrients-Water-Energy.
- e) Step 3.1.5: organisation of the ManuREsource conference every two years by INAGRO, VCM and Ghent University. The intention is to moderate consultation between the regions, with Nutricycle Flanders as 'host' playing an important organising and moderating role.
- f) Step 3.1.6: organisation of the European Sustainable Nutrient Initiative by Ghent University in Brussels every year, focusing on scientific developments as well as technical substantiation aimed at legal developments ('Policy recommendation'). This event always has a strong link to the European Commission, in addition to collaborations with other Member States and regions.
- g) Step 3.1.7: Nutricycle Flanders is the party within the strong network of academic research responsible for the translation of international research into the Flemish language and context. It takes the lead in professionalisation, i.e., the translation of what research can mean in practice.

Timing: until 2029, ongoing efforts, annually.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ghent University, INAGRO, University of Antwerp, KU Leuven, VCM, Vlaco.

Possible funding sources: project financing; Flemish government; institutional resources institutions involved, Nutricycle Flanders.

Expected output:

Through Joint PhDs on nutrient recovery between the Flemish knowledge institutions, knowledge of nutrient flows and recovery techniques is further deepened and kept up to date. The flow of information and know-how to and from European partners is assured through the participation of Flemish knowledge institutions, companies and sector organisations in European projects:

- Joint PhD and exchange researcher community until 2029 in the frame of circular economy. Until 2029.
 - Nutricycle Vlaanderen also mediates an analogous scientific cooperation framework between KULeuven and Ghent University. Ongoing efforts.
 - Annual ManuREsource conference. Annually.
 - Annual European Sustainable Nutrient Initiative (ESNI) conference.
- Action 3.2: **Systemic scenario analysis for more sustainable nitrogen, phosphorus and protein flows in the food chain.**

This action includes the budget of the N, P and protein flows in the Flemish agricultural sector and the development of a model based on substance flow analyses with advanced indicators for nutrient efficiency and circularity that can be used to assess the impact of new and complex recovery scenarios through to be calculated for Flanders.

This flexible model can be used for the first time with high resolution on many different subsectors within the agri-food system, and can also consider protein in addition to the nutrients nitrogen and phosphorus. Moreover, the intention is to link this to ecological, economic and social sustainability analysis methods.

- a) Step 3.2.1: inventory of N and P flows in Flanders and identification of the junctions.
- b) Step 3.2.2: further develop and apply a powerful and user-friendly model to map shifts in nutrient and protein flows in Flanders, based on technological and social transition scenarios, including the sustainability impact on ecological, economic and social aspects.
- c) Step 3.2.3: recording and calculating indicators that estimate nutrient efficiency and circularity.

Timing: 2023-2026.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ghent University (erik.meers@ugent.be) and UAntwerp (Marc.Spiller@uantwerpen.be; siegfried.vlaeminck@uantwerpen.be).

Possible funding sources: department of the Environment, UA, Ghent University.

Expected output:

- Dynamic model that calculates the N, P and protein flows graphically with the support of so that emissions and hotspots are clearly displayed.
 - Selection and identification of the most appropriate recovery technologies and scenarios the Flemish context.
 - Potential further extension to NOVAFERT partner regions.
- Action 3.3: **Foster Public-Private Partnerships.**

Encourage investment and innovation in biobased fertiliser production and distribution.

- a) Step 3.3.1: identify potential private sector partners such as fertiliser companies and agritech startups.
- b) Step 3.3.2: facilitate collaboration between public institutions and private companies.
- c) Step 3.3.3: promote joint ventures and funding opportunities for R&D in biobased fertilisers.

Timing: ongoing, with initial partnerships established in the frame of multiple EU projects.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ghent University (erik.meers@ugent.be).

Possible funding sources: EC, Interreg, Vaio, etc.

Priority area 4: New business models.

- Action 4.1: Counter function for first-line advice.

Within the duration of Nutricycle Vlaanderen, a digital counter function is available to support the actors involved in nutrient recovery. The counter fulfils a first-line advisory function, offering initial advisory services, particularly for pilot projects and business cases, and directs inquiries to the most appropriate experts. It provides further assistance to companies with questions regarding nutrient recovery, with special attention to first-line advice on pilot projects and concrete business cases regarding nutrient recovery.

To prevent market disruption, the counter function initially focuses on correctly referring and cross-referring to experts (consultants, researchers, civil society, etc.) and following up on advice requests. The aim is not to take over the roles of existing organisations, but to provide necessary referrals, additional guidance, and aftercare.

- a) Step 4.1.1: providing a counter function (digital & contact person) where one can go for a complete picture of nutrient recovery in Flanders, as well as a point of contact for first-line advice and for relevant and specific referrals to the relevant civil society & other organisations active in this theme.

Timing: 2023-2026.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Nutricycle Vlaanderen (nutricycle.vlaanderen@ugent.be).

Possible funding sources: regular operation of Nutricycle Flanders (including via the Flemish Government Subsidy).

Expected output:

First-line advice or referral function; logging of the questions.

- Action 4.2: Drawing up a Green Deal for the implementation of the Action Plan.

A Green Deal is a voluntary agreement between (private) partners and the Flemish government to start a green project together. The Green Deal is an obligation of efforts, not an obligation of results, in which environmental goals are pursued that go hand in hand with increased competitiveness and good business operations. The Action Plan can be further brought to a

successful conclusion through a 'joint effort' between the Government and the professional field.

- a) Step 4.2.1: Nutricycle Flanders will catalyse and monitor this Green Deal.

Timing: 2023-2026.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Nutricycle Vlaanderen (nutricycle.vlaanderen@ugent.be).

Possible funding sources: N/A.

Expected output:

Further elaboration of the Action Plan.

Priority area 5: Financial incentives.

- Action 5.1: **Provision of economic incentives to farmers that use alternative fertilisers by public administration.**

- a) Step 5.1.1: developing awareness campaigns to promote alternative fertilisers, contributing to the EU strategy "Farm to Fork" at the local and regional levels.
- b) Step 5.1.2: creating a set of national, regional, and/or local taxes bonification / exemptions.
- c) Step 5.1.3: developing preferential financing options for alternative fertiliser infrastructure.

Timing: 1-2 years.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Nutricycle Vlaanderen (nutricycle.vlaanderen@ugent.be).

Possible funding sources: Flemish government.

Priority area 6: Self-sufficiency.

- Action 6.1: **Optimised manure management: by closing cycles at company level, such as pocket fermentation or farm composting.**

A number of measures can be taken at agricultural company level to close the cycles on site as much as possible, and therefore avoid transport and additional costs for external processing. Research is currently underway into two systems that allow reuse possible on site:

- Pocket fermentation, both the energy and nutrient cycles can be partially closed.
 - Farm composting, the nutrients in the waste streams are locally recovered as compost and this compost can also be reused on site, while nutrients and carbon are absorbed back into the soil.
- a) Step 6.1.1: monitoring nutrient management, including methane emissions from installed pocket digesters.

- b) Step 6.1.2: optimisation of nutrient use. At a number of typical companies, research is being done into which upstream and downstream techniques (pocket fermentation) are most suitable and provide the greatest added value for the company.
- c) Step 6.1.3: the experiences surrounding pocket fermentation and through networking moments / demo sessions / workshops further spread farm composting within the sector.
- d) Step 6.1.4: facilitating farm composting through support of local partnerships (legal framework, advice, analyses).

Timing: ongoing effort.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Inagro (sander.vandendriessche@inagro.be), ILVO (fiën.amery@ilvo.vlaanderen.be). Implementers involved: Biogas-E, UGent, VCM, KU Leuven, Bioelectric, PCS, PSKW, Vlaco, PCA, VCM, UGent, UE, Paardenpunt Vlaanderen.

Possible funding sources: regular operation of the organisations involved, OG, Vlaio LA, Vlaanderen Circulair, Interreg.

Expected output:

- Brochure focused on nutrient flows during small-scale fermentation.
- Research into the impact of upstream and downstream technologies on the economic picture.

Priority area 7: Public acceptance.

- Action 7.1: **Stakeholder interaction through organisation's own workshops and support organisation of other actors to shape the transition from nutrient removal to nutrient recovery.**

Nutricycle Flanders will involve the various knowledge actors in the transition to nutrient recovery and support. Through its work in the field of circular economy, and nutrient cycles in particular, Ghent University already collaborates with all universities, research institutions, agricultural practice centres and civil society organisations on nutrient recovery that take this theme to heart. The Nutricycle Vlaanderen platform will try to coordinate all current initiatives in an overarching and inclusive platform, where all stakeholders can exchange experience regarding research and application in practice. Research questions received from practice (business & agriculture) or government are linked as much as possible to current projects.

- a) Step 7.1.1: establishment of working groups. The working groups involve smaller groups discussing specific nutrient recovery themes, that can be introduced by any participant. The following working groups were set up in the context of Nutricycle Vlaanderen: nutrient recovery from (waste) water (chaired by Watercircle.be), from manure (chaired by VCM), from Agro & Food (chaired by Flanders' FOOD) and a working group on Sustainable Sales and Land use.

- b) Step 7.1.2: stakeholder work takes place during the organisation of NOVAFERT and other EU project's workshops. Smaller groups of interested participants come together to discuss a specific theme related to nutrient recovery.
- c) Step 7.1.3: working groups meetings. Working groups meet at the necessary and useful for practical operations frequency. The progress and operation of these working groups are also discussed and adjusted by the Steering Committee.
- d) Step 7.1.4: proposed actions: organisation two thematic workshops per year to discuss progress.

Timing: working groups already established in 2023; organisation of 2 thematic workshops per year.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Nutricycle Vlaanderen (nutricycle.vlaanderen@ugent.be), nutrient recovery from (waste) water (chaired by Watercircle.be), nutrient recovery from manure (chaired by VCM), nutrient recovery from Agro & Food (chaired by Flanders' FOOD), sustainable Sales and Land use.

Possible funding sources: EU projects.

Expected output:

- Input and feedback on the action plan.
 - Dissemination of relevant (project) information and results from operational groups and to research.
 - Feedback on positions regarding developments in European regulations and their implementation.
- Action 7.2: **Providing information to farmers about RENURE products and new organo-mineral fertilisers, growth substrates and soil improvers that (under the new EU regulations) can replace products from primary raw materials in Flanders.**

In addition to the policy aspect, which should create the legal possibility to use RENURE products derived from animal manure as a full-fledged mineral fertiliser (without 'animal manure' status). Sufficient information must also be provided to farmers to trust these end users to do with this new range of fertilisation products, the legal options surrounding their use, practical aspects and preconditions for their application. Currently, these products can already be used within the limit of animal manure (170 kg Ntot/ha). Information will also be disseminated about other new fertilisers and soil improvers that do not fall under the RENURE criteria.

- a) Step 7.2.1: Nutricycle Flanders will work together with civil society organisations and agricultural practice centres on a series of target group-oriented documents in the form of brochures and 'fact sheets'.
- b) Step 7.2.2: workshops / webinars will also be organised, as well as demonstration moments for farmers in the field.

Timing: already implemented as part of the NutriCycle project, to be expanded in the framework of continuing projects over the next three years.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Nutricycle Vlaanderen (nutricycle.vlaanderen@ugent.be). Executors involved: UGent, VCM, VLACO, Biogas-E, Boerenbond, ABS, ILVO, B3W, Inagro.

Possible funding sources: project operations.

Expected output:

- Targeted communication using brochures to various stakeholders about the use of bio-based and/or recovered products. The first example is the use of ammonium sulphate produced from (acid) air scrubbing of stables, dryers or linked to stripping/scrubbing expandable to other RENURE products that are currently available and can be used within 170 kg Ntot/ha. These brochures are aimed at users of bio-based fertilisers with useful information regarding composition, application method, storage, stability, cost, etc. As part of a number of ongoing European projects, research is being conducted into recovered nitrogen, which is then upgraded to fertiliser quality. However, the lion's share of this research takes place in an English-speaking context. The added value of Nutricycle Flanders consists of converting English publications (in the form of scientific articles, project deliverables, reports, etc.) into Flemish language and context.
- Organisation of at least 5 workshops or webinars for farmers with input from expertise from knowledge centres, agricultural practice centres, civil society organisations and farmers regarding bio-based and/or recovered products. Detailed information is provided regarding composition, options and conditions of use and background information based on previous experience in comparison with fertilisation regimes based on mineral fertiliser from artificial fertiliser.

Priority area 8: Environmental protection.

- Action 8.1: **Substantiating and supporting precision agriculture to achieve optimal coordination and allocation of raw materials based on local crop and soil needs.**

Data mining and modelling collect information that can be used to manage spatial and temporal variability within the field and accommodate any variations in fertiliser composition. Using advanced modelling and control technologies, raw material allocation is adjusted to variations in the field. This approach can lead to a sustainable increase in yield and income for the farmer, while a significant reduction in environmental impacts is expected.

- a) Step 8.1.1: setting up a centre for precision fertilisation in Flanders.
- b) Step 8.1.2: developing technology for variable fertilisation with various types of fertilisers.
- c) Step 8.1.3: specific soil management.

Timing: ongoing effort.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ghent University (Abdul.Mouazen@UGent.be) and KUL (wouter.saeys@kuleuven.be).

Possible funding sources: EU projects.

Expected output:

An increase in crop yield and income for farmers, while at the same time achieving a decrease in the ecological footprint (less leaching of nutrients, fewer greenhouse gases, etc.).

- Action 8.2: **Scientific research into agronomic and environmental performance of bio-based mineral nitrogen fertilisers (N) with specific attention to field validation.**

Before upgraded products can be promoted as full-fledged mineral fertilisers, their efficacy and effectiveness must be independently scientifically investigated and demonstrated, both agronomically and environmentally.

- a) Step 8.2.1: monitoring nitrogen losses due to volatilisation of ammoniacal nitrogen or nitrous oxide using gas exchange measurements when bio-based N fertilisers are compared with animal manure, digestate.
- b) Step 8.2.2: monitoring the quality (variation in composition, stability) of the bio-based mineral N fertilisers (Monitoring and interacting with living labs, conducting interviews with analysis labs and manufacturers, Investigating the possibilities for certification of such products).
- c) Step 8.2.3: building up practical experience in real conditions (fertilisation regimes and methods, storage and transport).

Timing: some of the analyses have already been done, but it will be ongoing effort within the framework of programs.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ghent University (erik.meers@ugent.be).

Possible funding sources: project operations.

Expected output:

Scientific articles & doctorates with specific information regarding exemption / efficacy, agronomic & environmental performance from current projects.

Conclusion:

Most of the activities proposed are ongoing already, with the exception of the Green Deal drawing up. One of the key actors in the region, apart from UGhent, is Nutricycle Vlaanderen, a Flemish consultation platform committed to translating international developments in the field of nutrient recovery to the Flemish context and the Dutch language. Many of the activities proposed are framed within a variety of EU projects, or are part of the regular operation of the stakeholders involved, thus it is highly probable the mentioned activities are fulfilled at least at medium term.

4.2. Croatia – Continental Croatia

4.2.1. Methodology

Most of the information was gathered in the framework of the 1st NOVAFERT participatory workshop organised in Croatia. On June 20th, IPS Konzalting organised this participatory workshop in the Faculty of Agriculture at the University of Zagreb.

4.2.2. Regional Action Plan

The RSAP is structured, as already explained, in the 8 common priority areas identified in the GAP.

Priority area 1: Legal Framework.

- Action 1.1: **Work with local agricultural associations and policymakers to advocate for regulatory adjustments that facilitate the adoption of alternative fertilisers.**

- a) Step 1.1.1: establish Collaborative Partnerships. Engage key stakeholders, including farmers, local agricultural associations, policymakers, and environmental groups, to create working groups dedicated for regular strategy meetings to promote alternative fertilisers.

Timing: from 01/05/2023.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, farmers, agricultural associations, policymakers, environmental NGOs.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- b) Step 1.1.2: research. Collect and analyse data on the benefits and challenges of alternative fertilisers, highlighting successful case studies from both local and international contexts.

Timing: from 01/01/2025. 6-9 months to conduct comprehensive research and compile findings.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural researchers, universities, policy analysts, farmers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- c) Step 1.1.3: implementation. Launch awareness campaigns to educate farmers and the public about the benefits of alternative fertilisers, monitoring progress and gathering feedback to refine strategies. These campaigns will aim to build widespread support and ensure successful adoption.

Timing: from 01/02/2025. 9-12 months to launch campaigns and establish ongoing monitoring mechanisms.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, local media and farmers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

The desired result is to establish a supportive regulatory framework that encourages the use of alternative fertilisers, ultimately leading to widespread adoption among farmers in Croatia. By collaborating with local agricultural associations and policymakers, the aim is to remove regulatory barriers, introduce incentives, and create guidelines that ensure the safe and effective use of alternative fertilisers, thereby promoting sustainable agricultural practices and improving soil health.

- Action 1.2: **Transfer of knowledge about good regulatory frameworks in other EU countries.**

- a) Step 1.2.1: identify best practices. Research and identify EU countries with successful regulatory frameworks for alternative fertilisers. Document their policies, regulations, and implementation strategies to create a comprehensive resource for adaptation in Croatia.

Timing: from 01/02/2025. 3-6 months to conduct research and compile detailed documentation.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural researchers, policy makers, government officials, and EU regulatory bodies.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- b) Step 1.2.2: attend knowledge exchange programs. Participate in workshops and seminars where policymakers, regulatory authorities, and stakeholders from different EU countries share their experiences and insights on effective regulatory frameworks for alternative fertilisers.

Timing: from 01/11/2024. 6-9 months to attend and actively engage in various knowledge exchange events.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, policy makers, regulatory authorities, agricultural associations, EU representatives.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- c) Step 1.2.3: information sharing platform. Maintain an online information-sharing platform to facilitate continuous exchange of regulatory knowledge and best practices among stakeholders.

Timing: from 01/02/2023.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural researchers, EU regulatory bodies, farmers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT, internally.

Expected output:

The desired result is to adapt and implement proven regulatory frameworks from other EU countries that successfully promote the use of alternative fertilisers. By transferring this knowledge, the aim is to establish effective regulations in Croatia that support sustainable agricultural practices, enhance soil health, and reduce environmental impact.

Priority area 2: Political willingness.

- Action 2.1: **Foster partnerships between governments, private sector, and NGOs to promote the use of alternative fertilisers.**

- a) Step 2.1.1: identify and engage stakeholders. Map out relevant government agencies, private sector companies, and NGOs that have an interest in sustainable agriculture and alternative fertilisers. Organise initial meetings to discuss potential collaboration opportunities and align on shared goals.

Timing: from 01/05/2023.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, government officials, private sector representatives, NGO leaders, agricultural experts.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- b) Step 2.1.2: establish cross-sector working groups, and combine resources to promote alternative fertilisers. These groups will develop strategies to promote the use of alternative fertilisers and support implementation initiatives.

Timing: from 01/03/2025. 4-6 months to establish working groups and begin collaborative efforts.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, members from government agencies, private companies, and NGOs.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- c) Step 2.1.3: conduct public awareness campaigns, advocate for supportive policies, and monitor and report progress. Launch public awareness campaigns to educate farmers and the general public about the benefits of alternative fertilisers. Advocate for supportive policies and regularly monitor and report progress to ensure transparency and continuous improvement.

Timing: from 01/11/2024. 6-12 months to plan and execute campaigns, with ongoing monitoring and reporting.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, marketing team, agricultural associations, policymakers, farmers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT, internally.

Expected output:

The desired result is to create a strong, collaborative network between government agencies, private sector companies, and NGOs that collectively promote the adoption of alternative fertilisers. This partnership aims to leverage the strengths of each sector to drive innovation, provide financial and technical support, and advocate for policy changes that facilitate the widespread use of sustainable fertilisation practices.

- Action 2.2: **Create a knowledge exchange campaign to learn from countries that have successfully implemented alternative fertilisers.**

- a) Step 2.2.1: identify and partner. Research on countries that have successfully implemented alternative fertilisers and identify key organisations and experts in those regions, establish partnerships, and formalise agreements for knowledge exchange.

Timing: from 01/02/2025. 3-6 months to identify successful countries, establish partnerships, and formalise agreements.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural researchers, international experts, government agencies, NGOs.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- b) Step 2.2.2: arrange study tours, workshops, seminars, and virtual knowledge-sharing activities where local stakeholders can learn directly from the experiences of successful countries. These activities will provide practical insights and foster direct interactions with experts.

Timing: from 01/03/2025. 6-9 months to plan and execute study tours, workshops, and virtual sessions.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, policy makers, agricultural extension officers, farmers, international experts.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- c) Step 2.2.3: evaluate outcomes and disseminate knowledge to local stakeholders. Evaluate the outcomes of the knowledge exchange activities to assess their effectiveness and applicability. Disseminate the acquired knowledge and best practices to local stakeholders through reports, presentations, and follow-up workshops to ensure widespread understanding and implementation.

Timing: from 01/04/2025. 3-6 months for evaluation and dissemination of knowledge, with ongoing updates as necessary.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural researchers, policymakers, farmers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

The desired result is to facilitate the transfer of knowledge and best practices from countries that have successfully implemented alternative fertilisers. By creating a knowledge exchange campaign, the aim is to equip local stakeholders with proven strategies, innovative approaches, and practical insights that can be adapted to the local context, thereby accelerating the adoption of sustainable fertilisation practices.

Priority area 3: Research and technical development.

- Action 3.1: **Raise awareness.**

- a) Step 3.1.1: create informative content (develop brochures, infographics, videos, and articles that showcase recent research findings, innovations, and the scientific benefits of alternative fertilisers). Develop a range of educational materials, including brochures, infographics, videos, and articles, that showcase recent research findings, innovations, and the scientific benefits of alternative fertilisers. These materials will be used to inform and engage farmers, agricultural businesses, and policymakers.

Timing: from 01/07/2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural researchers, marketing team, graphic designers, content creators.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- b) Step 3.1.2: simplify technical information. Translate complex research and development data into easy-to-understand language, ensuring that farmers, agricultural stakeholders, and the general public can grasp the information. This involves creating user-friendly guides, summaries, and visual aids that make the technical details accessible.

Timing: from 01/01/2023.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural experts, communication specialists.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- c) Step 3.1.3: highlight successful case studies that demonstrate the positive impact of alternative fertilisers on crop yields, soil health, and environmental sustainability. Collect and present successful case studies that demonstrate the positive impact of alternative fertilisers on crop yields, soil health, and environmental sustainability. Use these case studies in various promotional materials to illustrate real-world benefits and encourage adoption.

Timing: from 01/05/2023.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural researchers, farmers who have implemented alternative fertilisers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

The desired result is to increase awareness among farmers, agricultural businesses, and policy makers about the latest research and technical advancements in alternative fertilisers. By raising awareness, the aim is to foster a more informed and receptive audience that understands the benefits and potential of these innovations, ultimately leading to greater adoption and support for sustainable agricultural practices.

- Action 3.2: **Find examples of studies showing differences between traditional fertilisers and alternative options.**

- a) Step 3.2.1: compile summaries of the most relevant studies, highlighting key findings and differences in performance, environmental impact, and cost-effectiveness. Collect and summarise the most pertinent studies that compare traditional fertilisers and alternative options, focusing on key findings related to performance, environmental impact, and cost-effectiveness. This step ensures that the gathered data are accessible and easily understandable.

Timing: from 01/02/2025. 3-4 months to gather and summarise relevant studies.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural researchers, academic institutions, policy analysts.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- b) Step 3.2.2: engage in discussions to gain insights and access to studies. Networking with researchers and experts in the field can provide valuable perspectives and uncover new research opportunities.

Timing: from 01/11/2024. Ongoing, with key engagements planned over a period of 6-12 months.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural researchers, industry experts, academic institutions, conference organisers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- c) Step 3.2.3: synthesise the gathered information into a comprehensive overview that highlights key differences and benefits of alternative fertilisers compared to traditional ones. Synthesise the collected data into a comprehensive overview that clearly highlights the differences and benefits of alternative fertilisers compared to traditional ones. This overview will be used to inform policy decisions, educate farmers, and support advocacy efforts.

Timing: from 01/01/2025. 2-3 months to synthesise data and produce the final comprehensive overview.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural researchers, communication specialists.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

The desired result is to gather a comprehensive collection of studies that clearly illustrate the differences in effectiveness, environmental impact, and economic benefits between traditional fertilisers and alternative options. This evidence will support advocacy efforts, inform policy decisions, and guide farmers in making informed choices about adopting alternative fertilisation methods.

Priority area 4: New business models.

- Action 4.1: **Conduct comprehensive market research to understand the current fertilising product landscape, identify potential competitors, and gauge market demand in Croatia.**

- d) Step 4.1.1: access market databases and online resources to gather existing data on market size, growth rates, and trends. Utilise market databases and online resources to collect existing data on the market size, growth rates, and trends of fertilising products in Croatia. This step aims to build a foundational understanding of the market landscape and identify key metrics.

Timing: from 01/03/2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, market researchers, data analysts, agricultural economists.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- e) Step 4.1.2: design and distribute surveys to farmers, agricultural suppliers, and distributors to gather firsthand information on fertiliser usage, preferences, and purchasing behaviour. Develop and disseminate surveys to farmers, agricultural suppliers, and distributors to gather firsthand information on fertiliser usage, preferences, and purchasing behaviour. This step provides valuable insights directly from key market participants.

Timing: from 01/01/2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, survey designers, farmers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- f) Step 4.1.3: create a comprehensive a list of major fertiliser suppliers and manufacturers operating in Croatia, including both local and international companies. This step identifies key players in the market and helps in understanding the competitive landscape.

Timing: from 01/03/2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, market analysts, business researchers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

The desired result is to obtain a thorough understanding of the fertilising product landscape in Croatia, including current market offerings, key competitors, and market demand trends. This research will provide critical insights to inform strategic decisions, identify opportunities for the introduction and promotion of alternative fertilisers, and develop targeted marketing and outreach efforts.

- Action 4.2: **Develop and implement awareness campaigns to educate farmers and agricultural businesses about the benefits of alternative fertilising products.**

- a) Step 4.2.1: develop brochures, fact sheets, infographics, and videos explaining how alternative fertilisers work, their benefits, and how to use them. These materials will serve as essential resources for educating farmers and agricultural businesses.

Timing: from 01/05/2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural experts, graphic designers, content creators, marketing teams.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- b) Step 4.2.2: collect and present case studies and testimonials from farmers who have successfully used alternative fertilisers. Gather case studies and testimonials from farmers who have successfully used alternative fertilisers, highlighting their positive experiences and the benefits they have observed. Present these success stories in various formats to build credibility and inspire others to adopt similar practices.

Timing: from 01/02/2025. 3-4 months to collect, document, and present case studies and testimonials.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, communication specialists, successful farmers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- c) Step 4.2.3: use social media platforms to share educational content, success stories, and interactive posts to engage with the farming community. Utilise social media platforms to share educational content, success stories, and interactive posts aimed at engaging with the farming community. This step leverages the wide reach and interactive nature of social media to foster greater awareness and support for alternative fertilisers.

Timing: from 01/11/2022.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, social media managers, content creators, community engagement specialists.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT, internally.

Expected output:

The desired result is to increase awareness and understanding among farmers and agricultural businesses about the benefits of alternative fertilising products. By educating these key stakeholders, the campaign aims to encourage the adoption of sustainable fertilisation practices, leading to improved soil health, reduced environmental impact, and potentially enhanced crop yields.

Priority area 5: Financial incentives.

- Action 5.1: **Explore opportunities for financial assistance from EU agricultural funds or other international organisations focused on sustainable agriculture.**

- a) Step 5.1.1: participate in informational sessions, workshops, and webinars organised by funding bodies to gain insights into available financial assistance programs, application processes, and eligibility criteria. This participation will help build a thorough understanding of funding opportunities and enhance the quality of applications.

Timing: from 01/05/2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural experts, representatives from funding bodies.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- b) Step 5.1.2: establish and maintain relationships with key contacts. Build and sustain relationships with key contacts in funding organisations, including program officers and grant managers. Regular communication and relationship-building will provide ongoing support, advice, and potential opportunities for future funding.

Timing: from 01/05/2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural experts, funding body representatives.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT, internally.

- c) Step 5.1.3: publicise the successful acquisition of funding and the progress of the funded project to build credibility and attract future funding opportunities through press releases, social media updates, and reports. Highlighting these successes builds credibility, showcases the impact of the initiatives, and attracts additional funding opportunities.

Timing: from 01/01/2023.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, communication specialists, marketing team.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

The desired result is to secure financial assistance from EU agricultural funds or other international organisations to support the adoption of alternative fertilisers. By obtaining this funding, the aim is to provide financial incentives and resources to farmers, reducing the economic barriers to transitioning to more sustainable fertilisation practices and enhancing overall agricultural sustainability in Croatia.

Priority area 6: Self-sufficiency.

- Action 6.1: **Promote the use of alternative fertilisers.**

- a) Step 6.1.1: develop and disseminate materials (brochures, videos, and infographics) that explain and emphasise the benefits of alternative fertilisers for self-sufficiency, including improved soil health, reduced dependency on imports, and cost savings. These materials will be targeted at farmers and agricultural businesses to encourage the transition to alternative fertilisers.

Timing: from 01/07/2023.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural experts, content creators, marketing team, local agricultural associations.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- b) Step 6.1.2: ensure all educational materials are available in the local language(s) to maximise accessibility and understanding. Translate all educational materials into local languages to ensure maximum accessibility and understanding among the target audience. This step will help overcome language barriers and ensure that the information reaches and resonates with a broader audience.

Timing: from 01/07/2023.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, content creators, local agricultural associations, communication specialists.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT, internally.

- c) Step 6.1.3: use social media platforms to share success stories, educational content, and interactive posts about the benefits of alternative fertilisers and self-sufficiency. This approach will engage the farming community, spread awareness, and foster a supportive online network.

Timing: from 01/11/2022.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, social media creators, content creators, agricultural experts, community engagement specialists.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT, internally.

Expected output:

The desired result is to significantly increase the adoption of alternative fertilisers among farmers and agricultural businesses, thereby enhancing soil health, reducing environmental impact, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices. By effectively promoting alternative fertilisers, the aim is to create a shift towards more eco-friendly farming methods and reduce dependency on traditional chemical fertilisers.

Priority area 7: Public acceptance.

- Action 7.1: **Public awareness campaigns.**

- a) Step 7.1.1: organise field days where farmers and the public can visit demonstration sites, observe the results of using alternative fertilisers, and interact with agricultural experts. These events will provide first-hand experience and foster direct engagement, helping to build trust and interest in alternative fertilisation methods.

Timing: from 01/11/2024. 3-4 months to plan and execute, with events scheduled regularly throughout the year.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural experts, local farmers, community organisers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- b) Step 7.1.2: conduct workshops and training sessions for farmers to educate them on the proper use, benefits, and potential challenges of alternative fertilisers. These sessions will provide practical knowledge and support, empowering farmers to make informed decisions and successfully implement alternative fertilisers on their farms.

Timing: from 01/10/2024. 2-3 months for initial planning and organisation, followed by ongoing sessions throughout.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural trainers, extension officers, local agricultural associations, farmers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

- c) Step 7.1.3: launch targeted social media campaigns to engage with younger farmers and the broader community. These campaigns will use platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter to share educational content, success stories, and interactive posts, promoting the benefits and proper use of alternative fertilisers.

Timing: from 01/05/2023.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, content creators, farmers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT, internally.

Expected output:

The desired result is to raise public awareness about the environmental and economic benefits of alternative fertilisers, fostering a community-wide shift towards sustainable agricultural practices. Through these campaigns, the aim is to educate the general public, farmers, and policymakers, leading to increased acceptance and adoption of alternative fertilisers.

Priority area 8: Environmental protection.

- Action 8.1: **Raise public awareness.**

- a) Step 8.1.1: use platforms like Facebook, LinkedIn and YouTube to share educational content, success stories, and calls to action related to environmental protection and the use of alternative fertilisers. These platforms will help reach a broad audience and engage the community in meaningful dialogue and action.

Timing: from 01/10/2022.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, content creators, agricultural experts, community engagement specialists.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT, internally.

- b) Step 8.1.2: ensure that all educational content is relevant to local environmental challenges and is available in the local language. This will make the information more accessible and relatable to the target audience, increasing its impact and effectiveness.

Timing: from 01/10/2022.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, local environmental experts, agricultural experts, content creators.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT, internally.

- c) Step 8.1.3: share success stories, impact reports, and case studies with the community and stakeholders to highlight progress and encourage continued involvement. Collect and share success stories, impact reports, and case studies with the community and stakeholders to highlight the positive progress made through the use of alternative fertilisers. This will encourage continued involvement and demonstrate the tangible benefits of environmentally friendly practices.

Timing: from 01/01/2023. 2-3 months to gather and compile stories and reports, followed by regular updates and sharing.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Ana-Marija Špicnagel, IPS Konzalting, agricultural experts, farmers, communication specialists.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT, internally.

Expected output:

The desired result is to increase public awareness about the importance of environmental protection and the role of alternative fertilisers in reducing environmental impact. By educating the public, the aim is to foster a community-wide commitment to sustainable agricultural practices that protect natural resources and promote long-term environmental health.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the action planning process has outlined a comprehensive strategy to promote the adoption of alternative fertilisers in Croatia through education, collaboration, and targeted campaigns. By engaging key stakeholders, leveraging local and international knowledge, and highlighting the environmental and economic benefits, the aim is to foster sustainable agricultural practices across the country. The next steps involve executing the outlined actions, monitoring progress, and continuously refining strategies to ensure widespread acceptance and effective implementation of alternative fertilisers.

4.3. Finland – South-West Finland

4.3.1. Methodology

Main challenges in the region are to reduce nutrient losses, especially phosphorus (P) to the Baltic Sea, mainly originating from the agricultural activities. Typical soil texture in southwest Finland is clay, prone for erosion. Minimising P losses through erosion is the main pathway for reducing P losses. At the same time, regions with high animal density, manure-based nutrients cannot be efficiently utilised, but could be used as alternative fertilisers to replace mineral fertilisers if properly processed.

The main collaborators for enhancing the use of alternative fertilisers are farmers and authorities, both at the local and national level. Co-operation exists through knowledge exchange and through national and local projects. When implementing Fertilising Products Regulation (2019/1009) into national legislation, researcher from Luke have provided their knowledge. Furthermore, close collaboration exists for providing knowledge about location, processing, efficiency and safety regarding the producing and using alternative fertilisers.

4.3.2. Regional Action Plan

The RSAP is structured, as already explained, in the 8 common priority areas identified in the GAP.

Priority area 1: Legal Framework.

- Action 1.1: **Uptake of nutrient recycling subsidy for enhancing the use of manure-based nutrients.**

This will enhance the use of manure-based nutrients by improving the nutrient ratios of the alternative fertilisers with mineral nutrients.

- a) Step 1.1.1: mapping of nutrient sources in the region for producing the alternative fertilisers.

- b) Step 1.1.2: producing tailor made alternative fertilisers according to regional crop requirement.
- c) Step 1.1.3: demonstrating the use of alternative fertilisers and showcasing their efficiency for the whole value chain.

Timing: from 2025.

Status: in process.

Responsible: policy makers, farmers union and farmers.

Possible funding sources: H2020 and HORIZON EU projects.

Expected output:

Production of nutrient-rich side-streams is demonstrated by using the Biomass Atlas (Spatial distribution of biomasses), followed by demonstrating the produced alternative fertilisers at a field scale (HE projects). Both policy makers, farmers union and farmers are involved. Project proposal under evaluation, and will start in 2025 if granted (4-years project).

Priority area 2: Political willingness.

- Action 2.1: **Demonstrating environmental benefits when substituting mineral fertilisers with alternative ones.**

Substituting mineral fertilisers with alternative ones will reduce the overall use of nutrients and will lead to reduced P content in soils, and thus potential P losses will be reduced.

- a) Step 2.1.1: collaboration with policy makers to provide information about soil P status in agricultural fields and consequence for P losses.
- b) Step 2.1.2: demonstrate agronomic efficiency of alternative fertilisers.
- c) Step 2.1.3: disseminate results of alternative fertilisers for different stakeholders.

Timing: 2024-2025.

Status: in process.

Responsible: researchers (mainly LUKE).

Possible funding sources: national funding schemes, H2020 and HORIZON EU projects.

Expected output:

Soil phosphorus status is evaluated to demonstrate P fertilisation requirement and agronomic efficiency of alternative fertilisers is demonstrated. These results are available from the previous projects (e.g. LEX4BIO, H2020) and will be disseminated at large during 2024-2025.

Priority area 3: Research and technical development.

- Action 3.1: **Supplementing alternative fertilisers with additional nutrients to improve nutrient ratios.**

Improving the nutrient ratios in alternative fertilisers will increase interest towards alternative fertilisers. Currently N/P-ratio is too low, and is not allowed to use in areas with high soil P status.

- a) Step 3.1.1: evaluating the right NP-ratio for fields with varying P status.
- b) Step 3.1.2: improving N/P ratio with fertiliser companies to meet crop demand and minimise nutrient losses.
- c) Step 3.1.3: demonstrate efficiency of new tailor-made fertilisers for farmers and policy makers.

Timing: 2025-2028.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: fertiliser companies, policy makers, researchers.

Possible funding sources: national funding schemes and HORIZON EU projects.

Expected output:

Evaluating soil nutrient data in a given region and workshop arranged with companies producing alternative fertilisers about actions needed to produce products with site-specific nutrient ratios (mainly N/P). Produced fertilisers will be tested at a field scale. If current HE-proposal is granted, research will start in 2025.

Priority area 4: New business models.

- Action 4.1: **Turning nutrient-rich side-streams into a valuable alternative fertiliser.**

Improving the quality of alternative fertilisers will increase their use among farmers. This will increase local business opportunities.

- a) Step 4.1.1: increasing awareness of alternative fertilisers and their potential in replacing mineral fertilisers.
- b) Step 4.1.2: creating a system for supporting production of alternative fertilisers.
- c) Step 4.1.3: increased production capacity will secure availability of alternative fertilisers.

Timing: 2025-2030.

Status: in process.

Responsible: fertiliser companies, policy makers, researchers.

Possible funding sources: national funding schemes and HORIZON EU projects.

Expected output:

Awareness campaign of the potential of alternative fertilisers, followed by evaluation of potential support system for enhancing production of alternative fertilisers. Both farmers, fertiliser industry and policy makers will be involved. Execution will take place during the next five years.

Priority area 5: Financial incentives.

- Action 5.1: **Economic incentives for reducing logistics of using alternative fertilisers.**

Larger application rates of alternative fertilisers compared to mineral fertilisers requires special equipment for spreading fertilisers. Incentives will enhance the use of alternative fertilisers.

- a) Step 5.1.1: evaluating the barriers related to logistics for using alternative fertilisers.
- b) Step 5.1.2: workshops among farmers, fertiliser producer and policy makers about actions needed to reduce logistics costs.
- c) Step 5.1.3: roadmap developed for the increased uptake of alternative fertilisers.

Timing: starting in 2025.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: fertiliser producers, farmers, researchers, policy makers.

Possible funding sources: national funding schemes.

Expected output:

Workshops will be arranged to determine the bottlenecks for using alternative fertilisers. All relevant stakeholders will be invited, and roadmap developed to reach the target for increasing utilisation of alternative fertilisers.

Priority area 6: Self-sufficiency.

- Action 6.1: **Enhanced replacement of mineral fertilisers with alternative ones.**

Currently, nutrient-rich side-streams are still considered as waste. After increasing knowledge about alternative fertilisers, their uptake and acceptance will increase and reduce the need of imported mineral fertilisers.

- a) Step 6.1.1: collecting farmer's opinion about alternative fertilisers.
- b) Step 6.1.2: providing up-to-date information about potential of alternative fertilisers in workshops arranged for farmers.
- c) Step 6.1.3: reducing restrictions for using alternative fertilisers originating from manure.

Timing: 2025-2028.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: fertiliser producers, farmers, researchers, policy makers.

Possible funding sources: national funding schemes and HORIZON EU projects.

Expected output:

Allowing small amount of P applied in alternative fertilisers originating from manure increases the utilisation of these fertilisers in fields with high soil P status. Both farmers and policy makers are needed to accelerate this development and will take place during the next few years.

Priority area 7: Public acceptance.

- Action 7.1: **Increase awareness about the food safety when using alternative fertilisers.**

One of the main challenges is the unknown effect of potential pollutants in alternative fertilisers to food safety. Low content of organic contaminants in alternative fertilisers will increase acceptance of alternative fertilisers.

- e) Step 7.1.1: evaluate potential risks related to the use of alternative fertilisers.
- f) Step 7.1.2: collect information about the safety of alternative fertilisers when it comes to food safety and human health.
- g) Step 7.1.3: disseminate results to the public.

Timing: 2025 onwards.

Status: in process.

Responsible: researchers (mainly LUKE).

Possible funding sources: national funding schemes and HORIZON EU projects.

Expected output:

Results from LEX4BIO-project will be collected and presented to consumers, farmers, food processing industry, fertiliser industry and policy makers. Results will be available in national language within the next year.

Priority area 8: Environmental protection.

- Action 8.1: **Alternative fertilisers have a potential to reduce the use of mineral fertilisers.**

Also, alternative fertilisers reduce P (potentially N as well) losses more than mineral fertilisers.

- d) Step 8.1.1: current nutrient (N and P) losses and required reduction to reach good ecological status of the surface waters.
- e) Step 8.1.2: determining the reduction limit for N and P losses to meet the requirements.
- f) Step 8.1.3: demonstrating potential N and P losses after using alternative fertilisers versus mineral ones.

Timing: 2025 onwards.

Status: in process.

Responsible: researchers (mainly LUKE).

Possible funding sources: HORIZON EU projects.

Expected output:

HELCOM states the nutrient loss reduction limits for each country in the Baltic Sea region. Earlier studies have shown that alternative fertilisers have a potential to reduce P losses. In the submitted HE-proposal also N based alternative fertilisers will be tested to evaluate N losses after field application. If granted, results (for N losses) are available after four years.

Conclusion:

Most of the activities proposed are related to ongoing or upcoming EU funded projects, what makes highly probable the mentioned activities are fulfilled at least at medium term. LUKE will be key in the development of the sector, as they are part of most of the initiatives mentioned.

4.4. Ireland – East Ireland

4.4.1. Methodology

A core working group was established within TEAGASC between researchers, advisors and specialists working on the EU funded projects Novafert, Nutriknow and bbionets. The focus of the three projects is nutrient use efficiency and developing the bioeconomy through the use of alternative fertilisers in the agricultural and forestry sector in Ireland. To develop a regional specific action plan to further develop the area, key stakeholders within Ireland were identified together with TEAGASC researchers working on the three EU funded projects. Collaboration between projects was used as a tool to target a larger audience.

A face-to-face workshop covering key areas and questions regarding to Novafert and Bbionets was designed and held in April, 23rd, counting with 17 attendees. Once a final plan and agenda was set, an invitation was circulated to all contacts within the Novafert, Nutriknow and Bbionet sphere in Ireland. The stakeholders in attendance at the workshop included representatives from research, advisory, education, agriculture, organic and forestry specialist, farmers, private company owners in nutrient recycling and the environmental protection agency. A key stakeholder which was missing on the day was a representative from the department of agriculture which is important for the development of the political willingness within the area.

However, attendees present at the face-to-face workshop held in TEAGASC Johnstown castle covered key questions outlined to develop a region-specific action plan and brought key knowledge and expertise from different areas. All feedback and ideas were taken on board and was filtered and summarised into key action points and steps required to fulfil a region action plan to further encourage the use of alternative fertilisers and develop the local bioeconomy. The identified actions are outlined below.

Figure 7. 1st NOVAFERT participatory workshop organised in East Ireland

Figure 8. 1st NOVAFERT participatory workshop organised in East Ireland

4.4.2. Regional Action Plan

The RSAP is structured, as already explained, in the 8 common priority areas identified in the GAP.

Priority area 1: Legal Framework.

- Action 1.1: **National legislation complies with the European legislation on the use of alternative fertilisers.**
 - a) Step 1.1.1: mapping of key national and European legislation.
 - b) Step 1.1.2: legal harmonisation of the national and regional framework.
 - c) Step 1.1.3: coordination within national and regional administrations.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: to be confirmed.

Possible funding sources: link in with existing work being carried out within the area.

- Action 1.2: **Introduce carbon credit incentives for farmers.**
 - a) Step 1.2.1: provide scientific evidence for the benefits of using fertiliser with greater % carbon.
 - b) Step 1.2.2: coordination with national and regional administrations.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: TEAGASC.

Possible funding sources: link in with existing work being carried out within the area.

- Action 1.3: **Encourage livestock / tillage relationship / partnership for the exchange of nutrients between intensive livestock farms and stockless farms.**
 - a) Step 1.3.1: make stockless farms aware of the benefits of using manures from animals as part of their nutrient management plan and reducing reliance on chemical fertiliser.
 - b) Step 1.3.2: advisory services need to be made aware of encouraging correct nutrient management planning in advance of growing seasons to be able account for the use of organic manures without breaching their farm phosphorus allowance.
 - c) Step 1.3.3: start to connect intensive livestock farmers with stockless farmers using advisory services/ discussion groups etc.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: TEAGASC, farmers, researchers and advisory services.

Possible funding sources: link in with existing work being carried out within the area.

Expected output:

This very practical but important measure can be implemented throughout Ireland to get a more balanced distribution of nutrients onto land to alleviate nutrient hotspots and lower the risk of environmental loss. Stakeholders involved include farmers, researchers and advisory services. TEAGASC is the main leader and continuously offers advice on best practice on nutrient efficiency and dealing with organic manure on an annual basis.

Priority area 2: Political willingness.

- Action 2.1: **Public awareness and education campaigns.**

- a) Step 2.1.1: educate farmers and the public about the environmental and economic benefits of bio-based fertiliser through demonstration farms, workshops, seminars and media campaigns.
- b) Step 2.1.2: use demonstration farms, workshops, seminars and media campaigns to educate consumers and farmers through networks on the EU funded projects NOVAFERT, Nutriknow and Bbionets.
- c) Step 2.1.3: seek Government funding to provide training and technical assistance to farmers to help educate them on the topic.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: TEAGASC, researchers, advisors, consumers and farmers.

Possible funding sources: existing funding through EU funded bioeconomy projects.

Expected output:

The focus with this action is to put more emphasis on educating consumers on actions being implemented on farms to reduce reliance on chemical inputs for food production. Farmers also need education regarding best use of bio-based fertiliser. This action needs political willingness to provide funding for projects to be able carry out this action. Researchers, advisors, consumers and farmers are the main stakeholders involved in this action and will run over the duration of the next 20 months led by TEAGASC.

Priority area 3: Research and technical development.

- Action 3.1: **Provide scientific research for displacing chemical fertilisers with alternative fertilisers for crop production.**

Provide scientific research for displacing as much chemical fertilisers as possible with alternative fertilisers for crop production without affecting yield or quality.

- a) Step 3.1.1: continue to seek funding to run field experiments testing different types of alternative fertilisers.
- b) Step 3.1.2: TEAGASC will continue to run field experiments testing different types of alternative fertilisers linking up with findings from other research institutes.
- c) Step 3.1.3: provide relevant information for advisors and teachers to include within their education programmes to educate young farmers in agricultural college.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: TEAGASC, researchers, advisors, teachers, students and farmers.

Possible funding sources: Horizon EU funded projects and national funding.

Expected output:

One of the challenges regarding to the adaption of bio-based fertilisers is the lack of long-term research. Teagasc intend on continuing their long-term bio-based living lab trial in Johnstown castle to continuously support stakeholders on best use of integrating bio-based fertilisers into nutrient management planning Stakeholders involved include researchers, advisors, teachers, students and farmers.

- Action 3.2: **Support mechanisms to encourage local production of alternative fertilisers.**
 - a) Step 3.2.1: harmonisation of local and national grant aid to support technological development for refining nutrients.

Timing: 2024.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: to be confirmed.

Possible funding sources: Horizon EU funded projects and national funding.

- Action 3.3: **Provide more information for advisory and extension services that farmers avail of regarding to the bioeconomy.**
 - a) Step 3.1.1: provide relevant information for advisors and teachers to include within their education programmes.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: TEAGASC.

Possible funding sources: Horizon EU funded projects and national funding.

Priority area 4: New business models.

- Action 4.1: **Collaboration between research and companies.**
 - a) Step 4.1.1: build relationships.
 - b) Step 4.1.2: create collaborative agreements.
 - c) Step 4.1.3: secure funding through project funding, government agencies, industry sponsors, etc.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: TEAGASC, ENVA, researchers, company owners.

Possible funding sources: project funding, government, private companies.

Expected output:

Stakeholders involved include researchers and company owners which are interested in a startup business models. TEAGASC is being available to support small start-up businesses in the area of nutrient recycling. This service is available on an on-going basis.

Priority area 5: Financial incentives.

- Action 5.1: **Government provides economic incentives to farmers that use alternative fertilisers.**
 - a) Step 5.1.1: developing awareness campaigns to promote alternative fertilisers, contributing to the EU strategy “Farm to Fork” at the local and regional levels.
 - b) Step 5.1.2: creating a set of national, regional, and/or local taxes bonification / exemptions.
 - c) Step 5.1.3: developing preferential financing options for alternative fertiliser infrastructure.

Timing: from 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: government representatives, citizens, researchers, farmers and private companies.

Possible funding sources: N/A.

Expected output:

Steps will be taken by promoting the use of alternative fertilisers through the NOVAFERT lighthouse demonstration farms and by participating on the topic in seminars, workshops, etc. within NOVAFERT and other relevant funded projects. There is no specific timeframe for execution, as it will be a longer term consultation process with government agencies. Stakeholders involved include government representatives, citizens, researchers, farmers and private companies.

Priority area 6: Self-sufficiency.

- Action 6.1: **Provide new research, support and innovative tools that farmers can adapt on farm to make best use of nutrients already available to them on farm.**
 - a) Step 6.1.1: provide scientific and technical information to advisors and farmers regarding the benefits of adapting tools such as crop rotation, cover cropping, crop residue management, green manure, composting, animal integration and soil testing. A set of combined management practices as mentioned would help a typical livestock and tillage farms in Ireland to become more self-sufficient regarding nutrient use on farm lowering the need to import fertiliser onto farm.
 - b) Step 6.1.2: providing up to date technical advice on the best use and management of animal manures from storage to application methods is a key focus within TEAGASC nutrient efficiency research. Animal manure is a significant nutrient source in Ireland.

- c) Step 6.1.3: continuously researching and updating farmers on the nutrient availability of different bio-based products. This is important research and information for farmers to be able to offset the need to import chemical fertiliser to crop demand.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: TEAGASC, research, education, advisory service, farmers.

Possible funding sources: existing resources available through a range of funded projects.

Expected output:

The overarching action is to be able to support farmers on how to use nutrients that are already available to them as efficiently as possible before turning to importing fertiliser to meet their nutrient requirement. The main stakeholders involved in this action is TEAGASC research, education and advisory service along with the target audience of which is farmers.

Priority area 7: Public acceptance.

- Action 7.1: **Raise awareness of the benefits of using alternative fertiliser to the public through the use of demonstration farms and videos / success stories.**
 - a) Step 7.1.1: establish lighthouse demonstration farms that are using alternative fertilisers to a high standard through the work of the NOVAFERT project. Lighthouse demonstration farms act as a knowledge transfer hub for key stakeholders and provide an opportunity for peer-to-peer learning between farmers increasing the adaption of such technologies.
 - b) Step 7.1.2: organise frequent stakeholder group visits to the lighthouse demonstration farms including open invitation to the public.
 - c) Step 7.1.3: provide relevant information regarding the benefits of the system in an agricultural context and receive feedback and questions from other farmers, consumers, general public, etc.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: TEAGASC, researchers, advisors, farmers, citizens and private industry.

Possible funding sources: EU funding through the NOVAFERT project.

Expected output:

The work of the lighthouse demos within the NOVAFERT project has a huge role to play when it comes to public acceptance. In Ireland, TEAGASC is supporting the lighthouse demo farm and facilitating frequent group visits to educate not only farmers, but also the public on the use of alternative fertilisers. This action will also allow the opportunity to receive feedback and questions from a broad stakeholder group regarding the benefits and challenges of displacing synthetic fertilisers with alternative sources of nutrients. Stakeholders include researchers, advisors, farmers, citizens and private industry.

- Action 7.2: **Public awareness campaign.**

- a) Step 7.2.1: launch educational campaigns to raise awareness about the benefits of alternative fertilisers, including environmental advantages. This can be achieved by utilising social media channels, workshops and community events.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: TEAGASC and other interested state and private bodies to be confirmed.

Possible funding sources: resources that are already available.

- Action 7.3: **Case studies/success stories.**

- a) Step 7.3.1: share success stories or case studies of farmers reducing their reliance on chemical fertilisers and replacing them with alternative sources of fertiliser to the public. This can be inspiring for peers to adapt similar practices and to help educate the public on what farmers are doing to reduce reliance on chemical inputs for food production.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: TEAGASC.

Possible funding sources: EU funding through the NOVAFERT project.

Priority area 8: Environmental protection.

- Action 8.1: **Promote the benefits that alternative fertilisers have on soil health.**

- a) Step 8.1.1: continue to carry out field measurements regarding the impact alternative fertilisers have on soil health.
- b) Step 8.1.2: groups visiting the Irish lighthouse demo. The importance of improving and maintaining soil health will be one of the highlights on the agenda for groups visiting the Irish lighthouse demo and how alternative fertilisers can have a significant positive impact on soil biota.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: TEAGASC.

Possible funding sources: EU funding through the NOVAFERT project.

Expected output:

Alternative fertilisers usually contain more carbon, which feed soil biota and improves the overall health status of the soil helping to protect our natural resource and prevent soil erosion / nutrient loss into our waterways.

- Action 8.2: **Use fertiliser at the right time, rate and place.**

- a) Step 8.2.1: provide scientific research to advisors, lecturers etc. regarding to best practices for applying nutrients to land to minimise chance of nutrient loss to the environment.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: TEAGASC.

Possible funding sources: internal funding through a range of funded projects.

- Action 8.3: **Enhanced soil health.**

- a) Step 8.3.1: provide up to date scientific research to all relevant stakeholders regarding the positive benefit that bio-based fertilisers have in relation to soil health. Bio-based fertilisers usually contain more carbon which feeds the soil biota and improves the overall health status of soil helping to protect our natural resource.

Timing: 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: TEAGASC.

Possible funding sources: internal funding through a range of funded projects.

Conclusion:

The regional action plan in Ireland is using relevant stakeholders and resources under the different subcategories to try best implement the actions and subsequent steps required to fulfil the action. The use of the lighthouse demonstration established within the NOVAFERT project is a key resource to facilitate actions required within the action plan to increase the adaption and understanding of alternative fertilisers.

4.5. Poland – South-East Poland

4.5.1. Methodology

The key partners and collaborators in Poland include a diverse range of stakeholders, following the Quadruple Helix Model of Innovation, which integrates science, policy, industry, and society. The identified partners and allies consist of:

- Polish Waterworks Chamber of Commerce (national public administration),
- GreenBack Ltd. (business – SME),
- Optimus Foundation (NGO),
- AGH University of Kraków (University),
- research centres.
- farmers (private sector),
- Herby Water Treatment Plant – Lisów Wastewater Treatment Plant,
- the group bringing together farmers,

- Municipal Water and Sewage Company in Rzeszów,
- Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development,
- Agricultural Advisory Centre in Brwinów,
- Grupa Azoty.
- Agricultural Advisory Centre in Boguchwała.

Collaboration with local authorities and organisations is conducted on topics related to alternative fertilisers and other relevant areas. Coordination mechanisms include regular meetings and workshops to ensure effective cooperation, though there is always room for improved communication and additional resources.

The expertise and resources are brought to the consortium. This includes research capabilities from institutions like the AGH University of Kraków and MEERI PAS, practical industry insights from partners such as GreenBack Ltd., Eko-tucz, Municipal Water and Sewage Company in Rzeszów, and Herby Water Treatment Plant – Lisów Wastewater Treatment Plant. Additionally, policy support is provided by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and the Agricultural Advisory Centre in Brwinów. Collaborative efforts are further strengthened by engaging a wide range of stakeholders from different sectors, including NGOs like the Optimus Foundation and industry leaders such as Grupa Azoty. This diverse involvement ensures comprehensive expertise and resources are available to address various aspects of the project.

The workplan includes organising meetings and workshops to facilitate collaboration. For example, the 1st online workshop titled "Fertilisers from Secondary Sources - Opportunities and Barriers" was held on December 11th, 2023, with 58 participants. This workshop is part of a larger engagement strategy that also includes in-person and online meetings, interviews and continuous communication among stakeholders. Additionally, meetings of the Regional Working Group have been held, and more such meetings are planned. The timeline and research steps are structured to ensure consistent progress and stakeholder involvement throughout the project.

Figure 9. Invitation to the 1st NOVAFERT participatory workshop organised in South-East Poland

Figure 10. 1st NOVAFERT participatory workshop organised in South-East Poland

To date, the 1st workshop titled "Fertilisers from Secondary Source - Opportunities and Barriers" have been organised on December 11th, 2023. This workshop focused on discussing the opportunities and barriers related to fertilisers from secondary sources (sewage sludge, animal manure and digestate).

The workshop began with a presentation on the NOVAFERT project, providing an overview of its objectives and scope. This was followed by a discussion on best practices for using fertilisers from secondary sources, with a specific focus on regional implementation. Additionally, an analysis of alternative sources of fertilisers was presented, highlighting potential benefits and challenges. The workshop concluded with a SWOT analysis of the use of fertilisers from secondary sources in Poland, summarising strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats followed by interactive discussions among participants. The workshop was well-received, indicating a high level of interest and engagement in the topic.

In addition, it is planned to organise two more workshops, additional Regional Working Group meetings, and visits from the lighthouse demo farmer group. These activities aim to further promote the use of alternative fertiliser products and demonstrate their benefits, ultimately fostering greater acceptance and adoption of sustainable agricultural practices.

Regional Action Plan

The RSAP is structured, as already explained, in the 8 common priority areas identified in the GAP.

Priority area 1: Legal Framework.

- Action 1.1: **Review and update regulations regarding alternative fertilisers (animal manure, digestate and sewage sludge).**
 - a) Step 1.1.1: mapping key national and European regulations.
 - b) Step 1.1.2: analysing the compliance of current regulations with EU requirements.
 - c) Step 1.1.3: collaborating with the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development to implement legal changes.

Timing: until the end of this project.

Status: in process.

Responsible: team MEERI PAS, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and local authorities.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

Harmonising national legal regulations with EU standards for alternative fertilisers will ensure regulatory compliance and facilitate the implementation of innovative solutions. Key stakeholders include the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and local authorities. These actions will be carried out until the end of the project.

Priority area 2: Political willingness.

- Action 2.1: **Increase the engagement of local and regional authorities in seeking solutions to replace mineral fertilisers.**
 - a) Step 2.1.1: organising meetings with Regional Working Group.
 - b) Step 2.1.2: promoting the environmental benefits of using alternative fertilisers.
 - c) Step 2.1.3: supporting legislative initiatives at the regional level.

Timing: until the end of this project.

Status: in process.

Responsible: team MEERI PAS, all RWG participants.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

Raising awareness and engagement of all target groups through information campaigns will help promote sustainable agricultural practices. Key stakeholders are all RWG participants. These campaigns will be conducted throughout the project period.

Priority area 3: Research and technical development.

- Action 3.1: **Support research on new technologies for converting waste into fertilisers..**
 - a) Step 3.1.1: identifying key research opportunities in the region.
 - b) Step 3.1.2: increasing funding for research and development of technologies.
 - c) Step 3.1.3: organising scientific conferences and workshops.

Timing: until the end of this project.

Status: in process.

Responsible: team MEERI PAS, scientific and industrial sectors.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

Research on new technologies for converting waste into fertilisers will enhance efficiency and innovation in agriculture. Research on new technologies for converting waste into fertilisers will enhance efficiency and innovation in agriculture. Poland has developed many innovative methods for waste processing and fertiliser production. These technologies have been included in the "Atlas of the EU Nutrient-Oriented Living Labs," a product of the NOVAFERT project. It is crucial to increase funding for research and development to ensure that these technologies can be thoroughly studied. Furthermore, it is essential to disseminate the results of initiatives aimed at promoting the use of alternative fertilisers through presentations at scientific conferences and the organisation of workshops. MEERI has presented activities carried out within the project at the following conferences:

- XI National Conference of Young Scientists on Doctoral Research Achievements – Grand Poster Session.
- 17th Conference on Methods of Disposal of Sewage Sludge.

- 4th International Conference on Strategies toward Green Deal Implementation: Water, Raw Materials & Energy.
- World Conference on Soil, Water, Energy, and Air (EUWCSWEA).
- 5th Symposium on Circular Economy and Sustainability.

Partners from both the scientific and industrial sectors will be key participants in these activities, which will continue until the project's completion.

Priority area 4: New business models.

- Action 4.1: **Promote the circular economy in the context of converting waste into fertilisers.**
 - a) Step 4.1.1: analyse the potential for transforming waste materials such as sewage sludge, animal manure and digestate into marketable fertilisers.
 - b) Step 4.1.2: promote circular economy frameworks that support waste-to-fertiliser processes.
 - c) Step 4.1.3: foster collaborations between organic farmers and alternative fertiliser producers.

Timing: until the end of this project.

Status: in process.

Responsible: team MEERI PAS.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

Promoting circular economy models enables the transformation of agricultural and industrial waste into valuable nutrient sources, contributing to sustainable farming and waste management.

Priority area 5: Financial incentives.

- Action 5.1: **Implement economic support systems for farmers using alternative fertilisers.**
 - a) Step 5.1.1: analysing available funding sources and support opportunities.
 - b) Step 5.1.2: developing grant and tax relief programs.
 - c) Step 5.1.3: promoting available forms of support among farmers.

Timing: until the end of this project.

Status: in process.

Responsible: team MEERI PAS, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and local authorities.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

Providing economic support through grants and tax relief will encourage farmers to use alternative fertilisers. Key stakeholders are the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and local authorities.

Priority area 6: Self-sufficiency.

- Action 6.1: **Reduce dependence on mineral fertiliser imports by using alternative fertilisers.**
 - a) Step 6.1.1: analysing the potential of local raw material sources.
 - b) Step 6.1.2: supporting local fertiliser producers.
 - c) Step 6.1.3: promoting self-sufficiency among farmers.

Timing: until the end of this project.

Status: in process.

Responsible: team MEERI PAS, local producers and farmers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

Supporting local producers and promoting self-sufficiency will help reduce dependence on mineral fertiliser imports. Key stakeholders are local producers and farmers. These actions will be carried out until the end of the project.

Priority area 7: Public acceptance.

- Action 7.1: **Increase public awareness of the benefits of using alternative fertilisers.**
 - a) Step 7.1.1: organising educational campaigns.
 - b) Step 7.1.2: collaborating with environmental organisations.
 - c) Step 7.1.3: promoting success stories of farmers using alternative fertilisers.

Timing: until the end of this project.

Status: in process.

Responsible: team MEERI PAS, local producers and farmers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

Public education and promoting the success of farmers using alternative fertilisers will enhance social acceptance. Working on social media is key. MEERI promotes all activities carried out within the project on its social media accounts (LinkedIn, Facebook, X). These actions will be carried out until the end of the project.

- Action 7.2: **Inform stakeholders (especially farmers) about alternative fertiliser products made from sewage sludge, animal manure and digestate.**
 - a) Step 7.2.1: organise workshops to promote alternative fertilisers.
 - b) Step 7.2.2: engage farmers in promotional activities for lighthouse initiatives.

- c) Step 7.2.3: present examples of alternative fertiliser products and their positive environmental impacts to farmers,
- d) Step 7.2.4: Utilise various communication channels to disseminate information.

Timing: until the end of this project.

Status: in process.

Responsible: team MEERI PAS, lighthouse demo (Rzeszów Municipal Water and Sewerage Company, MPWiK), agricultural extension services (Boguchwała Agricultural Advisory Centre) and local farming communities.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

Plan and conduct workshops where experts can present information about alternative fertilisers, including their benefits and usage. Provide hands-on demonstrations and Q&A sessions.

Involve farmers in initiatives that demonstrate the successful use of alternative fertilisers. This includes lighthouse visits, where farmers can observe and learn from these examples. Key stakeholders: lighthouse demo (Municipal Water and Sewerage Company - MPWiK in Rzeszów - Poland), agricultural extension services (Agricultural Advisory Centre in Boguchwała - Poland) and local farming communities. Moreover, leverage social media, newsletters and local agricultural fairs to reach a wider audience of farmers.

Priority area 8: Environmental protection.

- Action 8.1: **Support environmental protection efforts through the use of alternative fertilisers.**

- a) Step 8.1.1: identifying environmental benefits.
- b) Step 8.1.2: promoting narratives on mitigating climate change.
- c) Step 8.1.3: collaborating with environmental protection institutions.

Timing: until the end of this project.

Status: in process.

Responsible: team MEERI PAS, Rzeszów Municipal Water and Sewerage Company (MPWiK) Boguchwała Podkarpackie Agricultural Advisory Centre (PODR), environmental protection institutions and farmers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

Promoting the environmental benefits of using alternative fertilisers will help combat climate change. Key participants will be environmental protection institutions and farmers. MEERI PAS initiated such activities in cooperation with the Municipal Water and Sewerage Company (MPWiK) in Rzeszów and the Podkarpackie Agricultural Advisory Centre (PODR) in Boguchwała. These actions will be carried out until the end of the project.

- Action 8.2: **Promotion of best practices for the sustainable use of alternative fertilisers from animal manure, sewage sludge and digestate.**

- a) Step 8.2.1: organising workshops for farmers on sustainable application methods.
- b) Step 8.2.2: collaborating with agricultural advisors to provide on-site support and consultations for farmers

Timing: until the end of this project.

Status: in process.

Responsible: team MEERI PAS, research institutions, agricultural advisors and farmers.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

Key stakeholders include research institutions, agricultural advisors and farmers. These actions were undertaken as part of the participatory workshops and will continue until the end of the project.

- Action 8.3: **Publish scientific research on the use of alternative fertilisers.**

- c) Step 8.3.1: identify key research areas related to alternative fertilisers, focusing on animal manure, digestate and sewage sludge.
- d) Step 8.3.2: prepare detailed research papers based on the findings and submit them to high-impact scientific journals.
- e) Step 8.1.3: disseminate published research through academic conferences, workshops, and other relevant platforms.

Timing: until the end of this project.

Status: in process.

Responsible: team MEERI PAS.

Possible funding sources: NOVAFERT.

Expected output:

Present the research findings at national and international conferences and workshops to share knowledge and promote the adoption of alternative fertilisers.

MEERI is currently preparing a scientific paper based on the data collected during the participatory workshop and the Regional Working Group meetings. Further activities and scientific publications are planned in this area. These actions will be carried out until the end of the project.

Conclusion:

The Action Plan for South-East Poland aims to accelerate the implementation of alternative fertilisers from secondary sources such as animal manure, digestate, and sewage sludge. This will be achieved through reviewing and updating regulations, increasing local authorities' engagement, supporting research, developing new business models, introducing economic support systems, promoting self-sufficiency, enhancing social acceptance, and

protecting the environment. The subsequent steps involve further activities to implement the planned actions.

At short term (August 2024), it is planned to organise participatory workshops aimed at promoting good agricultural practices, educating the key target group—farmers—and gathering valuable feedback. Furthermore, the dissemination of project results is planned during the 5th International Conference Strategies toward Green Deal Implementation: Water, Raw Materials & Energy in Green Transition, scheduled for November 27th-29th, 2024, in a hybrid format (online and in-person in Kraków, Poland). Moreover, an article about the SWOT analysis will be published this year, with the goals of promoting environmental protection, disseminating project results, and educating/informing target groups.

4.6. Spain – Andalusia

4.6.1. Methodology

The regional action plan has been prepared thanks to the support of relevant stakeholders of the region already engaged in the promotion and implementation of alternative fertilisers, as they have worked or are currently working with BIOAZUL in other EU initiatives like [P2GreenN](#), [Water2REturn](#), [SuWaNu Europe](#) and [RichWater](#), as well as regional initiatives, like [Axarquía Sostenible](#). Thanks to the work on these projects, BIOAZUL has created a relevant network during these last years.

All these actions are focused the development of eco-innovative, circular and sustainable solutions for the treatment and reuse of water resources. In all cases the water resource is used, whether urban or industrial wastewater, process water, drainage water, etc., and through a range of processes framed in the circular economy model, different resources are obtained:

- The reclaimed water itself, which can be used for agricultural, industrial or urban use, thus being an important ally as a measure of adaptation to climate change and water scarcity, or discharged into the network with the required quality.
- A range of nutrients, which can be extracted to generate added-value products in the agricultural sector such as alternative fertilisers or biostimulants, or kept in the water for later fertigation, contributing at the same time to alleviating water scarcity and reducing the application of chemical fertilisers, which favours the decarbonisation of the economy and benefits the environment.

In this context, the different running initiatives try to join forces as much as possible and organise joint events to maximise their effect and get more visibility.

Some key partners take part in these initiatives, being some examples AXARAGUA, a public company operating water management in Axarquía region that represents the public sector and decision-making, and can offer its vision and experience on the field, AgriSmart Data, an SME developing intelligent fertigation tools for nutrient control and decision making, TROPS, an agricultural cooperative of more than 3,000 farmers in the region focused on the commercialisation tropical crops like mango and avocado (among many others), and CETAQUA, a research centre specialised in water management.

During the first regional working group meeting, held on May 24th 2023, the needs and challenges regarding nutrients recovery and use of reclaimed water as alternative biofertilisers were discussed already. This served as a basis, being the main findings:

Priority needs:

- Citizen awareness, promotion of good practices.
- Investments in infrastructure.
- Training in the use of digital tools for the entire public.
- Adaptation of European regulations, clear guidelines.

Priority challenges:

- Mediation with administrations (governance).
- Adaptation of water quality for its expected use.
- Efficient management of reclaimed water.
- Access to digital tools for all audiences.
- Irrigation/nutrient dosing.
- Cost reduction.

Using this information as a baseline, the first NOVAFERT participatory workshop was organised. It took place on June 20th, and it counted with 38 attendees. The workshop was organised in cooperation with P2Green project. The attendees worked on the elaboration of the regional action plan.

The workshop methodology was based on back-casting and design thinking to develop a joint vision. The back-casting process can be used in a wide variety of situations to develop a roadmap or path that links a desired future or vision to the present. Identifying and specifying the steps and actions necessary to turn that vision into a reality can help paint a clearer picture of how we can achieve this vision. This back-casting process was combined with the design thinking format, a work process that helps teams develop their creativity. It is based on a collaborative and creative approach that includes empathy, problem definition, idea generation, prototyping and experimentation.

Figure 11. 1st NOVAFERT participatory workshop organised in Andalusia region, Spain

Figure 12. 1st NOVAFERT participatory workshop organised in Andalusia region, Spain

4.6.2. Regional Action Plan

The RSAP is structured, as already explained, in the 8 common priority areas identified in the GAP.

Priority area 1: Legal Framework.

- Action 1.1: **Regularisation of irrigation communities, encouraging farmers to associate to have a more efficient and controlled water management.**
 - a) Step 1.1.1: creation of associations and federations of irrigators that contribute to regularising and updating water rights.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, farmers, associations, unions.

Possible funding sources: national and regional funding.

- Action 1.2: **Harmonisation of national and European legislation.**

The Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse is a common European legal framework for all member states with provisions to use reclaimed water in agriculture.

At national level, the basic regulations setting the administrative requirements to obtain the enabling title, as well as the permitted uses and required quality criteria, were included in Royal Decree 1620/2007 of 7 December 2007, and has been recently updated. Royal Decree-Law 4/2023, of 11 May 2023, adopts urgent measures in agricultural and water matters in response to the drought and the worsening of conditions in the primary sector, establishes the new legal framework of water reuse, adapting the Spanish legal regime for water reuse to the European regulation and establishing the appropriate framework to promote, in this context of scarcity, the obtaining of said alternative resources.

- a) Step 1.2.1: set goals to guarantee EU legislation compliance. It is necessary to identify the goals established in the European framework to analyse the actual application in the Andalusian context also considering the new national regulations.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2025.

Status: in process.

Responsible: farmers, associations, unions, industrial sector, research centres.

Possible funding sources: EU funded projects.

Priority area 2: Political willingness.

- Action 2.1: **Increase of specialised staff in public administration.**

Administrative procedures are too long and complicated, and although it is possible to generate reclaimed water in the region, it is not easy to get the enabling title to use it at short or even medium term.

- a) Step 2.1.1: increasing the budget devoted to hire administrative staff to speed up the processing and evaluation of applications and files.
- b) Step 2.1.2: promote training, as well as the need of a minimum target of specialised workers in the public administration in the framework of the National Hydrological Plan.
- c) Step 2.2.3: coordination among different public administrations and knowledge exchange.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Possible funding sources: national funds.

- Action 2.2: **Coordination between national and regional administrations.**

- a) Step 2.2.1: drive the coordination between national and regional administrations. Besides the differences between the National and Andalusian governments, there are other institutions managing water concessions like the water basin management authorities. Although the competencies over these management authorities belong to the National Government, coordination should be fostered among them to unify the criteria of water reuse in the regions where they coexist.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Possible funding sources: national funds.

- Action 2.3: **Foster a transparency portal.**

- a) Step 2.3.1: creation of a transparency portal to provide final consumers with information about the reclamation process, the water quality, and how the regulation is being complied. A public database is a proper tool to provide transparency and build public trust. The data base shall provide access to the quality standards achieved in the reclamation plants proving the completion with the legal requirements and building trust among consumers.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Possible funding sources: national funds.

Priority area 3: Research and technical development.

- Action 3.1: Facilitation of data interoperability.

- a) Step 3.1.1: determination and use of common criteria for data operability (“common language”). This includes the development of a data characterisation protocol and or a data interoperability protocol, as well as a data analysis tool.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, industrial sector, research centres.

Possible funding sources: EU, national and regional funding, private funding.

- Action 3.2: Improvement of the existing infrastructures.

- a) Step 3.2.1: investments to improve secondary and tertiary treatment plants. Tertiary infrastructures are fundamental in most of the reclaimed water facilities, as they are key to achieve the required parameters imposed by the EU Regulation for water reuse. However not all wastewater treatment plants have these infrastructures, thus investment is required as they should be modernised adapting their current infrastructures to the water reclamation process. The Public Administration should, therefore, check the existing wastewater treatment plants and decide which ones are more suitable to produce reclaimed water for agriculture. Then, they should invest in these facilities assuring that they include tertiary infrastructures, thus guaranteeing compliance with the current regulations.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2034.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: private sector, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Possible funding sources: national funding, private funding.

- Action 3.3: Accessibility of reclaimed water to irrigable areas.

- a) Step 3.3.1: assuring the connection between water reclamation facilities and irrigable areas. Sometimes, an investment for water reuse in a reclamation facility is completed but reclaimed water is still not available for irrigation as there are no pipes or a pumping system connecting the water from the reclamation facility to the irrigation

network. The building process should not finish in the construction of the water facility. The required infrastructures to connect the reclamation facilities with the irrigation networks should also be promoted by the public administration.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2034.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: private sector, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Possible funding sources: national funding, private funding.

- Action 3.4: **Need of reclaimed water storage infrastructures (irrigation pools).**

- a) Step 3.4.1: building reclaimed water storage infrastructures (irrigation pools). Although reclaimed water is produced throughout the year, its demand increases in the summer during the irrigation season. It is therefore important to have a great infrastructure of irrigation ponds to assure the availability of water when needed.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2034.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: private sector, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Possible funding sources: national funding, private funding.

Priority area 4: New business models.

- Action 4.1: **Creation of user associations that allow reducing the costs and scaling sensing technology.**

- a) Step 4.1.1: use of digital twin technology, which allows recommendations on efficient water use to be extrapolated to farms that do not have sensing technology, making possible reducing costs.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2028.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: private sector.

Possible funding sources: private funding.

Priority area 5: Financial incentives.

- Action 5.1: **Establishment of incentives for water saving.**

Water scarcity is a key issue in Andalusia, thus technologies focused on water regeneration and on efficient use of reclaimed water for fertigation are one of the main concerns of the sector.

- a) Step 5.1.1: establishment of tax deductions for those farmers who, through introducing sensing technology in their farms, demonstrate that they are using water efficiently.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Possible funding sources: national funding.

- Action 5.2: **Establishment of a joint venture capital fund – sector fund.**

Public funds are crucial, but private funds cannot be not considered.

- b) Step 5.2.1: characterisation of the sector, identifying the most influential producers.
- c) Step 5.2.2: preparation of a model framework as a baseline to start working.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2028.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: private sector.

Possible funding sources: private funding.

- Action 5.3: **Public administration provides economic incentives to farmers that use alternative fertilisers.**

- a) Step 5.3.1: developing awareness campaigns to promote alternative fertilisers, contributing to the EU strategy “Farm to Fork” at the local and regional levels.
- b) Step 5.3.2: creating a set of National, regional, and/or local taxes bonification/exemptions.
- c) Step 5.3.3: developing preferential financing options for alternative fertiliser infrastructure.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Possible funding sources: EU, national and regional funding.

Priority area 6: Self-sufficiency.

- Action 6.1: **Creation of an open digital platform at EU level to be continuously fed with onsite data.**

- a) Step 6.1.1: creation of public AI models for specific and tailored recommendations for each crop.

- b) Step 6.1.2: development of free mobile applications with public domain application for crop monitoring.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2028.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: private sector, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Possible funding sources: EU, national and regional funding, private funding.

- Action 6.2: **Updating the existing infrastructure.**

- a) Step 6.2.1: study on the existing vs. the needed infrastructures. This includes the study of population growth and associated needs. In addition, data collection will be necessary for an appropriated hydrological planning.
- b) Step 6.2.2: incorporation of renewable energies for production. This includes the evaluation of renewable energies that are adaptable to the environment, as well as the energy needs of the new infrastructures to be developed. Moreover, environmental feasibility studies may be needed.
- c) Step 6.2.3: establishment / improvement of distribution structures to facilitate the user access to reclaimed water.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2034.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: private sector, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Possible funding sources: EU, national and regional funding, private funding.

Priority area 7: Public acceptance.

- Action 7.1: **Promoting the citizenship participation.**

- a) Step 7.1.1: creation of an advertising campaign promoting the positive aspects of using reclaimed water, including healthiness and safety of the food produced with this resource.
- b) Step 7.1.2: contacting a personality from the region, close to the general public, who can articulate the correct message on the benefits of using reclaimed water as alternative fertiliser and attract the attention of the audience.
- c) Step 7.1.3: inserting institutional advertising in prime time.
- d) Step 7.1.4: making (general and specialised) information accessible through public websites.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2028.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: private sector, research centres, marketing companies, communication professionals, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Possible funding sources: EU, national and regional funding.

- Action 7.2: **Creation of communication campaigns for young students.**
 - a) Step 7.2.1: creation of communication campaigns at schools, and also via social networks, to engage the citizens since early age.
 - b) Step 7.2.2: creating communication materials adapted according to the different age groups, including also targeted influencers or referents.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2026.

Status: in process.

Responsible: private sector, research centres, marketing companies, communication professionals.

Possible funding sources: EU, national and regional funding.

- Action 7.3: **Creation of an official certificate on the products' circularity.**

The use of reclaimed water in food production represents a great advance in the framework of circular economy, thus it is necessary to not only recognise it, but also promote it. To achieve this, a circularity certificate could help consumers to identify the food that have been grown on a circular way.

 - a) Step 7.3.1: creation of a commission of experts to design the circularity certificate.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2034.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: private sector, research centres, Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Possible funding sources: EU, national and regional funding.

- Action 7.4: **Training and information for stakeholders involved in the decision-making process.**

It is necessary to provide information to sectorial stakeholders involved in the decision-making process, so they gain knowledge on the advantages and disadvantages of reclaimed water as alternative fertiliser, the application possibilities, etc. to decide on its use.

 - a) Step 7.4.1: creation of a regional training centre (online or presential).
 - b) Step 7.4.2: involvement of unions and agricultural associations to support this training and attack the stakeholders, as they are their first reference.

- c) Step 7.4.3: call from the regional government (Junta de Andalucía) for the specialisation in the use of regenerated water, making thus necessary this kind of training.
- d) Step 7.4.4: facilitation of this training by regional research institutions (IFAPA, LA Mayora, etc.), the authorised control bodies (OCAs), etc.
- e) Step 7.4.5: collaboration of qualified farmers willing to share their experience.
- f) Step 7.4.6: organisation of demonstration workshops, open days, etc.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2026.

Status: in process.

Responsible: private sector, research centres, marketing companies, communication professionals.

Possible funding sources: EU, national and regional funding.

Priority area 8: Environmental protection.

- Action 8.1: Emerging and other pollutants removal from reclaimed water.

- a) Step 8.1.1: implementing efficient equipment to remove emerging and other pollutants from reclaimed water. Emerging pollutants are causing increasing problems in water treatment processes. It is necessary to offer equipment that provides water quality not only in relation to biological parameters, but also in physical and chemical ones.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2026.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Environment and Water Agency of Andalusia, National Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Possible funding sources: EU, national and regional funding, private funding.

Conclusion:

The creation of a regional action plan contributes to make visible the potentialities and challenges faced, in this case, by Andalusia region to promote the use of reclaimed water as alternative fertiliser, being also very relevant not only because of agricultural exploitation, but also due to the water scarcity situation the region traditionally faces, which lately is becoming really critical. This makes the region an ideal setting for the exploration of alternative sources of water and circular schemes for the exploitation of resources.

The need to coordinate water policies at national and regional level is recognised, as well as to promote transparency in water quality controls. Investing in adequate infrastructure is crucial, which includes tertiary treatment plants, distribution schemes and reservoirs for water storage, so as to guarantee the success of regeneration projects for agricultural irrigation. Sustainable energy supply of water treatment is also very important.

Public acceptance for the success of regeneration projects in agriculture is extremely important, therefore the benefits of using reclaimed water have to be effectively communicated, from a positive narrative, eliminating its traditional negative image. To achieve this, civil society should be included in this process by being the main target of tailored communication campaigns combining traditional communication with experimental learning, what can help to increase confidence.

4.7. Spain – Catalonia

4.7.1. Methodology

The regional action plan involves all the relevant actors linked to the Catalonian-Aragon agri-food sector. The main actors involved are divided according to their type: private sector, research and innovation, public administration and society, as well as according to the point/s of the value chain where they are involved: generators of the by-products (livestock, agri-food industry, urban waste managers, sewage treatment plants), logistics companies, technology suppliers, fertilizers manufacturing industry, farmers, research and innovation, public administration and society. In addition to contacting them for specific Activities and Steps and having their feedback for the completion of the current Action Plan, they will be consulted for further steps or any adjustment they seem relevant. The involvement of the Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda is particularly important in the execution of this Action Plan and they are, together with other Departments of the Catalonian Government, promoters of many of the Actions and Steps proposed. As promoters, The Department will be responsible of coordinating the Actions while BETA CT will be supporting this coordination.

This Action plan was developed following relevant strategies developed in the last years within the Catalonian context. First, the Strategy for the Bioeconomy of Catalonia 2030 (or EBC2030) was developed to promote an efficient use of all natural resources and to apply innovation and technology to encourage the integral management and improve territorial development. This strategy defines 10 specific milestones or objectives to be achieved by 2030. From those objectives, some are relevant to boost uptake of alternative fertilising products. Second, the Catalonia Biogas Plan (CBP) was also consulted as it aims to valorise livestock and organic waste to obtain biogas and to take advantage of it for the generation of heat, electricity or biomethane, and biofertilisers. Additionally, to thoroughly cover this last part The Catalonian Digestate Plan (CDP) was created. In both Plans the main bottlenecks towards the development of the sector are identified together with the proposed measures in regulatory, economic and social dimensions to overcome them. The bottlenecks and proposed measures are extensive to other types of alternative fertilisers and therefore, inspired by the mentioned plans, the Action Plan was developed.

Additionally, having the main bottlenecks identified, the [PRO-FEM 2024](#) conference that was held in Vic on May 16th-17th permitted discussing them with all the relevant stakeholders involved. The topic of the conference was the potential for nutrient recovery, with presentations

on biogas or the valorisation of organic materials, but above all, the opportunities and threats surrounding this topic will be discussed. The discussion helped identifying potential measures and Actions that could be relevant to be included in the Regional Action Plan.

Figure 13. Invitation to the 1st NOVAFERT participatory workshop organised in Catalonia region, Spain

Figure 14. 1st NOVAFERT participatory workshop organised in Catalonia region, Spain

4.7.2. Regional Action Plan

The RSAP is structured, as already explained, in the 8 common priority areas identified in the GAP.

Priority area 1: Legal Framework.

- Action 1.1: **Revision of normative limitations towards promoting the construction of collective by-product valorisation plants in Catalonia.**

Limitations related to centralised manure-treatment are many times related to the minimum distance required between treatment plants and farms due to biosecurity issues. This is particularly relevant for biogas plants. Discussion of normative amendments between competent authorities will be promoted to reduce this distance.

- a) Step 1.1.1: evaluation and mapping on the manure treatment volume needed to be treated in these exceptional plants. Strategic distribution of plants in the territory.
- b) Step 1.1.2: establishment of some exceptions to be able to reduce the minimum distance between a by-product treatment/valorisation plant and livestock farms due to the real livestock management. Additionally, evaluation on exceptions to accept manure from the same epidemiological unit and of the same owner in an on-farm treatment system will be promoted.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2025.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda and the Spanish Ministry of agriculture, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biogas plant promoters, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres.

Possible funding sources: public funding from the Catalanian Government.

- Action 1.2: **Proposal to amend the National regulation on wastes (Law 7/2022) to determine an end point in the manufacture of fertilisers currently not included in EU regulation 2019/1009.**

- a) Step 1.2.1: amendment request.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: General Directorate of Agriculture and the Catalanian Waste Agency, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biogas plant promoters, composting companies, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres.

Possible funding sources: no funding needed.

- Action 1.3: **Proposal to amend the National regulation on wastes (Law 7/2022) to facilitate the utilisation of certain organic by-products in alternative fertilisers production and subsequent commercialisation.**

Sewage-sludge derived organic products (compost and digestate) and particularly those organic products produced from sludges generated in agri-food industry are relevant in this regard.

- a) Step 1.3.1: assess under which regulations the products resulting from their processing will be marketed. Identification of key materials currently not allowed to reach the end-of-waste status enabling their commercialisation.
- b) Step 1.3.2: data gathering on the effects (logistics, market perspective, business models) on the impact of the application of article 28 of the waste law on existing and new installations. This article makes impossible the establishment of the end-of-waste status of certain input materials. This step includes data gathering on the current market volume of such products.

- c) Step 1.3.3: compilation of quality and safety criteria and certificates for materials that cannot reach the end-of-waste status, to help give value to these materials that cannot be marketed as a product, also by consumers.
- d) Step 1.3.4: distribution and sharing of the data compiled. Discussion with the competent authority of the findings done to suggest a possible compromise solution.
- e) Step 1.3.5: propose the modification of the Waste Law 7/2022 to establish the end-of-waste status of the materials identified.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: steps 1.3.1-1.3.2, in process; step 1.3.3, awaiting; steps 1.3.4 and 1.3.5, in process.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, some sub-departments of Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, such as Waste Agency and Water Agency, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biogas plant promoters, composting companies, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres.

Possible funding sources: no funding needed.

- Action 1.4: **Recognition of RENURE (Recovered Nitrogen from Manures) products.**

- a) Step 1.4.1: transfer to the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture the convenience of using RENURE as analogous to mineral fertilisers.
- b) Step 1.4.2: develop and follow up of RENURE fertilisers (pilot testing and public funding to related projects).
- c) Step 1.4.3: assessing the possibility of including further derivatives of the digestate, in addition to the products accepted to meet the RENURE criteria, within the framework of the RENURE initiative.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: steps 1.4.1, in process; step 1.4.2, awaiting; steps 1.4.3, in process.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.

Possible funding sources: no funding needed.

- Action 1.5: **Promotion of alternative fertilisers in the sector of organic farming.**

- a) Step 1.5.1: unification of criteria for the definition of intensive farming, and assessing the efforts needed towards converting conventional farms in Catalonia into suitable rearing systems in organic farming sector. The modifications required to be assessed are mainly related to animal welfare and environmental conditions.
- b) Step 1.5.2: promotion of the representation of the Catalanian region in the technical expert groups advising the decision-making organisms related to the organic farming sector (EGTOP, EU CAP NETWORK, DG AGRI, DG ENV, etc.).

- c) Step 1.5.3: compilation of relevant data on quality and safety aspects of alternative fertilisers (chemical, physical, biological and pollutants of emerging concern such as pharmaceuticals) of the products obtained from the conventional farms and compare the composition of the components from the extensive farms

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, policy makers at regional, national and European level, particularly the competent authorities in organic farming issues (EGTOP; DG AGRI, DG ENVI), agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.

Possible funding sources: no funding needed.

- Action 1.6: **Promotion of the establishment of new end-points in the manufacturing chain in the framework of animal by-products regulation (Reg 1009/2009 and Implementing Regulation 142/2011).**
 - a) Step 1.6.1: creation of a working group with different entities in the sector (private sector, research centres, administration) to promote the incorporation of alternative methods of final points of the manufacturing chain (PCFC).
 - b) Step 1.6.2: encourage the generation of studies to incorporate new end points of the manufacturing chain (PCFC) through the inclusion in calls for funding for R+D+i projects.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Waste Agency of Catalonia, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.

Possible funding sources: no funding needed.

Priority area 2: Political willingness.

- Action 2.1: **Improve the characterisation, quantification and optimisation of generation and distribution of organic by-products or biomass (mentioned in EBC2030 and CBP).**
 - a) Step 2.1.1: elaboration of a guide according to the Waste Catalogue of Catalonia, to assist identifying the types of organic wastes and their codification, that could be processed in valorisation plants and what specifications these plants must meet.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2025.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalonian Waste Agency, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government, Waste Agency.

- b) Step 2.1.2: generation of information on the potential wastes that could be managed via certain technological processes (anaerobic digestion, stripping, composting etc.). This task includes the data gathering and mapping of the identified organic by-products.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2025.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Waste Agency, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government, Waste Agency.

- Action 2.2: **Development of a business network based on the circular bioeconomy throughout the territory, with special attention to the first sector and promotion of industrial symbiosis.**

To do so, Catalanian Bioeconomy Hub was already created, and relevant value chains identified.

- a) Step 2.2.1: development of the Catalanian Bioeconomy-Hub.
- b) Step 2.2.2: promotion of the consumption of the bioproducts obtained through adequate communication and marketing strategies, environmental declarations and labelling.
- c) Step 2.2.3: promotion of research, innovation and knowledge transfer related to circular bioeconomy. This includes research and innovation projects, start-ups, spin-off and scale-ups. To boost the transference of the knowledge generated, a program for the capitalisation of results should be foreseen together with advisory services for the whole value chain. For that, specific funding programs and financial incentives will be requested.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: step 2.2.1, completed; steps 2.2.2-2.2.3: in process.

Responsible: public administration, stakeholders from the whole value chain including industry, research and general society.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government.

- Action 2.3: **Promotion of the adoption of measures to shortening and simplifying the procedures for the licences for the valorisation plants for by-products.**

Specific measures to be considered would include those related to reducing deadlines, simplifying, and homogenising procedures and facilitating the interaction with the different administrations.

- a) Step 2.3.1: creation of a working group of the units involved in environmental, energy and urban processing.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2025.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda as main responsible, other several departments in the Catalanian Government like DG Environmental Quality and Climate Change, DG Energy, DG Agriculture and Livestock, DG Services, Water Agency, Waste Agency, DG Spatial Planning, Urbanism and Architecture and the Catalanian Institute of the Energy (ICAEN).

Possible funding sources: 1. Catalanian Government.

- b) Step 2.3.2: preparation of:
- A specific template for by-product valorisation projects with the minimum content to be included for presenting the projects to the competent environmental authority.
 - Orientation guide for the processing of projects addressed to promoters, to clarify which documentation must be presented and to which body.
 - Technical instruction for the procedures for the manufacture and marketing of alternative fertilisers products, including templates to facilitate and guide the presentation of documentation for such aim together with environmental authorisation.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2025.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda as main responsible, other several departments in the Catalanian Government like DG Environmental Quality and Climate Change, DG Energy, DG Agriculture and Livestock, DG Services, Water Agency, Waste Agency, DG Spatial Planning, Urbanism and Architecture and the Catalanian Institute of the Energy (ICAEN).

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government, Waste Agency.

- c) Step 2.3.3: revision of other legal requirements related to other normative frameworks that could potentially apply and integrate the requirements identified in the same procedure.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2025.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda as main responsible, other several departments in the Catalanian Government like DG Environmental Quality and Climate Change, DG Energy, DG Agriculture and Livestock, DG Services, Water Agency, Waste Agency, DG Spatial Planning, Urbanism and Architecture and the Catalanian Institute of the Energy (ICAEN).

Possible funding sources: no funding needed.

- d) Step 2.3.4: detailed description of the administrative procedures for the management and processing of the by-products and alternative fertilising products and

coordination of the different Departments and Agencies to unify criteria and have a single solution.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2025.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda as main responsible, other several departments in the Catalanian Government like DG Environmental Quality and Climate Change, DG Energy, DG Agriculture and Livestock, DG Services, Water Agency, Waste Agency, DG Spatial Planning, Urbanism and Architecture and the Catalanian Institute of the Energy (ICAEN).

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government, Waste Agency.

- Action 2.4: **Determine the targets to be accomplished and implementation model of recovered fertilisers in Catalonia.**

- a) Step 2.4.1: establishing the target of the treatment plants to be built in Catalonia by 2030.
- b) Step 2.4.2: estimation on the economic support for existing and new plants targeted.
- c) Step 2.4.3: establishing the management model for each of the plants foreseen (public, private) and estimation on the need (treatment capacity according to the volume generated) of infrastructure and its distribution across the region.
- d) Step 2.4.4: establishing quantitative and qualitative objectives for plants and identifying barriers followed by the planification of potential actions to overcome them.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2024.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government.

- Action 2.5: **Promotion of the creation of the Catalanian Platform of Nutrients.**

This action is aiming to include all the relevant stakeholders involved in the value chain of nutrients, from the generators of effluents rich in nutrients that can potentially be valorised, to the farmers who will be able to make use of these products, and all related industries. The timeline expected for this Action is 2 years starting from October 2024 and therefore, by the end of 2026 the Catalanian Platform of Nutrients should be formally established.

- a) Step 2.5.1: identification and mapping of the key actors involved in the whole nutrients' value chain.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2025.

Status: in process.

Responsible: generators of effluents rich in nutrients, farmers, related industries like suppliers of nutrient valorisation/recovery technologies, fertiliser producers, reference research centres, related associations, public administration.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government.

- b) Step 2.5.2: elaboration of the strategic plan, governance model and viability plan of the Catalanian Nutrient Platform.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2026.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: generators of effluents rich in nutrients, farmers, related industries like suppliers of nutrient valorisation/recovery technologies, fertiliser producers, reference research centres, related associations, public administration

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government.

- c) Step 2.5.3: legal establishment of the platform.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2026.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: generators of effluents rich in nutrients, farmers, related industries like suppliers of nutrient valorisation/recovery technologies, fertiliser producers, reference research centres, related associations, public administration

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government.

- Action 2.6: **Promotion of new accredited Notified Bodies for CMCs 3, 5, 12 and 13 in Catalonia.**

- a) Step 2.6.1: evaluate the conformity evaluation procedure as a bottleneck for the manufacture and marketing of fertiliser products derived from digestate.
- b) Step 2.6.2 development of a work plan with measures to facilitate and streamline the conformity assessment.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government.

Priority area 3: Research and technical development.

- Action 3.1: **Promotion of research projects related to experimentation and demonstration of the benefits of the use of alternative fertilisers in agricultural fields.**

- a) Step 3.1.1: promotion of demonstration projects in the experimental fields that the Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda holds for this kind of demonstration.

- b) Step 3.1.2: promotion of R&D&I projects in collaboration with other research institutions.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda is the responsible of this action while Waste Agency and the Catalonian Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology are also collaborating. Other key stakeholders will be also involved in this action: agricultural and livestock sector, agricultural, industrial, biogas plant promoters, companies marketing biofertilisers, research centres.

Possible funding sources: Catalonian Government, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production.

- Action 3.2: **Promotion of research projects towards demonstrating the feasibility of alternative processing methods towards the establishment of the end-point in the manufacturing chain of animal by-products (in the framework of Reg 1069/2009 and Implementing Regulation 142/2011).**

- a) Step 3.2.1: public calls for funding related to this topic.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalonian Waste Agency.

Possible funding sources: Catalonian Government, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production.

- Action 3.3: **Promotion of studies assessing the techno-economic feasibility of several organic by-product treatment systems.**

- a) Step 3.3.1: promotion of a specific funding program for the pre-feasibility of organic by-product treatment systems. This would include the assessment of the most suitable treatment technology or technologies, together with a techno-economic feasibility study.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

Possible funding sources: Catalonian Government, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production.

- Action 3.4: **Promotion of research and innovation studies focused on reducing the cost of treatment and valorisation of organic by-products and maximising their potential benefits.**

- a) Step 3.4.1: promotion of such studies.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production.

Priority area 4: New business models.

- Action 4.1: **Creation of rules for a Carbon credits market.**

A relevant number of the alternative fertilisers are known due to their capacity to increase the carbon soil and improve the texture. Carbon farming initiatives are a growing trend. Nonetheless, the rules and bases to allocate the fundings and to create a uniform market are not already developed.

- a) Step 4.1.1: other incentives based on the resources prevented.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

- Action 4.2: **Inclusion of sustainable nutrient management schemes in a certification system.**

This measure is specifically mentioned for digestate and manufacture and use of fertilizers from digestate, together with other organic materials (measure MD24 in the CDP).

- a) Step 4.2.1: inclusion of sustainable nutrient management schemes in a certification system.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

- Action 4.3: **Efforts to find synergies between livestock farmers, waste producers and nearby by-product treatment facilities towards developing new business models.**

- a) Step 4.3.1: promote conferences and technical meetings that can help create synergies, within the framework of the Bioeconomy Strategy of Catalonia 2030.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

- b) Step 4.3.2: creation of a figure within the Administration that facilitates synergies between these sectors.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

- c) Step 4.3.3: development of a digital platform to put into contact the waste/by-product producers with the manufacturers of fertilising products.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

- d) Step 4.3.4: provide a list of companies that provide digestate treatment technologies and manufacturers and marketers of organic fertiliser products, detailing the type of products they market.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, agricultural and livestock sector, industrial sector, biofertiliser manufacturers, research centres, etc.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

- Action 4.4: **Promoting the market of the alternative fertilisers obtained from post processing of organic by-products.**

- a) Step 4.4.1: promoting the quality of the alternative fertilisers to facilitate the development of the market for those products.
- b) Step 4.4.2: promoting technology implementation towards obtaining high quality fertilisers with potential to be competitive in the fertilising product market. Application of environmental labels.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: in progress.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

- Action 4.5: **Promotion of intermediate processing units and shared infrastructure schemes for the management, storage and concentration of nutrients in organic by-products.**

- a) Step 4.5.1: assessment of the techno-economic feasibility of the schemes proposed and their governance systems.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

Priority area 5: Financial incentives.

- Action 5.1: **Public administration provides economic incentives to build organic by-product treatment plants and to increase infrastructure for alternative fertiliser manufacturing plants.**

- a) Step 5.1.1: developing awareness campaigns to promote alternative fertilisers, contributing to the EU strategy “Farm to Fork” at the local and regional levels.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2026.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government already makes available public subsidies in 3 annual calls (budgets: 46M€ for 2024; 25M€ for 2025 and 9M€ for 2026) for new biogas plants (46M€) and digestate post-processing (3M€) in 2024.

- Action 5.2: **Articulation of public subsidies towards co-financing organic by-products treatment plants.**

- a) Step 5.2.1: articulation of public subsidies towards co-financing organic by-products treatment plants.

Timing: according to the Catalanian Government, a new budget line is foreseen for the same issue for the period between 2027 and 2030.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

Possible funding sources: according to the Catalanian Government, a new budget line is foreseen for the same issue for the period between 2027 and 2030.

Priority area 6: Self-sufficiency.

- Action 6.1: **Enhancement of the production of several bio-products by improving the operation of technological infrastructures.**

Energy generation would be particularly relevant in this line, in the Catalonian region via anaerobic digestion is being strongly promoted.

- a) Step 6.1.1: encourage the techniques and design the most efficient facilities on farms to improve the productivity of bio-products, including alternative fertilisers, and facilitate the transformation of current infrastructure to the ones better suited for circular bioeconomy.

Timing: according to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

Possible funding sources: Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

- Action 6.2: **Promotion of self-consumption in industry.**

- a) Step 6.2.1: promote the modification of the electricity self-consumption national regulation (Royal Decree 244/2019). This modification includes allowing the self-consumption of electricity at more than 500 meters for plants with self-production of energy such as biogas plants (limited in RD 244/2019) and allowing shared electricity self-consumption between an energy producer (from by-product treatment origin) and its associated consumers, at any distance between them.
- b) Step 6.2.2: in the case of anaerobic digestion plants, promote the use of biogas and biomethane by promoting the public purchase of the biomethane, the use of the biomethane by the heavy vehicles on interurban circuits and in industries, including the use of biomethane as an eligibility requirement to obtain public subsidies, improving the gas network infrastructure, etc.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalonian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda although other competent authorities in relation to renewable energy issues such as the Spanish Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge must be included in the decision making.

Possible funding sources: no funding needed.

- Action 6.3: **Incentives for the dependence reduction from third countries with geopolitical conflicts.**

Mineral fertilisers value chains are sourced in third countries because of the extraction of natural gas or phosphate ore. It is a geopolitical decision to enhance the use of nitrogen and phosphorous secondary sources.

- a) Step 6.3.1: promotion of RENURE products to reduce the dependency on synthetic mineral fertilisers.
- b) Step 6.3.2: promotion of phosphorus rich products such as struvite or similar to reduce the dependency on synthetic mineral fertilisers.

- c) Step 6.3.3: promotion of carbon-rich products (and biologically activated products or product with biostimulant effect) in agriculture to promote soils' health and its microbial activity to optimise the agricultural production limiting the use of nutrients.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia, Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production.

Priority area 7: Public acceptance.

- Action 7.1: **Promotion of the circular bioeconomy model, including the acceptance of organic by-product transformation technological processes and end products by the end-users and general society.**

A pedagogic formation of the benefits of the by-products transformation / valorisation technologies and particularly of alternative fertilisers is needed towards the acceptability of such and the change of the perception of waste to resource.

- a) Step 7.1.1: pedagogy in society to inform on the benefits of alternative fertiliser production from by-products such as of manure and organic waste. This step includes the preparation and publication of an annual balance of production and consumption of alternative fertilisers in Catalonia and the development of several specific infographics for to business associations and citizens.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalonia, Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, although other stakeholders should be also involved like research institutions, manufacturers of alternative fertilisers, farmers, industrial sector, other layers of public administration.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

- Action 7.2: **Promotion of workshops related to the alternative fertilisers in the framework of specific conferences and workshops.**

Some of these specific conferences and workshops are PRO-FEM conference, Bioeconomy Congress of Catalonia, PATT workshops (under the Annual Technological Transfer Plan Agricultural Training Program) organised by the Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda of the Catalanian government.

- a) Step 7.2.1: promotion of workshops related to the alternative fertilisers (from production step to the utilisation) in the framework of specific conferences and workshops.

Timing: these workshops have been promoted for some years and feedback is very positive regarding general acceptance of the topics presented. This action should be extended as long as it is required to improve the public acceptance of the alternative fertilisers.

Status: in process.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, research centres, manufacturers of alternative fertilisers, farmers and public administration.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Government, Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production.

Priority area 8: Environmental protection.

- Action 8.1: **Development of rules for eco-labelling.**

- a) Step 8.1.1: development of rules for eco-labelling.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

- Action 8.2: **Application of environmental sustainability labels (eco-labels).**

This Action is specifically proposed in the CBP. Several steps are required for that.

- a) Step 8.2.1: preparation of a manual or guide for the estimation of GHG emissions from alternative fertilisers manufacturing activities and the emission reduction achieved with the actions carried out.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2025.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Office for the Climate Change (OCCC) while it involves also other departments (Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production, Waste Agency, Water Agency) and research Institutions.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Office for the Climate Change.

- b) Step 8.2.2: estimation of GHG emissions from facilities generating biodegradable organic resources. Evaluation of the footprint and environmental risk of alternative fertilizers from the transformation of organic by-products.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2025.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Office for the Climate Change (OCCC) while it involves also other departments (Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production, Waste Agency, Water Agency) and Catalanian Institute of the Energy (ICAEN).

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

- c) Step 8.2.3: establishment of a public certification of the sustainability of agricultural holdings and animal husbandries.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2025.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda while other departments of the Catalanian Government are also involved (SG of Livestock, DG of Agri-Food Companies, Quality, and Gastronomy, Waste Agency), together with the research institutions.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

- d) Step 8.2.4: creation of a Sustainable Agricultural Production (SAP) label that contemplates the production and valorisation of the by-products generated, highlighting, in turn, those agricultural holdings that prioritise organic fertilisation and animal husbandries that encourage technological processes that obtain alternative fertilisers.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2025.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production in Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda while other departments of the Catalanian Government are also involved (SG of Livestock, DG of Agri-Food Companies, Quality, and Gastronomy, Waste Agency), together with the research institutions.

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda.

- Action 8.3: **Promotion of the implementation of Best Available Techniques (BAT) in the whole value chain of nutrients to avoid or minimise ammonia emissions.**

Accordingly, BAT for the storage and application methods of by-products/products should be promoted.

- e) Step 8.3.1: pedagogy.

Timing: to be accomplished by 2030.

Status: awaiting.

Responsible: Catalanian Office for the Climate Change (OCCC) while it involves also other departments (Department of Soil and Environmental Management of Agricultural Production, Waste Agency, Water Agency) and Catalanian Institute of the Energy (ICAEN).

Possible funding sources: Catalanian Office for the Climate Change.

Conclusion:

Most of the activities proposed are scheduled at long term and rely on the support of the regional authorities. In addition, a regional strong collaboration has been established with other projects and initiatives, like FERTIMANURE project.

5. General conclusions for the 7 target regions

The Regional Specific Action Plans (RSAPs) created by the NOVAFERT project represent a considerable effort to adapt the marketing and uptake of alternative fertilisers across seven European regions. Each region's action plan is systematically prepared to meet its own socioeconomic, environmental, and regulatory landscapes, reflecting the complexity and variability of challenges faced in the transition towards sustainable agricultural practices. The NOVAFERT initiative shows a localised approach to global environmental concerns, notably in terms of reducing dependency on synthetic fertilisers and promoting a circular economy.

Cross-Regional Insights and Impact

Across all seven regions, common themes emerge, including the need for stronger regulatory frameworks, increased public awareness, and the development of financial incentives to support the adoption of alternative fertilisers. The RSAPs collectively advocate for a shift in agricultural practices that not only meets local needs but also aligns with broader EU sustainability goals. By focusing on region-specific actions, the NOVAFERT project ensures that the transition towards sustainable fertilisation practices is both practical and effective, addressing the distinct challenges faced by each region.

In conclusion, the RSAPs provide a clear roadmap for each region to follow, ensuring that the lessons learned from the NOVAFERT project can be applied in a way that maximises local benefits while contributing to the global challenge of sustainable agriculture. These plans are dynamic and will continue to evolve as the regions implement the proposed actions, monitor their progress, and adapt to new developments and challenges in the agricultural sector.